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Federated Learning: Challenges, SoTA, Performance Improvements and Application Domains

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ABSTRACT Federated Learning has emerged as a revolutionary technology in Machine Learning (ML), enabling collaborative training of models in a distributed environment while ensuring privacy and security. This work discusses the topic of FL by providing insights into its various dimensions, perspectives, and components, leading to a comprehensive understanding of the technology. The survey begins by introducing the basic principles of FL and provides a high-level taxonomy of its methods. It continues by presenting application domains and associating challenges, categories and their applications. This mapping allows for an understanding of how particular challenges manifest in different contexts and applications. The main body delves into the various aspects of FL, including centralized and decentralized variants, methods for improving efficiency and effectiveness, and concerns regarding security, privacy, dynamic conditions, fairness, scalability and integration with other new technologies. Ultimately, the goal is to present recent advancements in these areas, along with new challenges and opportunities for future exploration. FL is poised to reshape the landscape of intelligent systems while promoting data privacy in decentralized and collaborative learning. Finally, this survey can serve as a reference point for methodological improvements as it highlights the strengths and weaknesses of existing approaches.

INDEX TERMS Federated learning, machine learning, artificial intelligence, distributed computing, distributed machine learning, decentralized learning, data heterogeneity, personalized federated learning, system heterogeneity, communication efficiency, security, privacy, fair federated learning, scalability, adaptive federated learning, adaptive algorithms.

I. Introduction

THE ever-evolving technological advancements continuously shape the landscape of business activities. In recent years, there has been a tremendous increase in businesses towards the adoption of state-of-the-art technological systems to maintain growth and remain competitive in the international market. Low-cost sensors, high-speed connectivity, the adoption of cloud solutions, and increased use of data analytics have

allowed the Internet of Things (IoT) sector to substantially contribute to the evolution of modern businesses, industry, and living.

As reported by Statista [1], the IoT market is expected to grow at an annual rate of 13.50% from 2023 to 2028, reaching a revenue of \$2,227.00bn in 2028. The segments of IoT that will dominate the sector, in descending order based on their market share, are Automotive (\$882.00bn), Industrial IoT (\$525.20bn), Con-

sumer IoT (\$231.70bn), Finance (\$204.30bn), Healthcare (\$167.70bn), and Smart Cities (\$165.80bn). IoT connects a myriad of devices and has managed to transform modern business, industry, and living, coinciding with the development of other key technologies like 5G and cloud computing. High-speed communication standards provide faster and more reliable connections among IoT devices. Although IoT is only one part of the big picture, its true potential lies in the analysis of vast streams of data and in facilitating intelligence in decision-making and automation.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the brain behind the IoT sector. AI processes the vast volumes of data generated by IoT and provides meaningful insights and knowledge utilized in decision-making and automation. The combination of AI with IoT produces smart applications and devices. However, the integration of IoT and AI is not straightforward. The massive data from myriad distributed IoT devices requires vast resources for storage and analysis, rendering usage in the cloud nearly infeasible. Fueled by these challenges, Cloud Computing has extended to Edge Computing, moving processing closer to the data to avoid latency and reduce communication costs. Yet, Edge Computing presents two significant challenges: edge devices have limited computational capabilities and cannot be used for complex AI computations, and the collection of data generated from IoT devices raises significant concerns regarding privacy and security. Additionally, policies like the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [2], adopted by the European Union (EU), impose strict rules on how users' personal data can be processed and transferred. This is where FL completes the picture.

FL is a distributed machine learning algorithm that can operate with a central server (centralized variant) or in a fully decentralized manner, without a server coordinating the training (decentralized variant). FL aims to collaboratively train a model across multiple devices or edge nodes without the need to collect raw data in a central location. This method, introduced by Google [3], trains a shared machine learning model on the data of millions of clients in a privacy-preserving manner. FL's unique feature of collaborative training on distributed datasets and the use of models on the edge brings forth various important advantages. First and foremost, it enhances data protection since raw data does not need to leave the device. It saves resources, as distributed storage and processing of data significantly reduce bandwidth and energy consumption, while a large central server with extreme processing capabilities is not required. Since models reside on the edge, inference is done without needing to communicate with a central server, promoting real-time continual learning simultaneously. These characteristics allow leveraging the distributed nature of IoT to efficiently scale AI applications.

The integration of FL in IoT has been adopted by various industries, offering novel intelligent, efficient and secure systems in several domains. These include smart and self-adjusting vehicles with enhanced safety and performance, manufacturing that can automatically adapt to real-time conditions, healthcare AI applications without exposing sensitive patient information, tailored financial services and fraud detection, and optimized traffic management and energy consumption for responsive and sustainable urban centers.

IoT, AI, and FL are forging new frontiers in how data is processed, analyzed, and utilized. This triad of technologies is not just reshaping industries but also redefines the interaction between humans and machines, posing not just a technological advancement but a paradigm shift. FL's diverse application domains and categories each with its own set of challenges, requiring specialized methods to address them. Existing methods provide a variety of techniques to tackle these challenges. This survey establishes an association between the categories, challenges and application domains as well as the techniques proposed by the literature to address them. Moreover, it aims to serve as a reference point for methodological improvements by highlighting the strengths of the existing methods documented in the literature.

II. Contribution

Aiming to discuss the full spectrum of FL, related research was divided into five high-level categories focused on the challenges of FL: algorithmic, heterogeneity, communication, security and fairness. Based on these five categories, a categorization is provided in Table 1, which highlights the focus of related survey studies on FL technology.

A. General discussion FL surveys

One of the first surveys on FL [32] identified initial FL challenges including issues related to communication, heterogeneity, and privacy preservation. The work in [21] provides an end-to-end detailed analysis of every challenge faced in various FL system settings, as well as methods to address them. It also considers system challenges faced during the deployment of such systems. The work in [25] briefly presents challenges regarding optimization, heterogeneity, and security, and mentions certain domains where FL is applied. The work in [19] provides a thorough theoretical analysis of every aspect of FL but does not include any application domain nor maps the analysis to real-case scenarios. In [22], the classification of existing challenges is fine-grained, adding client selection, resource management, and training service pricing. The work in [24] presents a new classification of existing research concerning four main areas: system model and design, application areas, privacy, security and resource management. The work in

TABLE 1. FL surveys comparison

Ref.	FL Challenges	SoTA	SoTA Metrics	Applications	Future Research Directions
[4]	X	X	✓	Smart cities	✓
[5]	Security	✓	X	X	✓
[6]	Security	✓	X	X	✓
[7]	Security	✓	X	X	✓
[8]	Security, Communication, Heterogeneity	✓	X	Healthcare, Recommended System, Smart City, Finance and Insurance, Edge Computing, Intrusion detection	✓
[9]	Heterogeneity	✓	X	X	X
[10]	Decentralized	✓	X	Healthcare, Industry, Mobile services, Military, Vehicles	✓
[11]	Decentralized	✓	X	X	✓
[12]	Statistical heterogeneity	✓	X	X	✓
[13]	Heterogeneity, Privacy	X	X	Artificial intelligence, IoT, Blockchain, NLP, Autonomous vehicles, resource allocation, Data science, Healthcare, Education	✓
[14]	Security, Communication, Heterogeneity, Hardware	✓	X	Healthcare, Unmanned Aerial Vehicles	✓
[15]	Security, Communication, Resource allocation	✓	X	IIoT, smart agriculture, smart energy, healthcare	✓
[16]	Communication, Heterogeneity, Privacy, Fairness, Energy consumption, Scallability	✓	X	Resource-efficient, Resource-constraint	✓
[17]	Optimization, Communication, Security	✓	X	Mobile application, Browser history ranking, object detection, healthcare, anomaly detection, augmented reality	✓
[18]	X	X	X	IoT	X
[19]	Security, Communication, Heterogeneity, Efficiency, Fairness	✓	✓	X	✓
[20]	Security, Communication	✓	X	X	✓

TABLE 1. FL surveys comparison – continued from previous page

Ref.	FL Challenges	SoTA	SoTA Metrics	Applications	Future Research Directions
[21]	Optimization, Heterogeneity, Communication, Security, Fairness, System challenges	✓	✗	✗	✓
[22]	Optimization, Communication, Security, Heterogeneity, Service pricing, Client selection	✓	✗	✗	✓
[23]	Optimization, Communication, Privacy, Scalability, Incentives	✓	✗	✗	✗
[24]	Optimization, Communication, Privacy, Statistical heterogeneity	✓	✗	Gboard, Healthcare, IoT	✓
[25]	Optimization, Heterogeneity, Security	✓	✗	Mobile services, IoT, Finance, NLP	✓
[26]	Optimization, Heterogeneity	✓	✗	✗	✓
[27]	Asynchronous	✓	✗	✗	✓
[28]	Statistical Heterogeneity	✓	✗	✗	✓
[29]	Decentralized	✓	✗	✗	✓
[30]	Optimization, Communication, Fairness, Meta-learning	✓	✗	✗	✓
[31]	Optimization, Communication, Fairness, Meta-learning	✓	✗	Cyberattack Detection, Edge Caching and Computation Offloading, Base Station Association, Vehicular Networks	✓
This work	Communication, Heterogeneity, Security	✓	✓	✓	✓

[14] covers most of the identified challenges of the FL system but limits the discussion of applications on edge devices to healthcare and unmanned aerial vehicles. The work in [13] focuses more on the technical details and applications of FL. The work in [17] aims to present FL architectures, hardware used, and real use-case scenarios in detail. In [8], challenges related to security, communication, and heterogeneity are discussed, along with various applications of FL. The work in [23] explores FL from a systems point of view, including information about building an FL system and presenting the components required for a complete and efficient system.

B. Targeted surveys of FL aspects

1) Decentralized FL

The surveys in [10] and [11] provide a taxonomy, analysis of challenges and state-of-the-art methods for decentralized FL. Additionally, [10] presents various implementations of DFL in a number of domains such as healthcare and industry. The survey presented in [29] provides a literature review in main challenges of the DFL setting and evaluates whether the methods resolve the identified problems.

2) Heterogeneity

The survey in [9] provides an analysis of the heterogeneity challenges in FL. Similarly, the survey in [28] presents a thorough analysis of statistical heterogeneity, as well as methods to address them. In a similar vein, [12] and [26] focus exclusively on statistical heterogeneity. However, the work in [26] delves into the more specific area of Personalized FL, where the goal is not to optimize for a single global model but to have a different final model on each device.

3) Security

The survey in [7] addresses the security aspects of a FL (FL) system and presents a taxonomy of threats and defenses that can be employed to address security challenges in FL. Another security-focused survey is presented in [5], which includes a more thorough taxonomy regarding privacy-preserving FL. Meanwhile, the survey in [6] describes challenges in safeguarding the security of an FL system, as well as use cases where FL can be employed to address security threats in a network

4) Asynchronous FL

The work in [27] regards challenges related specifically with asynchronous FL systems.

5) Meta-Learning and FL

The work in [30] provides a review of the advancements in FL, meta-learning and Federated meta-learning. Even though the authors present a review of FL they do not include information about the performance gains reported by the methods presented nor include a mapping of challenges to specific application domains.

6) Application domains

a: General IoT

In [15], the authors explore literature in the FL (FL) domain for IoT and present challenges associated with security, communication, and resource allocation. In addition, specific challenges are identified and paired with methods that address them. The work presented in [16] focuses more on resource-constrained IoT devices and outlines challenges associated with traditional areas such as communication, heterogeneity, efficiency, privacy, and fairness, as well as challenges associated with limited resources like energy consumption, scheduling, and scalability. Moreover, the applications presented in this work concern exclusively resource-constrained and resource-sufficient applications. The study in [18] also focuses on IoT, specifically examining applications that could benefit from FL. These applications include data sharing, data offloading, attack detection, localization, mobile crowdsensing, and IoT network security. Additionally, it presents several domains where IoT and FL are employed. A taxonomy for FL in the IoT field, alongside the state of the art for challenges that FL systems face in security and communication efficiency, is presented in [20].

b: Smart Cities

In [4], the authors present state-of-the-art methods in FL within the context of smart cities, covering a number of different aspects. These include healthcare, smart grids, governance, disaster management, industries, and the use of UAVs for monitoring a smart city.

c: Mobile Edge Networks

In [31], the survey presents a comprehensive overview of state-of-the-art in FL within mobile edge networks, including opportunities, challenges, and applications in this rapidly evolving field. Applications include cyberattack detection, edge caching and computation offloading, base station association, and IoV.

The aforementioned surveys provide a comprehensive overview of FL systems, their taxonomy, and key challenges and solutions. Many surveys illustrate applications and use cases, offering insights into the practical implications and benefits of FL in real-world scenarios. Lastly, most of them provide useful insights regarding future research directions.

Given the fast-paced advancement of technology especially in the domain of IoT and network communications, surveys and methods described can quickly become outdated. Furthermore, surveys being focused only on a specific aspect of the FL technology can contribute by delving into more details behind specific challenges, but they are not able to provide a complete overview of the field. Moreover, while FL theoretical aspects are often well described in related works, the practical comparison of state-of-the-art methods and their technological benefits and gaps remains underrepresented. Although existing works significantly contribute towards the understanding and development of FL, there is a significant need for demonstrating the overall evolution of the FL technology and highlighting its advancements, as well as identifying challenges that remain unresolved in this field. This study contributes to the field by:

- Provide an updated taxonomy on FL systems that incorporates new trends in FL methods.
- Include a categorization of the challenges presented in such systems, along with methods used to address them.
- Present advancements in evaluation metrics as reported by the authors, providing a quick and easy reference for tests that verify their claims, identify state-of-the-art methods recognized by the scientific community, and outline limitations of the presented methods.
- Offer an updated review that includes the latest methods proposed in the field.
- Highlight several areas for future research based on the latest trends and methods proposed in the literature.

III. Fundamentals

Centralized FL regards the traditional approach presented by Google [3] and regards an FL system in the cross-device setting that trains a model for the next keyword prediction in Gboard. The network topology, Fig. 4, consists of a *Star* where the central node is the parameter server and among other responsibilities is responsible for the orchestration of the training procedure. Other entities that exist in a FL system are the client devices, occasionally also referred to as nodes. In contrast to decentralized FL setting the client devices communicate only with the server. Fig. 1 shows the high level architecture of the centralized FL with various devices connected to the parameters server and the exchanged information between them. Specifically, depicts that the parameter server sends the same model to all the devices, w_t , and receives the gradients of the local update from each client Δw_t^i where i is the index of each client.

A typical implementation of the FL algorithm consists of four steps [21], Fig. 2:

FIGURE 1. FL High-level Architecture

- **Client selection:** A subset of the available clients is selected for participation in the upcoming round.
- **Configuration:** Instructions regarding the training procedure are sent to the selected clients.
- **Local training:** Devices train the global on their local dataset and report the updates.
- **Aggregation:** The collected local models are aggregated to form the next version of the global model.

The steps are repeated until the number of rounds defined has been completed or until the model has reached the requested level of performance. The main responsibilities of the entities are the following:

Server

- Orchestrates the training procedure.
- Selects the clients that will participate in the following round.
- Distributes the global model.
- Collects the client's updates.
- Performs aggregation on the collected updates and provides the updated version of the global model.

Client

- Declares availability to the server.
- Receives training instructions and the latest version of the global model.
- Performs training on the local data using as the initial point the global model from the server.
- Reports updates for the global model to the server.

The complete pseudo-code of the Federated Averaging (FEDAVG) [3] algorithm that describes the actions performed by each entity is presented in Algorithm 1.

IV. Categorization and Taxonomy

FL systems have been traditionally categorized according to data distribution or according to the type of the involved entities. However, recent research has introduced

TABLE 2. FL Taxonomy

Taxonomy	Category	Description
Data Distribution	Horizontal FL	Different devices hold different data instances of the same features (e.g., different clients in a banking context)
	Vertical FL	Different devices hold different features of the same data instances (e.g., medical records)
Environment	Cross Device	Mobile or IoT devices, large volume of participating clients, very low availability and very unreliable
	Cross Silo	Organizations and Institutions, relatively small number of participating clients, clients are considered reliable and almost always available
Architecture	Centralized	Clients collaboratively train a model under coordination of the central server.
	Decentralized	Clients collaboratively train a model without relying on a central server employing peer-to-peer communication.
Coordination	Synchronous	Participating clients have to send their model updates within a set time window before proceeding to the aggregation.
	Asynchronous	Clients send their model updates independently and at different times, no waiting for all participants to finish is required for aggregation.

FIGURE 2. FL Protocol

new algorithms that extend this categorization to include the system's architecture and the aggregation pattern as well. Fig. 3 illustrates the taxonomy identified.

A. Data Distribution Taxonomy

The data distribution taxonomy categorizes FL systems based on the partitioning and distribution characteristics of the data among participating nodes, as described in [33]. Datasets consist of samples and their respective features. Features are the measurable properties and characteristics of a sample, typically corresponding to the columns in a dataset. Samples consist of observations or data points and typically correspond to the rows in a dataset. If we consider a different set of samples and features for each participating client, it is possible, depending on the context of the problem, for these clients to not share the same feature and/or sample space.

- In **Horizontal FL**, the involved nodes share the same feature space but not the same sample space. For example, consider two hospitals in different regions trying to improve a disease prediction model.

Algorithm 1 Federated Averaging. The K clients are indexed by k ; B is the local mini-batch size, E is the number of local epochs, T is the number of total rounds and η is the learning rate.

```

Server executes:
initialize  $w_0$ 
for each round  $t = 1, 2, \dots$  do
     $m \leftarrow \max(C \cdot K, 1)$ 
     $S_t \leftarrow$  (random set of  $m$  clients)
    for each client  $k \in S_t$  clients do
         $w_{t+1}^k \leftarrow \text{ClientUpdate}(k, w_t)$ 
    end for
     $m_t \leftarrow \sum_{k \in S_t} n_k$ 
     $w_{t+1} \leftarrow \sum_{k \in S_t} \frac{n_k}{m_t} w_{t+1}^k$ 
end for
    
```

end for

```

ClientUpdate( $k, w$ ): //Run on client  $k$ 
 $B \leftarrow$  (split  $P_k$  into batches of size  $B$ )
for each local epoch  $i$  from 1 to  $E$  do
    for batch  $b \in B$  do
         $w \leftarrow w - \eta \nabla l(w; b)$ 
    end for
end for
    
```

In this case, both hospitals have datasets containing information about the same properties, such as age, symptoms, test results, etc. (the same feature space), but each hospital deals with different patients (a different sample space). Usually horizontal FL applications regard the participation of many devices and naturally the data do not follow the same distribution in every device.

- In **Vertical FL**, the involved nodes share the same sample space but not the same feature space. For example, consider a manufacturer of industrial ma-

chines and a production facility that uses these machines in its production line, both trying to improve their predictive maintenance models. In this scenario, both the manufacturer and the production facility store information about the same machines (the same sample space). However, the manufacturer keeps extensive data regarding the technical specifications, design aspects, and simulation results, while the production facility stores real-time operational data, performance metrics of the machines, and environmental conditions of the facility (a different feature space). Usually vertical FL applications regard different entities and naturally the available resources are considered different.

- In **Transfer Learning**, the involved nodes do not share either the feature or the sample space. This situation can arise in various contexts. For exam-

ple, consider a bank and an e-commerce company in different regions trying to improve the bank's credit score system. In this scenario, the bank holds information regarding account balances, past loans, and credit card payments, while the e-commerce company has data on its customers' shopping behaviors (a different feature space). Even though the customers of the e-commerce company are not the same as the bank's (a different sample space), the bank can still benefit from the insights gleaned from the shopping behavior data of the e-commerce company's customers. Usually transfer FL applications regard transfer of knowledge between two entities and naturally the available resources are considered different.

FIGURE 3. Federated Learning taxonomy.

B. Deployment Environment Taxonomy

The deployment environment taxonomy categorizes FL systems based on the characteristics and limitations imposed by their specific deployment environments. For instance, consider a scenario aiming to train a model for next-word prediction, as discussed in [3], involving millions of mobile devices. This scenario differs significantly from a system that learns from a model trained on hospital data. In these two examples, the primary factors impacting the systems include the type, number, availability, and reliability of the clients. From these considerations, two distinct categories emerge:

- The **Cross Device** category pertains to cases where there is an abundance of clients, but only a small fraction of them are available at any given time, and their reliability is not guaranteed. This category includes the example of next-word prediction in Gboard, as well as applications in the IoT field, where data from a multitude of devices participate in training. Given the large number of participating clients, the variety of systems and resources in terms of computation and networking, and the diverse distribution of data, the critical challenges in cross-

device settings include addressing communication efficiency, system heterogeneity, and data heterogeneity.

- The **Cross Silo** category pertains to siloed data, typically found in organizations such as hospitals and banks, rather than in small devices or in IoT settings. Laws often prevent the disclosure of this data; thus, Cross Silo FL aims to train shared models while ensuring privacy. In these cases, the participating clients are usually reliable and available, and their numbers are limited, contrasting with the Cross Device setting. In this scenario, the anticipated number of participating devices is expected to be small, with similar available resources and stable network connections available. However, the even distribution of training samples cannot be guaranteed.

C. Architecture Taxonomy

The taxonomy of architecture has emerged in response to real-world use cases that demonstrate the need to reduce reliance on a central parameter server.

- In the **Centralized FL** category, regards the traditional FL approach, where a parameter server is responsible for aggregating and distributing the global model. This setup follows a star network topology with the parameter server at the center. The main challenges in the centralized setting stem from the central server's requirement to perform optimally, even when devices with diverse available resources participate. Therefore, critical challenges in this setting include communication efficiency and system heterogeneity of participating devices.

FIGURE 4. Centralized FL Topology

- In the **Decentralized FL** category, there is no central parameter server. Instead, aggregation occurs directly among the participating clients. The network topologies in this category can vary based on the characteristics of the use case and the algorithm implemented for communication and aggregation. The absence of a central server responsible for managing the participating clients introduces several challenges associated with the selection of clients in each round, thereby also influencing fairness in the process. The lack of centralization also hinders data sampling in clients. Lastly, changes in the communication topology can impact the effectiveness of communication between the clients due to the added complexity.

FIGURE 5. Decentralized FL - Fully connected network (Mesh) Topology

D. Coordination Taxonomy

The taxonomy of coordination has emerged specifically to address the issue of stragglers in FL systems. The 'straggler effect' refers to clients that are significantly slower than the rest in sending their local updates back to the server. This latency can occur for various reasons, such as the limited computational capabilities of the devices and unreliable or slow network connectivity.

- **Synchronous.** In synchronous FL, all the clients in a round must send their local updates before proceeding to the aggregation of the shared model. It is essential for such systems to employ techniques that alleviate the straggler effect. One commonly used method is client redundancy, where tasks are dispatched to more clients than necessary. This approach ensures that there are enough updates at the end of each round to proceed with aggregation, even in the presence of stragglers. The straggler effect primarily arises from two challenges: unstable network conditions or bandwidth limitations, and limited computational resources. Therefore, the critical challenges that need to be addressed in this category are communication efficiency and system heterogeneity.
- **Asynchronous.** In asynchronous FL, clients are allowed to send their updates asynchronously. While this approach mitigates the straggler effect, efficient algorithms must be employed to handle on-the-fly aggregation. Furthermore, coordinating clients in an asynchronous manner introduces an additional layer of complexity to data sampling and client selection algorithms, consequently impacting systems fairness. Finally, security and privacy algorithms typically consider the synchronous FL setting, and this added complexity also affects these system aspects.

V. Application domains

FL has been widely adopted in numerous applications across numerous domains. Keeping data locally and synchronizing the training procedure of a model across multiple devices, leverages the benefits of edge computing. These benefits include efficiency, privacy and security, all highly valued features in real-world applications. Consequently, this fosters the uptake of FL technology by organizations that handle sensitive data in various industries. Several domains that FL has demonstrated its efficacy and strength are briefly presented below:

Internet of Things IoT witnessed a rapid growth in the recent years. IoT provides sensing and computing capabilities from a wide range of things connected over the internet. These capabilities facilitate the collection of data which, when combined with artificial intelligence techniques, yield useful insights and enable the training of efficient models. Traditionally, data storage and model

training has been centralized in cloud servers or data centers. However, the vast growth of data collected by IoT devices has highlighted significant limitations in this approach. FL being a distributed collaborative training approach is well-suited for smart devices and IoT. IoT applications can be found in a variety of domains such as smart cities [34], industry [35], agriculture [36] etc.

Healthcare Data privacy is a paramount factor in healthcare and its applications. Training models collaboratively without exposing THE medical information of the clients has been utilized in disease prediction [37], personalized health recommendations and health monitoring applications [38]. By considering the characteristics of two use cases in the healthcare domain, we can identify the challenges most impacted by the taxonomy, and thus, the solutions that should be taken considered during the development and deployment of these solutions. Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 depict the categories associated with each application as well as the challenges affected the most. The first use case Fig. 6 regards a cross-device, asynchronous, horizontal and decentralized application.

FIGURE 6. Cross-device healthcare use case application, categories and primary challenges.

The second use case Fig. 7 regards a cross-silo, synchronous, horizontal and centralized application.

FIGURE 7. Cross-silo healthcare use case application, categories and primary challenges.

Smart Cities Rapid growth of urban population has lead to the emergence of new challenges associated with traffic, environment, health, energy and many others. In combination with IoT, numerous applications have emerged to address these challenges by recognizing hidden patterns and extracting valuable knowledge from IoT data. Sensors in smart cities collect data from the public, and is crucial to comply with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [2], making FL ideal for this domain. Moreover, not collecting the vast amount of data generated by sensors yields benefits not only in security but also in network bandwidth by reducing the communication overhead incurred. In [39], an FL system of computer vision-based safety monitoring solution is presented. In Fig. 8 the taxonomy and the respective challenges for this use case are presented.

FIGURE 8. Smart-city safety monitoring use case application, categories and primary challenges.

Industry There are several benefits that manufactures can gain from FL in ensuring privacy while reducing their cost. Privacy concerns are addressed by ensuring that data remains confidential and under the control of its owner while training a model collaboratively across multiple parties. Moreover, manufactures might not be able to produce the volume of data required to train an efficient model; FL allows them to leverage knowledge from other companies. In addition, small manufacturers often have limited resources which prevents them from operating and managing a private cloud. Such constraints can be alleviated by FL allowing them to participate with other manufacturers in the collective training of the models without significantly increasing costs. Adoption of FL in the industry includes applications regarding predictive maintenance [40], [41], quality inspection [41], supply chain management [42] and others. The supply chain risk prediction FL system in [42] can be categorized as shown in Fig. 9, and the relevant challenges should be considered.

Agriculture FL offers several benefits to agriculture and agricultural management. Agriculture, which also involves sensitive data, can reap the benefits offered by the distinctive features of FL. Decentralized computation on

FIGURE 9. Smart-industry supply chain risk prediction use case application, categories and primary challenges.

FIGURE 11. Smart-finance credit and risk rating use case application, categories and primary challenges.

edge devices minimizes the dependence on a centralized infrastructure and enhances the utilization of available resources, making it suitable for remote agricultural areas with resource constraints. Lastly, the ability of FL to incorporate knowledge from diverse sources enables the development of customized solutions in a variety of agricultural challenges, such as crop yield prediction [43], disease detection [44], among others. Fig. 10 depicts the categorization and challenges of the federated crop yield prediction system presented in [43].

FIGURE 10. Smart-agriculture crop yield prediction use case application, categories and primary challenges.

large-scale analysis of educational data. FL has the ability to promote the evolution of education through secure and private AI enabled applications. These applications include large-scale analysis of students data in a private manner [46], student dropout prediction [47], course recommendation for online education platforms [48] and others. Fig. 12 illustrates the taxonomy and challenges that need to be addressed in a federated dropout prediction system like the one presented in [47].

FIGURE 12. Education dropout use case application, categories and primary challenges.

Finance and Insurance The finance and insurance industry is another sector where privacy is of paramount importance. FL has allowed the development of collaborative intelligence solutions enabling financial institutions to utilize and analyze big data cooperatively [45]. The applications developed in this field include risk control by improving predictions of customer credit score, fraud prevention, and others. Fig. 11 illustrates the categorization and challenges of a federated credit and risk prediction application across different finance organizations.

Education FL has been utilized by educational institutions in various cases, particularly in addressing concerns related to privacy of the students while enabling

Cyber-security Artificial intelligence has been widely used in the field of cyber-security though it is often infeasible due to limitations in computational resources and privacy concerns. FL mitigates these limitations by allowing businesses to train effective security-related AI models collaboratively without exposing valuable data. Moreover, FL can leverage the computational capabilities of edge devices, making it a resource-efficient solution for training models over big data. In addition the growth of IoT in the recent years has promoted the development of Federated Security a concept addressing security challenges in the IoT domain. Applications in the domain include user authentication [49], intrusion detection systems (IDS) [50], malware detection [51], data collaboration [52], security through honeynets [53]

and a plethora of various applications to ensure security and privacy. Fig. 13 illustrates the taxonomy and challenges that need to be addressed in a federated intrusion detection system such as the one presented in [50].

FIGURE 13. Cyber-security intrusion detection system use case application, categories and primary challenges.

Military The IoT domain has revolutionized many areas, and recently, the concept of Internet of Battle Things (IoBT) has gained significant attention in defense systems. The deployment of sensors and smart devices in combat scenarios enables the development of intelligent defense solutions. In this context, the privacy and security of the systems are paramount and the unique characteristics of FL can be employed to safeguard them and provide collective intelligence from the data collected by the deployed devices [54]. Fig. 14 illustrates the taxonomy and challenges that need to be addressed in a federated defence system such as the one presented in [54].

FIGURE 14. Military defence system use case application, categories and primary challenges.

Smart Vehicles & Unmanned Aerial Vehicles Same as in previous domains, smart vehicles collect sensitive data, such as location and driving behavior, which must remain private. Vehicles are also susceptible to changes in road conditions and need to be able to adapt in real-time. Moreover, they have limited resources making efficient utilization essential. Additionally, the

presence of multiple smart vehicles on the roads and sensors in smart cities enables smart vehicles to leverage collaborative intelligence to improve their models with unknown knowledge. Taking into consideration the above characteristics of smart vehicles it is evident that FL can be utilized to improve their efficiency. Applications in this field include vehicle trajectory and collision prediction [55], driver behavior analysis [56], energy management in networks of electric vehicles [57] and many others.

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), a rapidly developing subdomain of smart vehicles, exhibit several characteristics that have promoted the adoption of FL in this domain. Often UAVs collect sensitive information making privacy a major concern so algorithms should be able to protect them. A UAV typically has limited communication bandwidth rendering the uploading of large amounts of raw data to a central server infeasible. UAVs usually operate in different environments and should have the ability to adapt their models to new conditions. Additionally, UAVs can participate in collaborative missions in coordination with other UAVs. Overall, FL offers a suitable solution where privacy is safeguarded by design, raw data remain on the device and communication cost is reduced, iterative learning enables the UAVs to adapt to changes in the environment and allows them to collaboratively improve their models with knowledge from data of other UAVs. Applications include joint scheduling and resource management [58], coordinated trajectory planning [59], cooperative image classification [60] and many others. Fig. 15 presents the taxonomy and challenges that need to be addressed in a trajectory planning and cooperative target recognition application, like those presented in [55], [59].

FIGURE 15. Trajectory planning and cooperative target recognition use case application, categories and primary challenges.

Mobile services The FL paradigm was first introduced by Google to improve the GBoard's next word prediction model [3] leveraging data from many devices in a privacy-preserving manner. The aim was to harness collaborative intelligence and transfer knowledge from data existing on other devices. Similarly, many

mobile services employ FL to reap the same benefits such as SMS spam classification [61]. Fig. 16 illustrates the taxonomy and challenges in a federated next word prediction application similar to [3].

FIGURE 16. Mobile services next word prediction use case application, categories and primary challenges.

VI. Decentralized approach

FL still faces major drawbacks due to centralized processing. Therefore, one of the categories identified in the literature regarding FL systems is DFL. In contrast to traditional CFL settings, DFL does not require a central server to collect and aggregate the client updates. While some DFL applications may include a central server, it is used only for orchestration purposes, not for aggregation. There are several benefits provided by the absence of the server such as:

- **Not a central point of failure:** In CFL, the server is prone to attacks and system failures. A failure in the central server renders the system non-functional. In contrast, DFL can handle the failure of multiple edge nodes without compromising the training procedure.
- **Adaptability and System Heterogeneity:** A DFL system can more easily adapt to issues related to dropout clients and stragglers, making it more aligned to real-world scenarios.
- **Scalability:** The central server not only presents a vulnerability but also a bottleneck to the system. Additionally, it must scale according to the number of participating clients.

To achieve successful system implementation of a DFL, several unique aspects and parameters must be considered. These considerations introduce new taxonomies specifically designed for DFL.

- **Traditional peer-to-peer networks:** The study of decentralized systems where peers, or clients in the context of FL, communicate directly with each other without the need for a central authority.
- **Blockchain-infused methods:** Blockchain technology and its distinctive features are capable of

mitigating several issues in the FL context, making the combination natural. It has been adopted by various approaches as a way to perform aggregation and ensure trustworthiness in a decentralized FL system.

A. Communication protocols

The protocols developed for distributed systems are leveraged to achieve decentralization in FL. The specific characteristics and limitations of each use case, combined with the distinctive attributes of each protocol, dictate the appropriate protocol to be used.

- **Point-to-point** is the simplest form of communication between two peers.
- **Gossip, or rumor style**, inspired by social gossip processes, is a well accepted and widely used protocol in the context of DFL [62], [63], prized for its simplicity and fault tolerance. The peer randomly selects another peer to exchange information with and the information rapidly spreads over the network through successive iterations.
- **Broadcast**, is a peer-to-all method where each peer sends its information to all the other peers. It is also a simple and effective method that has been adopted in the context of DFL [64].
- **All reduce protocol**, commonly used in parallel and distributed computing, serves as a collective communication mechanism. In this process, each participating peer contributes a value, and upon completion, the result of the specified operation is returned to all peers. Compared to gossip protocol, all-reduce is more consistent and faster. However, it lacks the fault tolerance and scalability of gossip algorithms. Nonetheless, newer implementations of all-reduce aim to address these limitations making the protocol suitable for the context of FL [65].

B. Network topology

Factors such as convergence, generalization, communication overhead and robustness in distributed optimization are influenced by the configuration and the characteristics of the communication network among the clients. In [66] several network topologies are presented along with detailed information about their performance and limitations. For brevity and to maintain focus on the DFL setting we categorize the algorithms in the following three categories, which are derived from the ones presented in [66].

- **Fully-connected** also known as a complete topology, refers to a network where each peer communicates with every other peer. This topology is considered reliable and robust, as the failure of one

FIGURE 17. Decentralized FL network topologies. (a) Fully-connected (b) Partially connected - Ring (c) Node clustering

link does not disrupt the overall system; alternative paths can still be utilized. In addition, it ensures communication efficiency since all peers communicate directly, allowing the data to be transmitted using the shortest path. However, the disadvantages include constraints on scalability due to the exponential growth of links as the number of nodes increases and the increased complexity.

- **Partially connected**, unlike the fully-connected topology, where there is a direct connection between all peers, in this topology each peer communicates only with a subset of peers. The topology offers improved scalability because it is easier to integrate new peers in the network and is less complex than the fully connected one. In contrast, it is less reliable than the fully-connected topology and incurs delays in communication. Due to partial communication among peers, the data must follow a longer path to reach their destination. In this topology fall the ring network, and networks randomly generated.
- **Node cluster**. In this topology, peers are also partially connected, communicating only with the peers in the cluster they are organized. In contrast to partially-connected topology, the structure is more hierarchical and segmented. Node clustering often organizes peers into clusters with similar data distributions to address data heterogeneity.

C. Open issues

1) Communication optimization

Based on ongoing research, it is evident that DFL has the potential to significantly improve communication efficiency due to its varying network topologies, in contrast to the CFL. However, research is still focused on further improving this efficiency, either by optimizing the communication protocols or by employing compression mechanisms.

NET-FLEET [67] employs a gradient tracking method that allows more training updates on the clients without leading to the client drift problem. It shows that when each client performs K training iterations in each round, the model is updated $S \times K$ times and shared only S times. This results in a communication reduction of $1/K$ compared to methods that do not use this approach.

FED-DESN [68] utilizes deep Echo State Networks (ESN) for model training. However, deep ESN is not suitable for devices with limited resources. To alleviate this issue, the method decomposes deep ESN parameters into smaller subproblems using Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM), which also reduces communication costs.

In GOSSIPFL [63], two novel communication-efficient techniques are presented. The first one, model sparsification, aims to reduce communication traffic between peers. The method employs gradient subsampling [90] where instead of sending the complete model parameters after local training, clients send only a random subset of them based on a mask randomly generated. In centralized FL, the clients generate the random mask locally using a seed, which, when sent to the server, allows them to reconstruct the client mask. Similar to subsampling in GossipFL any two peers communicate only a subset of the model parameters, achieving a significant reduction in the data exchanged. In contrast to subsampling in CFL, any two peers use a seed from their coordinator node to generate the same random mask to sparsify their parameters. Based on theoretical analysis this compression ratio does not impact the convergence rate while ensuring great benefits in communication cost. The second technique employs a dynamic and bandwidth-aware gossip matrix algorithm, which generates perfect matching networks while also considering the bandwidth of each peer.

In C-DFL [69] the CHOCO-G [91] is employed for inter-node communication, paired with an operator re-

TABLE 3. Decentralized FL approaches

Method	Network Topology	Communication mechanism	Proposed Solution	Challenge
NET-FLEET [67]	Node-clustering	Peer-to-peer	Employs gradient estimator to approximate the global gradient	Communication optimization
Fed-dESN [68]	Fully-connected	Broadcast,	The problem is decomposed into small subproblems using ADMM	Communication optimization
Fed-dESN-ip		Decentralized Average		
Fed-dpr-ESN-ip		Consensus (DAC)		
GossipFL [63]	Partially-connected	Gossip	A sparsification algorithm and a novel gossip matrix generation algorithm is used. Clients exchange compressed models with each other. Nodes are divided in Coordinators and Clients. Clients communicate with each other and Coordinators manage the training process.	Communication optimization Lack of management
C-DFL [69]			Compressed communication is employed to reduce communication cost.	Communication optimization
CFL-LF [70]	Node-clustering	Averaging Consensus	Devices independently select fragments of the neural network to be shared with neighbors based on a local optimizer that balances model quality improvement and communication resource savings.	Communication optimization
DisPFL [71]	Partially-connected	Gossip	Uses personalized sparse masks to develop sparse local models at the edge.	Communication optimization Computational optimization
DFEDSAM [72]	Node-clustering	Gossip	Employs local gradient perturbation with SAM to improve generalization	Convergence optimization
DFEDSAM-M				
Decentralized Learning rule [73]	Arbitrary	Peer-to-peer	Employs posterior averaging to improve convergence on non-IID data.	Convergence optimization
CMFL [74]	Node-clustering	Peer-to-peer	Committees filter out outlier gradients.	Convergence optimization Security enhancement
Combo [62]	Partially-connected	Gossip	Employs model segmentation to reduce training time.	Convergence optimization Security enhancement
BGFL [75]	Partially-connected	Gossip	Employs model segmentation to reduce training time.	Convergence optimization Security enhancement
Bandit RW SGD [76]	Partially-connected	Gossip	Employs peer sampling strategy to reduce variance in gradient estimates.	Convergence optimization
Def-KT [77]	Node-clustering	Peer-to-peer	Employs mutual knowledge transfer to address the client drift issue.	Convergence optimization
PENS [78]	Node-clustering	Gossip	Employs performance-based node selection to address the covariate shift issue.	Convergence optimization
Fine-grained FL [79]	Blockchain-based	N/A	Blockchain-based reputation-aware FL method to ensure trustworthy clients.	Security enhancement

TABLE 3. Decentralized FL approaches – continued from previous page

Method	Network Topology	Communication mechanism	Proposed Solution	Challenge
FL-Block FL [80]	Blockchain-based	Peer-to-peer	Addresses poisoning attacks	Security enhancement
BESIFL [81]	Blockchain-based	Peer-to-peer	Accuracy based malicious node detection Contributions-based incentive mechanism	Security enhancement Incentive mechanism
FabricFL [82]	Blockchain-based	Peer-to-peer	Employs an identification mechanism for local updates trained on fake or malicious data	Security enhancement
BDFL [83]	Blockchain-based	Peer-to-peer	Employs an identification mechanism for local updates trained on fake or malicious data	Security enhancement
BLADE-FL [84]	Blockchain-based	Peer-to-peer	Employs an identification mechanism for local updates trained on fake or malicious data	Security enhancement
PVD-FL [85]	Partially-connected	Peer-to-peer	Employs a verifiable cipher-based matrix multiplication algorithm (EVCN) to ensure training integrity Model is encrypted with SHE technique to increase confidentiality.	Security enhancement
BE-DHFL [86]	Partially-connected	Peer-to-peer	Robustness against Byzantine attacks Employs homomorphic encryption to prevent leakage and membership inference attacks	Security enhancement
BISCOTTI [87]	Partially-connected	Peer-to-peer	Robustness against Byzantine attacks	Security enhancement
RDFL [88]	Partially-connected	Peer-to-peer	Robustness against Byzantine attacks	Security enhancement
Moshpit-SGD [65]	Node clustering / Independent	All-reduce	All-reduce algorithm in small independent and dynamic groups where clients have different neighbors in each round.	Lack of management
Soft-DSGD [64]	Fully-connected	Broadcast	Ensures convergence even under unreliable networks	Lack of management
FLCHAIN [89]	Fully-connected	Broadcast	Ensures convergence even under unreliable networks	Lack of management

sponsible for compressing the model parameters exchanged between peers. Four compression strategies are considered: Sparsification, Rescaled Unbiased Estimators, Randomized Gossip, and Random Quantization. Theoretical and empirical results demonstrate the linear convergence behavior of C-DFL.

CFL-LF [70] improves communication efficiency by exchanging only a subset of the model among peers. However, instead of randomly selecting a subset of the model parameters, an optimizer on each device sorts the layers according to their expected contribution to the learning performance of the global model. Only the layers with the highest contribution are exchanged among peers.

DISPFL [71] presents a combination of multiple local iterations on devices with model sparsification. In con-

trast to the other sparsification methods, this method proposes generating a random mask in each client that favors informative-rich gradients, expected to improve the personalization of the model for each client. The mask generation occurs in two steps: first, the model is pruned based on the rate derived from the work in [92], followed by the recovery of the most useful pruned gradients using a batch of local data.

In DFEDAVGM [93], the authors incorporate momentum and quantization to improve convergence and communication efficiency. The quantization enables clients to reduce the information they exchange, and the momentum aids in alleviating the loss in convergence due to reduced precision in client updates.

In DECEFL [94], the authors present a peer-to-peer approach designed to handle changes in communication

topology and focus on efficiency with convex and non-convex functions. The authors also present the applicability of the method in the fields of medical and industrial domains. Specifically, in the medical field, they present the application where multiple healthcare institutions train models on patient data. While in the industry domain, they show the applicability to smart manufacturing and control systems, where different manufacturing units collaborate to optimize their processes.

In [95], the authors utilize slotted ALOHA network protocol to improve communication efficiency of decentralized FL over wireless networks. The ALOHA protocol is designed to improve efficiency of channel utilization and reduce packet collisions. The proposed decentralized approach is compared with centralized FL and demonstrates comparable performance in accuracy while reducing latency, and improving flexibility.

In TORR [96] the authors employ a lightweight blockchain framework. The method uses proof of reliability (PoR) consensus mechanism where clients that are frequently online are considered more reliable and are preferred for the training and aggregation tasks resulting in reducing latency. In addition, the method employs an erasure coding-based storage protocol where small chunks of models are distributed for storage across different nodes. The method aims in recovering the model even in the case of stragglers. Also, a fast aggregation mechanism is used that allows calculation of intermediate global models to further reduce latency. Empirical results demonstrate that the method reduces execution time compared to other systems especially in the cases where larger models are used. Specifically, it reduces execution time by 8% compared to enhanced committee-based BFL on LeNet. On the larger model, MobileNetV3, it even manages to outperform centralized training by reducing the time by 42%. In addition, the results show that the method converges slower than the rest in the first rounds, which is attributed to similar stakes between nodes, but as the training progresses unreliable nodes are filtered out resulting in faster convergence in later rounds. Empirical results show that TORR is preferable for cases with large models where the benefits are enhanced.

In RPDFL [97], the authors propose the Ring-Allreduce algorithm where the clients are organized in a logical ring topology and clients communicate only with their adjacent nodes. The method considers the possibility of dropouts in which case the updates of the dropout client are replaced with an empty array to allow the round to complete. The results validate the robustness of the method, although the assumed ring topology might not be efficient in large-scale scenarios where the cumulative communication overhead increases greatly.

In KD-PDFL [98], communication efficiency is enhanced by the use of a collaboration graph. The weighted graph represents the relationships between clients based on model similarity and enables them to collaborate with clients closer to them. The method selects a node to act as the center of a star topology and calculate similarities on the received gradients and determine which clients are model relevant to each other. The selective communication approach reduces the amount of information exchanged in the network and similarity based selection leads to faster convergence. However, the added complexity of maintaining the collaboration graph limits the scalability of the system since it would lead to increased overhead and slower convergence.

The authors in [99] integrate peer-to-peer FL within a software-defined architecture for Time and Wavelength Division Multiplexing Passive Optical Networks (TWDM-PON). The proposed architecture utilizes direct communication between optical network units without routing through a central optical line terminal. Results demonstrate reduction in packet loss ratio and throughput gains validating that the method improves the quality and the reliability of the communication.

FEDDUAL [100], presents a hierarchical and asynchronous aggregation approach utilizing pair-wise communication protocol. Local updates are aggregated asynchronously without waiting for all other clients, in addition the clients are clustered based on their geographical proximity with others. Clustering reduces communication overhead since clients need to communicate only with nodes in the same cluster. The design of the system allows communication efficiency in large-scale FL systems where clients span across large geographical areas. In addition to communication efficiency the method considers privacy and security and employs local differential privacy and attestation mechanism through digital signatures. Notably, the authors propose a noise cutting trick based on private set intersection to mitigate the performance loss from differential privacy. The method is evaluated against centralized training on three datasets: MNIST, CIFAR-10 and FEMNIST. Regarding MNIST the FEDDUAL achieves comparable performance to centralized training, specifically 98.92% and 99.05% respectively. Though for the most difficult tasks the method achieves only 62.71% (FEDDUAL) against 75.42% (centralized) on CIFAR-10 and 70.51% (FEDDUAL) against 85.73% (centralized) on FEMNIST. The results demonstrate a level of instability across datasets which can be attributed to the complexity of the tasks. The competitive points of the method are that it addresses the communication efficiency of DFL by employing asynchronous and pair-wise communication between nodes in the same cluster, and it also incorporates privacy and security measures, making it a more comprehensive method. However, there are some limitations

to the method. Specifically, the observed instability in the results and the lack of comparison with other DFL methods instigate that further evaluation is required. Additionally, the added computation and communication costs among devices for calculating the PSI, used in the noise adjustment trick, should be considered in practical implementations.

2) Convergence optimization

Decentralized learning, especially DFL, presents unique challenges for the convergence of learning systems due to the distributed nature of the computations and the data. Distributed data sets in the real world follow non-identical distributions, this greatly hinders the convergence rate of the learning algorithms. Thus research in DFL, similarly to the CFL setting, has been focused on improving convergence rates as well as addressing the issues that arise from non-IID distributions.

In DFEDSAM [72], the Sharpness-Aware Minimization (SAM) [101] is utilized to improve generalization. The fundamental principle of SAM is to minimize not just the loss value but also the sharpness of the loss. Essentially, the algorithm identifies parameters that reside in neighborhoods with uniformly low loss. This is achieved by applying a perturbation to the local gradient during training, directing it towards a flatter local model.

In the work of [73], a decentralized learning rule is presented, inspired by the social learning and distributed hypothesis testing literature. Peers perform variational inference to estimate the global posterior, and the aggregation calculates the average of all the clients' posteriors.

In Committee Mechanism Based FL (CMFL) [74], the authors propose a method that establishes a committee each round to identify local model updates hindering the global models performance. The gradient updates are evaluated and scores are assigned to the relevant clients based on the Euclidean distance, distinguishing honest and malicious updates. The method is based on the assumption that the distances between two honest updates are smaller than those between dishonest updates. Two selection mechanisms are presented that determine the uploaded updates that will be used for aggregation focused either on performance or robustness. The robustness-oriented selection favors updates from clients with high scores, thus preventing malicious clients' updates from affecting the global model. The performance-oriented strategy selects the clients with the lowest scores improving the convergence rate of the global model.

In COMBO [62] the clients split their model parameters into several non-overlapping subsets in each round and request each subset from a different peer in the network. The algorithm defines the hyper parameter R , which denotes the number of requests for the same subset

from a specific client in one round. The aggregation is completed when all requests are fulfilled. Theoretical and empirical results indicate that with the proper selection of R , the training time of the algorithm can be improved.

BGFL [75] presents a blockchain-based DFL system where a group of nodes are selected in each round as the miners, based on their accuracy. Miners are responsible for adding the collected updates to new blocks in the chain and when an adequate number of blocks is collected a smart contract performs the aggregation. In Bandit RW SGD [76], a random walk algorithm is presented where the local update of a peer is passed to the next until the aggregation is completed. The intuition lies in the node selection strategy used. Due to the partially-connected topology considered in this work, the selection of the next peer is treated as a Sleeping Multi-Armed Bandit problem and the proposed solution derives from the relevant literature [102]. The aim of the algorithm presented is to sample the peers that will reduce variance in the local updates and thus improve the convergence rate.

The work in [77] introduces the DEF-KT algorithm, the proposed method avoids the client-drift issue by replacing averaging with model fusion through Mutual Knowledge Transfer inspired by [103].

In the work presented in [78], the primary objective is to address the covariate shift caused by heterogeneous distributions. The PENS method identifies peers with similar distributions by evaluating the models received by each client on their local dataset. The models with the lowest loss indicate that their respective peers have a dataset of similar distribution and thus are selected for aggregation.

In Quantum FL (QFL) [104], the authors present a decentralized FL system based on peer-to-peer communications. This proposed framework addresses challenges associated with security through secure multi party computations, privacy via differential privacy, transparency with blockchain and computational efficiency through quantum computing.

In YOGA [105] the authors employ a heuristic algorithm called Max-Match to create tailored layer-wise aggregation policies for each client. The method aggregates individual layers rather than the whole model, it generates a ranking of layers for each client based on speed and layer-wise divergence to decide which layers will be aggregated by each client. The proposed method improves convergence of the model and efficiently handles non-IID data. Empirical results validate the convergence gain, depicting a substantial speedup of $1.9\times$ and $2.7\times$ for CIFAR-10 against GOSSIPFL and CFL-LS respectively. The characteristics that lead to these improvements derive from the random peer selection in GOSSIPFL which is not optimal leading to slower convergence. On the other hand CFL-LS considers layer

ranking but still adds extra communication overhead by exchanging full models. However, even though the selection of layers for aggregation improves communication efficiency it also introduces computation overhead that could hinder scalability as the number of clients increases. In PFEDGAME [106], the authors utilize Game Theory to address dynamic network topology. The method proceeds in two steps: first, it selects suitable clients for participation and secondly executes a two-player cooperative game to achieve convergence optimizing the aggregation strategy. The client selection mechanism aims to minimize the number of selected clients and is inspired by PENS, a method also met in [78], by selecting clients that contribute the most. The peer selection aims on pairing clients to collaborate with each other and execute the cooperative game. Empirical results presented demonstrate that the method maintains performance similar to PFEDGRAPH, a state of the art centralized and personalized FL method, in the decentralized setting on various heterogeneity settings. Even though the one-hop decentralized communication protocol employed can reduce communication overhead it is not suitable for large-scale cases where each client having direct communication with only one client sequentially is not feasible. In addition, peer selection adds complexity and computation overhead and might be inefficient within a large network limiting scalability. In CDF-S [107], the authors consider a decentralized approach suitable for Internet of Vehicles. The method employs a regularized nonlinear acceleration scheme to accelerate convergence and every client fuses the updates of its neighbors through a weighted averaging process. The random broadcast gossip-based protocol is proposed since it is inherently resilient in dynamic network conditions and allows the system to continue functioning even when vehicles dropout. In addition, the introduction of new clients does not require significant changes, making it suitable for large-scale and dynamic environments. Experiments demonstrate that it requires only 25 rounds for the model to converge where the best performing baseline FedM requires 200. Results also show that increasing the probability of a communication link failing results in slight degradation for the method and it should be considered in scenarios without reliable communications.

3) Security enhancement

The unique characteristics of DFL also present a new set of security challenges. Significant research has been focused on addressing the unique vulnerabilities introduced by direct communication among peers and the decentralized aggregation implemented in DFL. The CMFL [74] method mentioned previously in the communication efficient challenges subsection also incorpo-

rate a selection mechanism for security enhancement. In fine-grained FL, the concept of a blockchain-based reputation-aware and fine-grained FL system is introduced. It outlines the core requirements for achieving fine-grained FL systems and employs reputation services for the edge, fog, and cloud to ensure the trustworthiness of the participating nodes and central authorities.

The work presented in [80] introduces FL-BLOCK, a blockchain-based FL system. Unlike other blockchain approaches in this method the updates are stored off the chain in the fog servers preventing access to malicious clients. It uses secure keys to encrypt the updates adding a layer of security by preventing adversaries from adding their updates. However, the existence of security key theft or adversaries that can modify the communication protocols is not considered.

Another security-focused blockchain-based method is presented in BESIFL [81]. In this study, two subsets of the peers are dynamically created to play the distinct roles of computing supporters and verification supporters. Computing supporters train the global model on their local dataset while verification supporters aggregate the updates through a blockchain mechanism. The system also distributes a pre-defined testing dataset to the verification supporters to evaluate the received local updates. The system employs a scoring mechanism to prevent low-accuracy computing supporters from participating in the training process. However, the existence of a pre-defined testing set is not always available in real-world scenarios.

FABRICFL [82] leverages the immutability and authentication features of blockchain for security and trust. In contrast to other algorithms, FABRICFL keeps the global model off the ledger to avoid the added complexity introduced by continuous updates. In BLADE-FL [84] the blockchain technology is integrated with FL, focusing on addressing the issue of lazy nodes that do not contribute to the training process.

In BDFL [83] a Byzantine-Fault-Tolerant DFL system is proposed for autonomous vehicles. The main differences to other studies in the field are that it utilizes HYDRAND [108] and Publicly Verifiable Secret Sharing (PVSS) [109] schemes to preserve privacy, instead of using differential privacy. In [85], the PVD-FL system is presented focusing on ensuring system verifiability and integrity. The EVCN algorithm plays a key role in the PVD-FL system, combining symmetric homomorphic encryption (SHE) [110] and Single Instruction Multiple Data (SIMD) [111]. With SHE secure computations of addition and multiplication can be achieved while SIMD allows the partitioning of the data in multiple slots and the execution of single instructions to multiple data points simultaneously. In PVD-FL, the global model is encrypted in ciphertext, allowing the peers to collaboratively train the global model.

In BE-DHFL [86], similarly to other approaches, leverages the authentication and security characteristics of blockchain technology for the integrity of the DFL system. Committee nodes are included in the peer-to-peer network and are responsible for aggregation while training nodes calculate local updates. Homomorphic encryption is employed to enhance privacy during the communication of gradients.

BISCOTTI [87] also employs blockchain technology to address multiple security vulnerabilities including threats from Sybil attacks, poisoning attacks, information leakage, and utility loss. The first three are common threats in the FL setting, while utility loss regards the performance degradation of the model due to privacy-preserving techniques. To address Sybil attacks, a consistent hashing method paired with Proof of Federation (PoF) to select peers with good reputation is employed. To address poisoning attacks the collected updates are validated using MULTI-KRUM [112]. Finally, for information leakage, two different methods are employed, differential privacy and verification of the model updates.

The work in RDFL [88] also presents a byzantine robust DFL system. In this study, the peers are connected in a ring network topology and share updates only with adjacent nodes, the previous and next peer. Each peer evaluates collected updates to identify malicious contributions based on the loss of the combined local model.

In PPT [113], the authors present a peer to peer approach with emphasis on privacy, security and efficiency. The method employs noise mechanism similar to differential privacy for privacy preservation and a symmetric cryptosystem for encrypting local updates and safeguarding security. The cryptosystem is based on the Eschenauer-Gligor (E-G) key distribution scheme, and ensures that only authorized clients can decrypt messages. In addition, the method incorporates game theory to mitigate potential collusion attacks. The protocol consists of mutual reporting of malicious activities and penalties for the attackers. In addition to security and privacy aspects, the method also considers scalability and dynamic conditions. PPT utilizes one-hop communication protocol where each client communicates the aggregated model with only one neighbour. Lastly, the method's robustness to clients dropping out during training enhances its overall resilience. Empirical results demonstrate that the method achieves better than centralized training in ROC curves. Additionally, the method has been evaluated in dropout rates ranging from 1% to 15%, demonstrating more than 91% accuracy even in scenarios with 15% client dropout. In light of these results, it is essential to consider the following limitations. A significant limitation of the method derives from the assumption of a static network. Even though the method considers clients dropping out of

the training the communication key establishment is not suitable for the scenario where new clients are introduced after key establishment, making the method unsuitable for cases where mobility of the clients is of paramount importance such as cases in the Internet of Vehicles domain. In addition, one-hop communication protocol is not efficient for large-scale applications since it introduces additional communication overhead as the number of clients increases. Lastly, the reporting mechanism is suitable for simple adversarial strategies and could be easily bypassed from newer and more complex attacks.

As mentioned above, the FEDUAL [100] method considers privacy and security. Specifically, for security, the authors employ an attestation mechanism based on signatures and for privacy, they utilize local differential privacy paired with a noise cutting trick based on private set intersection to mitigate the performance loss from the added noise. The clients communicating with each other identify common values in model parameters and reduce noise in them since this knowledge is common on both of them. Evaluation results demonstrate that the PSI-noise method improves performance on all three datasets. Specifically the accuracy is improved by 0.67% on MNIST, 6.15% on CIFAR-10 and 1.38% on FEMNIST. Accuracy improvement on CIFAR-10 is considered significant and on MNIST dataset no safe deductions can be made since the standard LDP is already very accurate, 98.21%. On FEMNIST dataset, however, the improvement seems rather insignificant especially if we consider the added computation and communication cost for calculating the PSI among devices. The results on the noise trick1 demonstrate a certain level of variability across diverse datasets which should be further investigated. In addition, PSI requires sharing common parameters across clients which might lead to leaking sensitive information of the clients dataset.

In BLOCKDFL [114], a blockchain based DFL method is presented that combines a scoring mechanism, a byzantine fault-tolerant voting mechanism and gradient compression to address issues in security and communication efficiency. The scoring mechanism is two-fold: the local updates from clients are scored using median-based testing in the first layer and the remaining updates are evaluated with KRUM. Median-based testing involves comparing each update with the median of the collected updates, considering outliers as malicious updates and filtering them out. The byzantine fault-tolerant voting mechanism involves clients assuming committee roles and if a specific update receives sufficient support from the committee it is added on the global model and the blockchain. Results demonstrate the effectiveness of the method, maintaining performance even with 40% malicious clients. Specifically the method achieves up to 4% against FEDAVG while it outperforms BISCOTTI in the case where malicious clients are more than 40%

in MNIST and in any malicious ratio in CIFAR-10. Moreover, the results demonstrate significant reduction in attack success rate (ASR) in all cases achieving -10% to -65% reduction against BISCOTTI on both datasets. Although the method aims in improving efficiency alongside security of DFL systems, the voting mechanism still introduces complexity, computational and communication overhead that might impact scalability of the system. However, results presented demonstrate that the completion time of each round is mainly affected by the size of verifiers, and the rest operations do not add significant amount of time and do not scale as the number of clients increase. Thus it is argued that careful consideration of the number of clients in the voting committee can allow the method to scale. Empirical results also reveal a possible limitation of BISCOTTI; the method is resilient against poisoning attacks with up to 30% malicious clients only in the IID scenario. In the non-IID scenario, the accuracy of the method is significantly hindered even with 10% of malicious clients, and it performs at best comparably to FEDAVG, which does not employ any defense mechanisms.

Many security-related solutions stem from blockchain-based methods. This fact is justified since blockchain is a pivotal technology in the edge domain, ensuring robust security and reliability in the systems it utilizes.

4) Lack of management

The central server in CFL was used not only for the aggregation of the global model but also to orchestrate FL sessions and send instructions to participating peers. In DFL the absence of a central server introduces new challenges associated with orchestration and potential confusion among clients.

To address these challenges many algorithms have been proposed. It is common in many algorithms to dynamically select a subset of clients to collect the local updates from [74], [75], [81] and perform aggregation. These methods utilize scoring mechanisms to detect malicious updates and nodes and exclude them from the aggregation. Usually, methods that would be employed by the central server in CFL, in DFL are performed by dynamic subsets of clients. Another issue that emerges due to lack of management is client dropout, a simple case that can be easily resolved in CFL by just sampling more clients than necessary. However, in DFL, changes in the network can cause system failure.

In Moshpit SGD [65] addresses the network reliability issue with a simple mechanism. It employs the all-reduce algorithm for the collaborative training of the global model, which has favorable theoretical properties and can achieve considerable speed-ups compared to gossip-based algorithms. However, this algorithm is not well-suited for the unreliable and unstable networks typical

of DFL settings. To mitigate this, the participating nodes are split into clusters in each round to perform all-reduce thus dropout peers will affect only the cluster they belong to. Convergence is ensured by enforcing a simple rule stating that if two peers belong to the same group in one round, they cannot be in the same group in the next. All-reduce empirically demonstrates convergence in fewer rounds compared to gossip-based methods.

Another approach that considers unreliable communication is presented in [64]. The method proposes the use of Soft-DSGD a robust training algorithm to address unreliable networks. The algorithm accounts for unreliable links between peers and potential packet loss in the exchanged local updates. Based on this insight, a reliability matrix is constructed regarding the quality of the communication links in the network. During aggregation, the missing values of a local update are filled with stale values, and the mixing weight matrix is optimized according to the reliability matrix.

5) Incentive mechanisms

Another challenging aspect of DFL is the lack of incentive mechanisms. In networks that are unreliable, unstable, and without a central authority, peers may be unwilling to participate and contribute their local updates. Consequently, research has been focused on the design of incentive mechanisms suitable for the decentralized FL setting.

The focus of FLCHAIN [89] is to provide a blockchain-based decentralized FL system that utilizes incentives to increase peer participation and reliability. The study presents a marketplace for model commercialization and aims to partition profit among peers based on their contribution and reliability.

Similarly, BESIFL [81] employs an incentive mechanism where peers are rewarded based on the improvements their contributions bring to the global model's accuracy. This is realized through a token-based reward/punishment system where each node offers tokens to other peers to request their contribution. Participating peers thus increase their tokens, enabling them to request more updates from the other peers. However, providing malicious updates can result in punishing the peer to lose all of its tokens. Consequently, the tokens are necessary for the improvement of each peer's local model, incentivizing them to provide honest updates.

The work in Fine-grained FL [79] in a similar fashion employs an incentive mechanism based on the reputation of the peer aiming to offer increased benefits to honest participants and fewer to dishonest ones.

Similar to security-related solutions, there is a notable correlation between incentive mechanisms and blockchain-based solutions, attributed to the distinct features of blockchain technology.

Table 3 summarizes the methods presented by the scientific community, focusing on various challenges of decentralized FL systems. The table includes a categorization of each method based on the network topology and the communication mechanism used, as well as the specific challenge they address alongside the proposed solution.

VII. Challenges of FL

The implementation of FL systems comes with a set of challenges that span various dimensions. These encompass client participation, data, communication, security, and fairness. In this section, we delve into the multifaceted challenges encountered in FL, providing a detailed exploration of critical obstacles and the methods presented by the scientific community to address them. In addition, we further categorize the proposed solutions based on the method used, if possible, and present tables with the methods and the metrics and baselines used in the experiments reported by the authors. Understanding and addressing these challenges is essential for the successful implementation and use of FL and to ensure robustness, scalability, and fair deployment in any real-world case scenario. Fig. 18 shows the categorization of the challenges as well as the categorization of the methods used to address them, where possible.

A. Client Selection

Client selection is the process of choosing a subset of the available client devices to participate in the next round. Effective client selection can yield several benefits and help address various challenges encountered during the training of a federated model. The criteria for selection vary based on the system's needs, with factors such as heterogeneity, resources, fairness, and security influencing the choice. In the work presented in [115], a client selection method is introduced, which improves the convergence of the model by selecting clients with higher local losses. In addition, two variants are also presented that take into consideration communication and computation while the authors suggest that opting for different metrics can benefit fairness and robustness. Another study presented in [116] evaluates each client's contribution to global accuracy and uses it to regulate the probability of each client being selected. In [117], an irrelevance score is introduced, which is used to filter out clients with class imbalance and very few samples in their datasets. Clients with very few samples are considered free riders since their data provide little to no contribution to the global model improvement. The method can adequately address the potential existence of free riders in the system; however, excluding clients from training could impact its fairness. In PYRAMID-FL [118] selection is based on a utility score. Each client

has the ability to balance local iterations and the number of parameters sent according to his computational and communication capabilities. The FEDCOR [119] considers both the loss of each client and the loss correlation between them. It uses a Gaussian process to model the expected loss change and selects the clients that strongly correlate with other clients but exhibit weak correlations with those already selected. The method introduces variance among the selected clients while maintaining a small subset size. The algorithm proposed in [120], a Neural Combinatorial Contextual Bandit (NCCB), treats the client selection problem as a combinatorial bandit problem. It clusters the clients based on their data features and promotes selection from all the identified clusters, preventing repeated selection from the same cluster. This approach is similar to the previous method focusing on weak correlations and aims to ensure variance in the clients selected.

In FEDPNS [121], present a client selection mechanism using probabilities. The probabilities of clients are dynamically adjusted in each round. The method evaluates the contribution of each client by comparing local updates with the global model, promoting clients that align more closely as they are considered

more beneficial for the convergence of the global model. In addition the method facilitates a procedure termed check expectation and which identifies local updates that negatively impact the global model and penalizing their probability of being selected. The method is evaluated against standard FEDAVG which utilizes uniform random selection of clients and demonstrates improvements on accuracy. Additionally, the improvement is even greater as the heterogeneity among clients increases, further highlighting the effectiveness and the benefits of the method in realistic scenarios. In light of these results, it is essential to consider that evaluating contributions and dynamically adjusting selection probabilities introduces computational complexity that scales linearly with number of clients reducing the method's scalability potential.

In INTELLIFL [122] multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL) is utilized to optimize client selection. The method selects clients that contribute the most to model accuracy considering also their resource capabilities. MARL agents evaluate the performance of each client and select those most likely to positively contribute. The agents are trained using a reward mechanism that considers improvement in model accuracy, processing time reduction and communication cost. The results depict that INTELLIFL outperforms all baselines in accuracy while reducing by 22% processing latency validating that it can effectively manage data and resource heterogeneity among clients. However, training of MARL might be computationally intensive and complex and it could jeopardize scalability to large-scale scenarios.

FIGURE 18. High level categorization of FL challenges.

The authors in [123], use sparsity regularization and compressive sensing to identify a sparse subset of clients that provide the most relevant and important information. This is achieved by measuring the importance of the contribution each client’s contribution to the global model. The method consistently outperforms FEDPNS on accuracy and convergence rate on various datasets. Despite the results, there are limitations that have to be considered. Firstly, the sparsity regularization assumes a certain level of sparsity which might not always reflect the true conditions leading to suboptimal performance. In addition, even though the approach is designed for large-scale applications it still might face issues in cases with extremely large populations.

The authors in [124], utilize Repeated Arrays of Count Estimators (RACE) sketches based on Locality Sensitive Hashing functions to represent the data distribution on each client. The representation of each client’s dataset is calculated only once in the first round and is then aggregated on the server to form a representation of the global data distribution. The proposed client selection mechanism prefers clients that are more aligned to the global distribution addressing this way the heterogeneity problem. The method is evaluated against uniform random sampling and demonstrates improvement on convergence and generalization. In addition, the method can also be used to address the cold start problem where a new client is introduced to the training procedure. Different models can be maintained based on clients distribution sketches and help new clients identify models closer to their distribution. On the other hand, high dimensionality on the data require increasing the size of the sketches to adequately represent distribution. Additionally, even though the aggregation of the sketches is computationally efficient it still adds a computational overhead in the first round and it should be considered in extremely large-scale cases.

SPACE [125] method employs the construction of prototypes on the server and the clients and the distance of each local prototype to the global prototype is used to evaluate how well the client generalizes against the global model. The server prototype is constructed after one round of training, following the update of

the global model through knowledge amalgamation. The presented method aims to address the limitations of the Shapley value that requires several training rounds to converge as well as its dependence on the size of the dataset for accurately evaluating the performance of the model. In contrast, SPACE requires only one round to calculate the contributions and the prototype-based evaluation method eliminates the need to iterating over all samples of the evaluation dataset. Even though results demonstrate the applicability and improvement in client selection, the method relies heavily on the existence of a quality and reliable validation dataset on the server. In addition, even though the proposed evaluation method requires less computation than Shapley value, it still introduces considerable overhead for large-scale scenarios, potentially limiting scalability.

In EPISODE++ [126] the authors use historical gradient information from previous rounds for each client to optimize selection. The algorithm records the averaged stochastic gradients of each client from previous rounds, which are used to construct control variates. It also takes into account the gradient norms of historical gradients, preferring clients with lower norms, as well as participation history, with a preference for more reliable clients. Historical gradient norms have been used by other methods to depict the alignment of the local update to the global model where smaller norm means greater alignment. Even though it is a good estimate, the specific method cannot be used in cases where differential privacy is applied since the random noise introduced impacts the norm of the gradients.

The improvement achieved by each client selection method as well as the baselines used by the authors in the reported experiments can be found in Table 4. The client selection methods above use a variety of criteria derived in numerous ways. Loss based selection methods prioritize clients with higher loss and help accelerate convergence focusing on not yet learned patterns. EPISODE++ instead of loss utilize the norm of the gradients. Although a smaller gradient norm often correlates with smaller loss, these are not strictly equivalent. Accuracy as a selection criterion prioritizes clients that contribute more to global model accuracy ensures

stable accuracy gains. In FEDPNS accuracy is used as selection criterion and results demonstrate small but consistent improvement in accuracy. The characteristics of client data, such as the number of samples, can be used as a selection criterion. While this criterion can be beneficial in addressing statistical heterogeneity of clients datasets, it might also exclude important information from smaller datasets hindering performance as well as fairness. Utility-based selection methods, such as INTELLIFL, consider the ability of the clients to contribute, leading to gains in resource usage and communication costs. Variance based selection, whether through loss correlation among clients or by client data features, improves model robustness and generalization. Incorporating diverse information ensures that the training process avoids redundancy and overfitting to specific patterns. Alignment to global representation. RACE and SPACE algorithm employ different methods to represent the clients, data distribution sketches in RACE and client prototypes in SPACE, and after aggregating them to create a global representation, they select clients based on their proximity to the global representation. Both of these methods ensure that data of the selected clients are consistent with the overall data distribution, leading to better accuracy and generalization. Based on the selection criteria and performance of the algorithms we can safely conclude to the below observations. Contribution is an important factor for selecting clients as it ensures that the most valuable updates are used in each round. Variance also plays a crucial especially in heterogeneous environments. Selecting diverse clients Balance between contribution and diversity provide the most effective results. These methods avoid overfitting to specific clients and ensure that client updates are valuable to the global model. RACE and SPACE methods which consider alignment of the client to global distribution, exemplify this balance, leading to improved accuracy. Efficiency is another significant aspect of more effective client selection. Although target efficiency does not specifically aim to improve model performance, it enhances overall system efficiency, which is crucial for resource limited scenarios.

It is evident that the selection criteria significantly influence the performance of FL algorithms. Different selection criteria bring benefits on different aspects of the system. Selecting those client selection criteria is crucial and it should be strategically aligned with the purpose of the system and the context of the application. Results exhibit that there is not a single solutions that fits all. Notably, Irrelevance Score method exhibits inconsistent improvements depending on the dataset used, indicating that it may not be universally applicable. The findings from the analysis of the selection criteria and their performance suggest that there is a need from mode adaptable or universally effective selection criteria that

can perform across a broader range of scenarios and cover more aspects of the system.

B. Data Sampling

Extensive research has shown that not all data are equally beneficial during training [127]. Low-quality data include biased, outlier, duplicate samples, or samples that do not offer any new information. The existence of such data hinders the performance of training by increasing the time required to converge while simultaneously increasing storage. Especially in the case of deep neural networks research has demonstrated that once the initial training phase is completed, most of the data do not provide new information to the model and thus could easily be ignored. Research has been focused on discovering “information-rich” subsets of the data to accelerate training and decrease the resources required [127]–[130].

Significant performance can be achieved by training only on a small fraction of the dataset using data sampling techniques. Data sampling techniques aim to reduce the resources required while maintaining the representativeness and performance of the model. This can result in reduced computational and storage costs and thus improve system efficiency without sacrificing performance.

Commonly used data sampling techniques include random sampling, stratified sampling, importance sampling [130], active learning, mini-batch sampling, and hard example mining. The choice of the technique depends on the specific characteristics of the dataset, the learning task, and the available resources.

FL, though, also suffers from heterogeneity problems. Data in real-world federated settings are imbalanced and not identically distributed among clients (non-IID). Incorporating data sampling techniques in FL can improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the training process. It allows the systems to prioritize the most informative data samples, leading to faster convergence, improved model performance, and reduced communication and computational costs.

Most of the data sampling techniques in centralized learning require inspecting the whole dataset, which is not feasible in the distributed and privacy-preserving setting of FL. Recent studies in FL focus on addressing the challenges of heterogeneity [131]–[133] and limited resources [134] by employing data sampling techniques in a privacy-preserving manner.

Given the different characteristics of training algorithms between centralized and FL, different approaches are required by each paradigm. Data sampling strategies could be used to evaluate the quality of the raw data online, allowing only high-quality data to be stored. This could result in the reduction of the size of the data storage needed and the reduction in computational

TABLE 4. Client selection methods improvement

Method	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
POWER OF CHOICE [115]	Accuracy	+5.42%	FMNIST	Random
CBE3 [116]	Convergence (Speedup) ¹	×1.58	CIFAR-10	Random
IRRELEVANCE SCORE [117]	Accuracy ²	+0.03% (Random) +0.05% (AFL) +0.08% (Random) +0.14% (AFL) +0.05% (Random)	MNIST KMNIST FEMNIST HAR cardiotocography	Random, AFL
PYRAMIDFL+PROX [118]	Time to accuracy (Speedup) ¹	×13.66 ×2.74 ×9.31 ×3.97	HARBox OpenImage Google speech StackOverflow	OORT
FEDCOR [119]	Rounds to accuracy (Speedup) ¹	×1.34 (Pow-d) ×1.37 (Random)	FEMNIST CIFAR-10	Random, AFL, Pow-d
NCCB [120]	Rounds to accuracy (Speedup) ¹	×1.3 (OORT) ×1.06 (k-LinUCB) ×1.06 (OORT)	Superuser Yelp Sentiment140	Random, OORT, k-LinUCB, ClusterFL
FEDPNS [121]	Accuracy	+3% (FEDAVG)	MNIST	FEDAVG, BN2
INTELLIFL [122]	Accuracy Latency Communication cost	-0.01% (FEDMARL) -22% (FEDMARL) -12% (FEDMARL)	MNIST, CIFAR-10, FASHIONMNIST	FEDAVG, HETEROFL, FEDPROX, FEDNOVA, OORT, FEDMARL
SPARSITY REGULARIZATION [123]	Accuracy	+3% (FEDPNS)	MNIST	FEDAVG, FEDPNS
RACE [124]	Rounds to target accuracy	-10 (FEDAVG)	Shakespeare	FEDAVG
SPACE [125]	Accuracy	+3% (Clustered Sampling)	CIFAR-10	Clustered Sampling, Multinomial Distribution
EPISODE++ [124]	Accuracy	+0.24% (NaiveParallel Clip)	Sent140	SCAFFOLDCLIP, NaiveParallel Clip, CELGC, EPISODE

¹ Speedup is calculated using the following formula: $Speedup = \frac{baseline}{improved}$

² Improvement over the best performing baseline. (Best baseline)

costs. Lastly, such strategies can be applied iteratively to re-evaluate the data stored after training and discard samples that are no longer required.

An example of such an approach is FEDBALANCER [132] which aims to select client samples that benefit training the most. Samples with rich information are sampled from the dataset instead of training on the full dataset.

C. Heterogeneity

1) Statistical Heterogeneity - Single-model approaches

Even though FEDAVG has been proven quite robust and efficient in many use cases, it has also been proven that there is a significant drop in performance in the presence of non-IID datasets among the peers [152]. In the traditional FEDAVG algorithm, it has been argued that due to the aggregation mechanism used a learning bias is added towards the clients that hold the majority of samples.

The improvement achieved by the methods presented in this subsection, which address statistical heterogeneity

TABLE 5. Single-model/Generalization approaches part A

Method	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
AFL [135]	Accuracy	+3.2% +1.9%	Fashion MNIST Adult	FEDAVG
FEDAVGM [136]	Accuracy Clients= 0.05 Accuracy Clients= 0.4	≈ +40% ≈ +10%	CIFAR-10	FEDAVG
FEDPROX [137]	Accuracy	≈ +20%	Synthetic, MNIST, Shakespeare Sent140	FEDAVG
SCAFFOLD [138]	Rounds to 0.5 accuracy (Speedup) ¹	×3.3 ×12.9		FEDAVG FEDPROX
FEDNOVA [139]	Accuracy	+9% ² +9.67% ² +0.00% ²	CIFAR-10	FEDAVG FEDPROX SCAFFOLD
FEDYOGI, FEDADAGRAD ⁷ FEDADAM [140]	Accuracy Recall MSE	+0.6% (FEDADAM, FEDAVGM) ⁶ −0.1% (FEDADAM) ⁶ −0.1% (FEDADAM) ⁶ −0.1% (FEDAVGM) ⁶ +0.0% (FEDADAM) ⁶ −1.2% (FEDADAGRAD) ⁶ +0.2% (FEDADAM) ⁶	CIFAR-10 CIFAR-100 EMNIST CR SHAKESPEARE SO NWP SO LR SO LR	FEDADAGRAD, FEDADAM, FEDAVG, FEDAVGM
MOON [141]	Accuracy Rounds to accuracy (Speedup) Accuracy Rounds to accuracy (Speedup) Accuracy Rounds to accuracy (Speedup)	+2.2% (FEDPROX) ⁶ ×1.9 (FEDPROX) ¹ +2.9% (FEDPROX) ⁶ ×1.7 (FEDPROX) ¹ +1.9% (FEDPROX) ⁶ ×1.9 (FEDPROX) ¹	CIFAR-10 CIFAR-100 Tiny-Imagenet	FEDAVG, FEDPROX, SCAFFOLD, SOLO
FEDPROX + CCVR [142]	Accuracy for	+0.30%	CIFAR-100	FEDPROX
FEDPROX + CCVR FEDAVGM + CCVR	Accuracy for Accuracy for	+9.53% +0.28%	CINIC-10 CIFAR-100	FEDPROX FEDAVGM
FEDAVGM + CCVR	Accuracy for	+10.41%	CINIC-10	FEDAVGM
MOON + CCVR MOON + CCVR	Accuracy for Accuracy for	+0.15% +3.75%	CIFAR-100 CINIC-10	MOON MOON
FEDDYN [143]	Parameters transmitted to 80% accuracy	×2.6 (SCAFFOLD) ×1.9 (SCAFFOLD)	CIFAR-10 CIFAR-100	FEDAVG, FEDPROX SCAFFOLD

¹ Speedup is calculated using the following formula: $Speedup = \frac{baseline}{improved}$

² Accuracy improvement regards the improvement to the system when using the same optimizer with and without FEDNOVA and not using FEDNOVA instead as the optimizer method that is usually the case in other metrics.

³ No baselines have been provided. The improvement regards the comparison between L2GD and L2GD+ where the later includes variance reduction. The experiment showcases the importance of variance reduction.

⁴ The percentage regards to how much less number of parameters were exchanged.

⁵ Comparison in these cases is made between AVG and GMA. We present the method that was used alongside AVG and GMA and achieved the highest accuracy for the specific dataset. The difference regards the difference in accuracy between AVG and GMA for this method.

⁶ Improvement over the best performing baseline. (Best baseline)

⁷ Comparison regard FEDYOGI and FEDADAGRAD and FEDADAM are seen as baselines.

TABLE 5. Single-model/Generalization approaches – continued from previous page

Method	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
CREFF [144]	Accuracy	+1.08 (CCVR) ¹	CIFAR-10-LT CIFAR-100-LT	FEDAVG, FEDAVGM, FEDPROX, FEDDF, FedBE, CCVR, FEDNOVA, Fed-Focal Loss, Ratio Loss, FEDAVG with τ -norm
CLIP2FL [145]	Accuracy	+2.20 (CREFF) ¹	CIFAR-10-LT CIFAR-100-LT	FEDAVG, FEDAVGM, FEDPROX, FEDDF, FedBE, CCVR, FEDNOVA, Fed-Focal Loss, Ratio Loss, FEDAVG with τ -norm, CREFF
FEDBN [146]	Accuracy +0.85% (FEDPROX) +1.48% (FEDAVG) +0.7% (FEDAVG)	+7.96% (FEDPROX) +1.39% (FEDPROX)	SVHN USPS SynthDigits MNIST-M MNIST	FEDAVG, FEDPROX
FEDDC [147]	Rounds to accuracy (Speedup)	$\times 1.3$ (FEDDYN) $\times 1.36$ (SCAFFOLD) $\times 0.69$ (FEDDYN) $\times 1.1$ (FEDDYN)	Mnist Fashion MNIST EMNIST CIFAR-100	FEDAVG, FEDPROX, SCAFFOLD, FEDDYN
FEDPROTO [148]	Accuracy Number of parameters exchanged (Reduction) Accuracy Number of parameters exchanged (Reduction) Accuracy Number of parameters exchanged (Reduction)	+0.87% (FEDPROX) +96% (FEDPER) ⁴ +2.297% (FEDPROX) +96% (FEDPROX) ⁴ +1.24% (FEDPROX) +99.99% (FEDPROX) ⁴	MNIST FEMNIST CIFAR-10	FEDSEM, FEDPROX, FEDPER, FEDAVG, FEDREP
COMFED (PROXYOGI) [149]	Accuracy	+0.5% (FEDAVG) ¹	CIFAR-10	FEDAVG, FEDADAGRAD, FEDYOGI, NOVASGD, NOVAADAM, NOVAADAGRAD, NOVAYOGI, FEDPROX, PROXADAM, PROXADAGRADM SCAFFOLD, SCAFADAM, SCAFADAGRAD, SCAFYOGI

¹ Improvement over the best performing baseline. (Best baseline)

² Comparison in this cases is made between AVG and GMA. We present the method that was used alongside AVG and GMA and achieved the highest accuracy for the specific dataset. The difference regards the difference in accuracy between AVG and GMA for this method.

³ Speedup is calculated using the following formula: $Speedup = \frac{baseline}{improved}$. Speedup values < 1 mean there is a slowdown.

⁴ The percentage regards to how much less number of parameters were exchanged.

TABLE 5. Single-model/Generalization approaches – continued from previous page

Method	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
GRADIENT MASKING AVERAGE [150]	Accuracy	-0.5% (SCAFFOLD MGA) ²	MNIST	AVG
		+0.27% (FEDAVG AVG) ²	FMNIST	
		+1.44% (FEDADAM AVG) ²	FEMNIST	
		+1.35% (SCAFFOLD AVG) ²	CIFAR-10	
FEDFTG [151]	Accuracy	+2.24% (SCAFFOLD) ¹	Cifar-10	FEDAVG, FEDPROX, FEDDYN,
	Rounds to accuracy	+1.6% (SCAFFOLD) ¹	Cifar-100	MOON, SCAFFOLD,
		$\times 0.97$ (FEDDYN) ³	Cifar-10	FEDGEN, FEDDF
		$\times 1.11$ (SCAFFOLD) ³	Cifar-100	

¹ Improvement over the best performing baseline. (Best baseline)

² Comparison in this cases is made between AVG and GMA. We present the method that was used alongside AVG and GMA and achieved the highest accuracy for the specific dataset. The difference regards the difference in accuracy between AVG and GMA for this method.

³ Speedup is calculated using the following formula: $Speedup = \frac{baseline}{improved}$. Speedup values < 1 mean there is a slowdown.

through generalization, as well as the baselines used by the authors in the reported experiments, can be found in the Table 5.

In agnostic FL (AFL) [135] the learning bias issue is addressed by changing the weighting mechanism during aggregation. Instead of weighing the updates according to the sample size of each client, they propose the Agnostic FL algorithm that considers the existence of multiple distributions in the participating clients, and introduces an unbiased weighting mechanism agnostic to the clients' data distribution.

The study in [136] also supports the claim that simplistic FEDAVG is not suitable for aggregation of local updates from non-IID datasets. Inspired by the acceleration that momentum [153] imposes in gradient descent algorithms, proposes the Federated Averaging with Server Momentum (FEDAVGM) where momentum is utilized during the aggregation.

Similar approaches include the work in [154] and [140]. In FEDPROX [137] and in SCAFFOLD [138] the same issue is addressed from a different perspective. Instead of identifying inadequacy in the weighting mechanism they hold the clients responsible for drifting away from the true solution due to their non-IIDness. In FEDPROX [137] client drift is addressed by integrating a proximal term to regularize the loss function in the training procedure on the devices, preventing strong variance between the local update and the global model.

SCAFFOLD [138] introduces a server control variate which is sent to each device in every round and a client control variate that is stored in each client. The server and client control variates, which denote the drift of the

client, are used to correct the local update in the device before sending it to the parameter server. The method achieves significant speed-ups in reaching 0.5 accuracy compared to FEDAVG ($\times 3.3$) and FEDPROX ($\times 12.9$).

A similar approach to SCAFFOLD is presented in [143] named FEDDYN. FEDDYN though dynamically regularizes the local loss functions of the clients. Even though the results demonstrated performance similar to SCAFFOLD, $\approx \times 2$ less parameters than SCAFFOLD are required to be exchanged making it more efficient and suitable, especially for systems with communication constraints.

In [140] the methods proposed, FEDADAGRAD, FEDADAM and FEDYOGI, use momentum in combination with adaptive optimization on the server. The methods are primarily compared to the adaptive method FEDAVGM and vanilla FEDAVG. However, they are compared also to the SCAFFOLD method which performs poorly in the provided evaluation results with accuracy in many experiments to be lower than that of FEDAVG. This is attributed to the small number of participating clients per round used in the experiments that leads to stalling control variates on the clients. This shows that the proposed algorithm, SCAFFOLD, even though robust against heterogeneity is not suitable in the cross-device setting where clients usually have infrequent participation.

FEDDC [147] proposes a combination of SCAFFOLD and FEDPROX employing both regularization of the loss function and gradient correction. L2GD [155] in a similar fashion to SCAFFOLD employs a variance reduction technique based on control variates in the clients.

Experiments further confirm the importance of variance reduction. In the decentralized setting [67], inspired by variance reduction methods in CFL also utilized and controlled variate in clients.

FEDNOVA [139] instead of correcting the gradients on the device simply normalizes the collected updates before aggregation. The method can be used alongside other methods and experiments validate that there is an improvement in accuracy when employing FEDNOVA. The FedLin method presented in [156] combines gradient correction mechanism with sparsification techniques to also benefit the communication efficiency of the system.

The work in [146] examines a specific case of non-IID data, specifically considering the case where deviation comes from the feature space, termed as feature shift. To address the feature shift issue, FEDBN, employs batch normalization layers in the model that exclude from aggregation in the parameter server. Experiments demonstrated improvement on the accuracy compared to FEDAVG and FEDPROX.

MOON [141] addresses the client drift problem by employing contrastive learning. It is based on the idea that a model trained on all data centrally is able to produce better model representations compared to the model representations of a local model trained on a small subset. When a client receives the latest model extracts a representation of its data using the model, another representation of the data using the previous local model and a third representation of the data using the current model. The goal is to minimize the distance between the global and the current model representation and maximize the distance between the previous and the current one.

COMFED [149] argues that an optimal algorithm can be devised by the combination of existing SoTA algorithms for variance reduction and adaptive model aggregation on the server. It performs extensive experiments for the combination of a total 7 state-of-the-art methods.

The study in FEDPROTO [148] addresses heterogeneity not only in the data but in the model too by incorporating Prototype Learning. In this approach, instead of exchanging gradients of the local model, prototypes of the local data are calculated and exchanged. Prototypes, introduced in Prototypical Networks [157], represent the average feature representation of examples from a specific class. Experiments demonstrate that the method achieves an improvement in accuracy, however small it is, while at the same time exchanged parameters are reduced by 96-99% making the method suitable for devices with limited communication capabilities that are usually met on the cross-device FL setting.

In the study presented in [150], the association between the client drift issue in FL and the OOD hypothesis is examined. Based on the insights of the study, a

gradient masking technique is proposed for enforcing an agreement among clients regarding their updates, and weights to the local updates are based on the compliance of each client to this agreement.

The study in [142] evaluates the impact of non-IID data in each layer of a neural network and based on the finding that the classifier layer holds the most bias proposes a post-training regularization of the classifier layer. Experiments demonstrate improvement in the performance of all the methods used. However further analysis of the results demonstrates that the bigger benefit occurs when the method used is capable enough to learn good representations.

In [144], the authors, similarly to the work in [142], propose CREFF, Classifier Re-training with Federated Features, in which they utilize federated feature representations to address bias induced by class imbalance. In each round, the server sends the global model and a re-trained model with a different classifier to the clients. The clients use the re-trained model to extract feature gradients which are sent to the server alongside the local model update. Feature gradients are aggregated on the server and used to re-train the classifier. In a similar fashion, [145], CLIP2FL, the authors utilize the CLIP model alongside knowledge distillation to assist in training of the local models and aggregation on the server. Specifically, the CLIP model assumes the role of the teacher model on the client side and forces client training to be consistent with CLIP outputs to improve feature representation. Clients extract feature representations using the encoder of the CLIP model, building upon the idea of [142] and [144], which are sent to the central server. The central server utilizes the aggregated feature representations to retrain the global model ensuring that it is not biased towards dominating classes. Empirical results demonstrate the superiority of the method against baseline in dataset with high class imbalance. Specifically, the method improves accuracy on average by approximately +2.20 against CREFF, the best-performing baseline. However, the method relies heavily in the quality of the CLIP model which means that if the model does not perform well for a given task the performance of the method deteriorates. In addition, the added computation cost on the server increases as the number of clients increases imposing limitations on the scalability of the method.

Recently, the work in FEDFTG [151] has proposed utilizing Data-Free Knowledge Distillation to fine-tune the global model on the server. It aims to distill the knowledge from the collected updates into the global model created after aggregation. To achieve Data-Free KD, a generator on the server is responsible for creating fake data using the knowledge from the local updates. The extra training taking place on the server and the additional communication cost imposed on the client

devices make the method more suitable for the cross-silo domain.

However, recovering clients' data on the server could violate the privacy constraints of several applications, especially in the healthcare domain. Towards this end, the authors suggest employing additional privacy-preserving measures to further safeguard privacy.

2) Statistical Heterogeneity - Multi-model approaches

Single model methods, described in the previous subsection, aim to learn a model that performs well on unseen and diverse data. However, the research community has also focused on approaching statistical heterogeneity from a different perspective. Instead of aiming to learn a single model that performs well on all the clients, this approach treats each client's data as an individual task that requires learning a separate model. This subsection is further divided based on the origin of the methods employed to create the personalized models and methods presented fall in one of the following categories:

- **Personalization layers** These methods separate the neural network model layers in global and personal.
- **Multi-task** Methods derived from multi-task learning employ techniques that allow a model to be trained into multiple tasks.
- **Meta-learning** Methods derived from meta-learning algorithms aim to leverage the generalization and adaptability of meta models.
- **Knowledge distillation** Methods derived from knowledge-distillation aim to distil knowledge either from the a globally trained model to the personalized model of the client or vice versa.
- **Clustering** Clustering methods aim to identify associations between clients and learn a model for each group of clients.

Personalization layer approaches

In Table 6 the methods that utilize personalization layers are reported alongside the improvement achieved and the baselines used in the experiments conducted by the authors.

In [158] the proposed method, FEDPER, suggests the use of two groups of layers. The one considers the base model which is trained using FEDAVG and the other group considers personalization layers that are excluded from the federated aggregation and are kept locally in each device. The experiments demonstrate benefits in the context of statistical heterogeneity and outperform standard FEDAVG that aggregates the full model on the server.

Another aspect, regards the communication efficiency of the proposed method since the amount of data required to be exchanged is reduced. The algorithm presented in [159] formulates a bi-level optimization problem that achieves learning a general global model and, in parallel, personalized models for the clients. The method PFEDME utilizes a Moreau envelope to regularize the loss function on the clients.

LG-FEDAVG [160] employs two models where the local representation model is used to extract high-level representations on which the global model is trained. Clients update both the local representation model with regard to the global and the global with regard to the local model. The method outperforms FEDAVG in terms of accuracy and in terms of communication efficiency. Specifically, the experiments on CIFAR dataset demonstrate a speedup in the communication round of $\times 1.46$ and 28% less parameters exchanged to reach the same accuracy. The work also reports the benefits of training a fair method with only a small drop in accuracy.

The work in [161] proposed an adaptive method, APFL, in which the standard global model trained over FL and a local model trained only locally on the data of each device are combined with the use of mixing coefficient parameters and create a mixed personalized model for each client. Experiments demonstrate small benefits in accuracy compared to PERFEDAVG though the use of a tunable parameter to balance between global and local learning can learn the optimal mixing for each client. Moreover, the parameter could be utilized for other aspects of the FL systems like fairness.

Another approach proposed in [162] presents a system with hypernetworks. The PFEDHN method utilizes a large hypernetwork, which is trained and used by the clients to extract their model parameters. Employing a hypernetwork allows the system to integrate unseen clients. In addition, the size of the local models is not fixed and can be aligned to fit the system and thus address system heterogeneity and communication efficiency. The performance gain in system heterogeneity is also backed by experiments where clients with different architectures demonstrate improvements in accuracy compared to predecessor methods.

In PFEDGP [163], it is argued that since participating clients usually have a relatively small dataset, it is better to employ Gaussian Processes classifiers that exhibit better adaptability in non-IID datasets. Experiments conducted in this work demonstrated improvement in accuracy against baselines having PFEDHN [162] as the best-performing baseline. Interestingly PFEDHN is slightly better in the case of CIFAR-10 dataset when only a few clients participate, specifically 50 clients.

The focus in FEDREP [164] is to learn common representations globally and for each client to learn personalization layers locally. The method argues that

TABLE 6. Personalization layers approaches reported evaluation

Method	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
FEDPER [158]	Accuracy	50% (MobileNet-v1) ³ 55% (ResNet-34) ³	CIFAR-100	FEDAVG
PFEDME [159]	Accuracy	+1.3% (PER-FEDAVG) ¹	MNIST	FEDAVG, PER-FEDAVG
	Accuracy	+1.71% (PER-FEDAVG) ¹	Synthetic	
LG-FEDAVG [160]	Accuracy	+0.03% (FEDPROX) ¹	MNIST	FEDAVG, FEDPROX
	Accuracy	+3.3% (FEDPROX) ¹	MNIST (rotated data)	
	Rounds to accuracy (Speedup) Parameters communicated to accuracy	×1.46 ² +28% ⁴	CIFAR-10 CIFAR-10	FEDAVG FEDAVG
APFL [161]	Accuracy	+0.27% (PERFEDAVG) ¹	MNIST	FEDAVG, PERFEDAVG, PFEDME
PFEDHN [162]	Accuracy	+3.36% (LG-FEDAVG) ¹	CIFAR-10	LG-FEDAVG, PFEDME
		+12.39% (FEDPER) ¹	CIFAR-100	FEDPER, PER-FEDAVG
		+5.43% (PER-FEDAVG) ¹	Omniglot	FEDAVG
PFEDGP [163]	Accuracy	-1.0% (PFEDHN) ¹	CIFAR-10 50 clients	FEDAVG FEDPER FOLA
		+3.4% (PFEDHN) ¹	CIFAR-10 500 clients	LG-FEDAVG PFEDME FedU
		+3.3% (PFEDHN) ¹	CIFAR-100	PFEDHN
		+1.9% (PFEDHN) ¹	CINIC-10	
FEDREP [164]	Accuracy	+0.88% (L2GD) ¹	CIFAR-10	FEDAVG, FEDPROX, SCAFFOLD,
		-0.24% (DITTO) ¹	CIFAR-100	Fed-MTL, PERFEDAVG,
		+0.29% (FEDPER) ¹ +1.65% (FEDPER) ¹	SENT140 FEMNIST	LG-Fed, L2GD, APFL Ditto, FEDPER
PFEDLA, HeurPFEDLA [165]	Accuracy	+0.35% (PFEDHN) ¹	EMNIST	
		-0.12% (PFEDHN) ¹ +1.2% (FEDBN) ¹	FashionMnist CIFAR-10	
		+2.37% (FEDBN) ¹	CIFAR-10	
FEDPER++ [166]	Accuracy	+0.67% (Ditto) ¹	Fashion-MNIST	FEDAVG, FEDAVG-FT
		+3.41% (Ditto) ¹	CIFAR-10	FEDPER, LG-FEDAVG, FEDREP, PFEDME, Ditto

¹ Improvement over the best performing baseline.

² Speedup is calculated using the following formula: $Speedup = \frac{baseline}{improved}$

³ Model used for evaluation

⁴ This percentage regards the percentage of the reduction in the parameters exchanged to reach the same accuracy.

TABLE 6. Personalization layers approaches reported evaluation – continued from previous page

Method	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
DIS-PFL [71]	Accuracy	+1.08% (D-PSGD-FT with 50% params) ¹	CIFAR-10	D-PSGD, D-PSGD-FT
	Communication (MB)	0.00%		
	FLOPS	-53%		
FEDCP [167]	Accuracy	≈ +26% ¹	CIFAR-10 (100% Non-iiD)	FEDAVG
FEDFTHA [168]	Accuracy	+1.96% <i>d</i> (FEDREP) ¹	CIFAR-10	FEDAVG, LG-FEDAVG FEDPER, FEDREP
		+1.90% <i>d</i> (FEDREP) ¹ +0.36% <i>d</i> (LG-FEDAVG) ¹	CIFAR-100 mini-ImageNet	
FEDAVG-BE [169]	Accuracy	-0.57%	MNIST	FEDAVG
	Execution time (min)	+12%	CIFAR-10	
	Accuracy	-4.79%		
	Execution time	+8%		
FETNETS [170]	Average local accuracy on 5 clients	≈ +26% (FEDAVG) ¹	CIFAR-100	FEDAVG, FEDYOGI
	Average local accuracy on 10 clients	≈ +30.8% (FEDAVG) ¹		
SEMIPFL [171]	F1 score	9.89% (FEDHEALTH2) ₁	PAMAP2	FEDHEALTH2, FEDBN, FEDPROX, FEDPER, SemiFL, Flame FEDHAR FEDAR FedSCN
	F1 score	2.97%	HAR-UCI	
	F1 score	24%	WISDM	
	F1 score	3.98%	Mobiact	
FEDNCM [172]	Accuracy	+10% (Fine-tuning) ¹	CIFAR-10	Fine Tuning, Linear Probing
FEDICON [173]	Accuracy (attribute test-time shift)	+0.56% (T3A) ¹	CIFAR10	FEDAVG, FEDAVG-FT, FEDPROX, FEDREP, FEDBN, FedTHE, Tent, EATA, T3A
	Accuracy (covariate test-time shift)	+7.68% (FEDAVG-FT) ₁	Digit-5	
	Accuracy (covariate test-time shift)	+4.15% (FEDAVG-FT) ₁	Office-10	
PAGE [174]	Global Accuracy	+0.18% (FEDDYN) ¹	Synthetic, CIFAR100, Tiny-ImageNet,	FEDRECON, PFEDME, Ditto, FedALA, Fed-ROD FEDAVG, FEDPROX, SCAFFOLD, FEDDYN, DAP-FL,
	Local Accuracy	+0.9% (DAP-FL) ¹	Shakespeare	
FEDDPA [175]	Accuracy	+2.26% (DP-FEDSAM) ₁	FEMNIST	DP-FEDSAM, BLUR+LUS, PPSGD
	Accuracy	+5.01% (DP-FEDSAM) ₁	SVHN	
	Accuracy	+0.478% (DP-FEDSAM) ¹	CIFAR-10	

¹ Improvement over the best performing baseline.

TABLE 6. Personalization layers approaches reported evaluation – continued from previous page

Method	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
PFEDHR [176]	Accuracy	-0.06% (PFEDBAYES) 1	MNIST	
	Accuracy	+3.49% (PFEDBAYES) 1	SVHN	
	Accuracy	+4% (PFEDBAYES) ¹	CIFAR-10	
PFEDBRED [177]	Accuracy	+2.04% (PER-FEDAVG) ¹	CIFAR-10	FEDAVG, PER-FEDAVG,
	Accuracy	+1.43% (PER-FEDAVG) ¹	Sent140	PFEDME, FEDAMP, PFEDBAYES, FEDEM
FEDL2P [178]	Accuracy	+2.04% (PER-FEDAVG) ¹	CIFAR-10	FEDAVG, PER-FEDAVG,
	Accuracy	+1.43% (PER-FEDAVG) ¹	Sent140	PFEDME, FEDAMP, PFEDBAYES, FEDEM

¹ Improvement over the best performing baseline.

learning global and local objectives can be achieved by utilizing alternating minimization descent methods, which is backed by the results since the method performs well in heterogeneous data and is robust to varying levels of heterogeneity. Another key takeaway from the experiments is that FEDAVG with fine-tuning outperforms other baselines in some cases.

The PFEDLA [165] method, instead of focusing on the model of each client, focuses specifically on the most contributing layers. In the method, the contribution of each layer in the local models is evaluated and utilized to improve the aggregation mechanism. Again, the use of hypernetworks is proposed, but instead of a single network in this case a dedicated hypernetwork for each client is stored on the server, which is updated in each round.

Moreover, in contrast to other implementations, it does not consider a single weight for each local update during aggregation but unique weight parameters for each layer based on the importance of the layer. In addition, presents a heuristic approach that selects and keeps the layers with low contribution locally to benefit the communication efficiency of the algorithm. The experiments show that the method outperforms all baselines in all the cases except two in PFEDHN is slightly better. The PFEDLA though has demonstrated efficiency also towards varying client model architectures which is important in specific domains.

The study in FEDPER++ [166] aims to extend the FEDPER algorithm and improve the personalized classifier of the clients. The improved user-specific classifiers emerge from the linear combination of classifiers from clients with similar data distributions. The benefits of this approach lie in the collaboration between classifiers, which was missing in FEDPER [158].

The work presented in [71], DIS-PFL, employs a personalization method on the decentralized setting where the models in each user are personalized using unique sparsification masks. The proposed algorithm provides benefits not only in the personalization but also in communication and computation efficiency. Results show that the method achieves the highest accuracy and reduced communication cost while maintaining an adequate number of floating operations. The experiments show improvement in accuracy with the same communication cost, which indicates that the algorithm can benefit in terms of heterogeneity. However, it should be noted that there is a significant increase in floating operations, hindering the computation performance in heterogeneous settings.

A new approach introduced in [167], termed FEDCP, uses the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence to assess the degree of non-IIDness in the local datasets. KL divergence measures the difference between two distributions and is used in the study to calculate the disparity between the local and global model. The difference in disparity is referred to as the degree of non-IIDness (DoN), and it is used to constrain the personalization layer, determining whether it should deviate from the global model or not. The method has demonstrated robustness, even in scenarios with high DoN. However, experiments are conducted only between FedCP and FEDAVG and no other personalization method is considered. Moreover, the added computational cost incurred from measuring DoN should be evaluated to determine if the method is appropriate for computationally constrained devices.

Recently [168] proposed FEDFTHA which splits the problem in two parts: federated fine tuning FEDFT, responsible for discovering personalized model in each client, and federated head aggregation FEDHA, responsible for creating a general global model. In FEDFT,

the model is divided into base and personalization layers, similar to the personalization methods mentioned above, and training is performed on two phases. In the first phase, the model is trained updating all the layers followed by the second phase where it is fine-tuned and updates only the personalization layers over multiple rounds. FEDHA method on the server is also performed in two phases. The first part involves standard averaging of the updates collected by the clients during FedFT training, and the second part involves averaging the personalization layers gathered through FEDFT to create global head layers.

FEDAVG-BE [169] evaluates each sample and attempts to discard those that disrupt the dataset's distribution. The sample selection is based on entropy, operating under the assumption that high-quality samples exhibit less entropy. Initially, the entropy of all clients is calculated and aggregated in the server to form the global mean entropy. Data samples with entropy lower than the global mean are selected for training. Experiments do not demonstrate improvement in accuracy in the context of heterogeneity, though there is a significant reduction in execution times which could benefit devices with limited resources. However, calculating entropy for all participating devices beforehand might not be feasible in FL settings that involve a vast number of client devices.

In the study in [170] FETNETS is introduced. The authors utilize ensemble aggregation to create the global model. In the first phase, pruned models are dispatched to the clients for training, after which they are collected. During the second phase, the server clusters the clients based on the similarity of their pruned model embeddings. Subsequently, the server requests the full model from each cluster representative and the ensemble of these models constitutes the updated global model. The method demonstrated improved accuracy compared to FEDAVG and FEDYOGI algorithms on heterogeneous data but requires longer execution time to perform a single communication round. Considering these limitations, the method is more suitable for cross-silo FL systems that emphasize accuracy and utilize client devices with increased computational capabilities and stable network connectivity.

In PFEDGRAPH [179], the authors optimize a collaboration graph that guides how the local models are aggregated based on similarities with updates from other clients. The method allows the clients to benefit from collective intelligence while at the same time maintain the personalization of their models. On the client, side a regularization term is added that reflects the similarity between the local and the aggregated models. Results demonstrate that the method consistently outperforms the baselines including FEDPROX, FEDPER, PER-FEDAVG, PFEDME, FEDAMP, DITTO, FEDREP, PFEDHN and FedRod. However, the added complexity

and computation required for maintaining the collaboration graph as the number of clients increases should be considered.

In [173] the authors consider inter-client heterogeneity and intra-client heterogeneity and aim to utilize collective knowledge to address inter-client heterogeneity. The proposed method, FEDICON, utilizes contrastive learning to improve the fine-tuning procedure of the personalization layers. Contrastive learning is used to capture robust features that remain invariant across clients. This is achieved through a local invariance extraction scheme and global invariance sharing among clients. The local feature extraction involves training a feature encoder on the local samples and improving it by aggregating it on the server. FEDICON achieves 62.23% and 64.96% for Digit-5 and Office-10 datasets respectively under covariate test-time shift while the best performing baseline, FEDAVG+FT, achieves 54.55% and 60.45% in the same datasets. In the case of attribute shift the method achieves 86.47% accuracy while the best performing baseline, T3A achieves 85.91%. Despite these promising results, there are several limitations to consider including added computation and communication costs, and scalability issues due to the collaboratively training of the feature encoder.

In [172], the authors propose an based on a pre-trained model and careful initialization of the classifier layer. Specifically the authors propose passing all data from the model and calculate the mean feature vector (centroid) based on the feature vectors extracted from the local data for each class. This work considers training only the classifier layer with FL and fine-tuning the base model and the head after training. The method is compared against another standard fine-tuning and achieves an increases of 10% in accuracy for CIFAR-10 which demonstrates the efficiency of the proposed initialization method to handle heterogeneity. However, the method is focused on the the use of pre-trained models which might not always be the case.

In [174] the authors propose PAGE, a method that aims to balance generalization and personalization. The iterative process of balancing generalization and personalization is framed as a multi-stage co-opetition game, where clients (leaders) and the central server (follower) interact. This game is reformulated as a feedback multi-stage MLSF (Multi-Leader Single-Follower) Stackelberg game, which allows for the establishment of an implicit relationship between global and local models. Clients utilize deep deterministic policy gradients algorithm to update their local models and the server utilizes deep deterministic policy gradients to calculate weights for each client update. The method achieves substantial improvement in accuracy against the baselines. Specifically, it improves global accuracy over the best performing baseline, FEDDYN by 0.18%, excluding the synthetic

dataset where is the only where FEDDYN is better. Regarding local accuracy it is improved on average by 0.9% against DAP-FL for all four datasets. While the findings are encouraging, sophisticated reinforcement training techniques increase complexity of the method. In addition, the increasing number of participants can make it more challenging to achieve equilibrium between global and local models hindering scalability of the system.

In [175], FEDDPA, the authors propose integrating Dynamic Fisher Personalization (DFP) to enhance model personalization by utilizing layer-wise Fisher information. The Fisher information for each layer of the model is used to identify the parameters that carry significant information about the local data. During the personalization process the most informative local parameters, those with higher Fisher values, are retained ensuring flexible personalization and tailored to the specific needs of the client. The method also considers the addition of noise, and DFP is used to prevent noise from overwhelming important parameters, improving efficiency of the method in realistic scenarios where differential privacy is applied. Results demonstrate that the method combining personalization and privacy security outperforms works applying differential privacy such as DP-FEDSAM. Specifically, improves accuracy against DP-FEDSAM on average by 2.26% on FEMNIST, 5.01% on SVHN and 0.478% on CIFAR-10 for various values of epsilon. In [176], PFEDHR, the authors propose model reassembly for personalization of the model. The method employs layer decomposition, dynamic grouping of layers and reassembling candidate personalized models on the server with the assistance of public dataset. The method is tested in two settings one where clients are allowed to have different model architectures and one where all clients follow the same architecture. In the first setting the method achieves improving accuracy by 1.01% on MNIST, by 1.41% on SVHN and by 1.49% on CIFAR-10 against FedGH and FCCL. In the other setting, the method improves accuracy by 3.49% on the SVHN dataset, by 4% in CIFAR-10 dataset against PFEDBAYES. Conversely, the method does not outperform PFEDBAYES in the MNIST dataset which is attributed to the simplicity of the dataset. Despite the favorable results, the method is significantly influenced by the quality and relevance of the public data used for fine-tuning. If the public dataset is small or does not adequately capture the overall distribution of data across clients, it can lead to performance degradation. In addition, the process of dynamically generating personalized models through model reassembly can incur high computational costs, limiting scalability of the system.

In [177], PFEDBRED, the authors employ relaxed mirror descent (RMD) to extract prior information

about the local and inject them to the global model before training on the device. Results show that the method achieves 79.44% and 72.04% accuracy on CIFAR-10 and Sent140 datasets respectively outperforming the best baseline PER-FEDAVG which achieves 78.87% and 70.0% on the same datasets. Results validate that the method allows clients to effectively extract knowledge and enhance local training improving overall performance. However, some instability of the global model is observed and is recognized as a limitation of the method and a topic for future work. In addition, the implementation of the proposed method involves significant complexity, and careful tuning of the parameters should be considered. In [180], FLOW, the authors combine both global and local model parameters, utilizing a dynamic routing mechanism to enhance personalization for each client. The dynamic routing module enables each data instance to choose between global and local model parameters for the prediction. FLOW achieves an improvement of 1.33-4.58% in average client accuracy over the best-performing baselines on four datasets, indicating that a higher percentage of clients benefit from personalization under FLOW method. However, dynamic routing introduces added complexity, which might hinder performance on resource-constrained devices. In addition, the method relies on accurately estimating the distribution divergence, which is achieved by utilizing the difference in losses between global and local model which may not be always be accurate.

Multi-task based approaches

In Table 7 the methods derived from multi-task algorithms are reported alongside the improvement achieved and the baselines used in the experiments conducted by the authors.

Multi-task Learning (MTL) considers the training of a model on two objectives. Since the non-IID issue can be seen as a multi-task issue rather than a generalization problem, methods developed in the context of MTL research are also suitable candidates for the FL setting.

The first framework towards this direction, called MOCHA [181], enables personalized learning by training separate but interconnected models for each device, and utilizing a shared representation through multitask learning. The VIRTUAL [182] algorithm treats the FL setting, central server, and clients, as a Bayesian network, where learning is achieved through approximated variational inference. Clients maintain local and private parameters that are fine-tuned separately, while the server maintains and shares a posterior distribution that represents the global parameters' plausibility. In [155], the idea of softly-enforced similarity of local models, originating from the domain of multi-task relationship

TABLE 7. Multi-task based approaches

Method	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
MOCHA [181]	Primal Sub-Optimality	≈ 0.09 (COCO) ¹		COCO, Mb-SGD, Mb-SDCA
VIRTUAL [182]	Multi-task Accuracy	1.2% (FEDPROX)	FEMNIST	FEDAVG, FEDPROX
	Server Accuracy	1.0% (FEDAVG)		
	Multi-task Accuracy	0.5% (FEDAVG, FEDPROX)	MNIST	
	Server Accuracy	0.2% (FEDAVG, FEDPROX)		
	Multi-task Accuracy	-1.7% (FEDAVG)	PMNIST	
	Server Accuracy	-5.8% (FEDAVG)		
	Multi-task Accuracy	0.4% (FEDAVG)	VSN	
	Server Accuracy	-0.8% (FEDAVG)		
	Multi-task Accuracy	-0.3% (FEDAVG, FEDPROX)	HAR	
	Server Accuracy	0.3% (FEDPROX)		
L2GD+ [155]	Relative Sub-Optimality	0, 0999999	Dataset: a1a	L2GD ³
	FEDEM D-FEDEM [183]	Accuracy	1.0% (FEDPROX) ¹ 0.2% (PFEDME) 2.0% (FEDAVG+) 2.3% (PFEDME) 0.0% (FEDAVG) 5.5% (PFEDME)	FEMNIST EMNIST CIFAR10 CIFAR100 Shakespeare Synthetic
DITTO [184]	Accuracy	0.009 (PER-FEDAVG) ¹	FEMNIST	L2SGD, EWC, SKL
		-0.001 (SKL) ¹	CelebA	
MTFL [185]	Average User Accuracy	0.01 (PFEDME) ¹	MNIST	FEDAVG, PER-FEDAVG, PFEDME
		0.03 (PFEDME) ¹	CIFAR10	
FEDGRADNORM [186]	Accuracy	0.05 0.1 -0.01	RadComDynamic (modulation classification) RadComDynamic (signal classification) RadComDynamic (anomaly behavior)	FEDREP

¹ Improvement over the best performing baseline. (Best baseline)

² Speedup is calculated using the following formula: $Speedup = \frac{baseline}{improved}$

³ No baselines are provided the improvement concerns between L2GD and L2GD+ where the later includes variance reduction. The experiment showcases the importance of variance reduction.

learning, is exploited, proposing a mixture of global and local models, preventing local models from deviating strongly from their mean.

FEDEM and D-FEDEM [183] are built on the assumption that client data distributions are a mixture of underlying distributions. The proposed algorithm makes use of the Expectation-Maximization algorithm to learn shared (global) component models and personalized (local) mixture weights.

In Ditto [184], two tasks are considered: the global task, which considers all the clients' data, and the local objective, which learns a model based only on the data existing in the device. This results in a bi-level optimization problem, where the proximity of the local model to the optimal global model is controlled by a regularization term. Based on the work of [187], a Multi-Task FL algorithm is presented in [185] with private batch normalization layers, similar to the approach in [146]. Batch normalization layers are kept private, providing a personalized model for each client and enhancing privacy and communication efficiency since fewer parameters are exchanged.

FEDGRADNORM [186] generalizes the work of GradNorm [188] and presents a distributed and dynamic weighting strategy for the FL setting. The algorithm aims to dynamically adjust gradient norms so that tasks across clients are trained at similar rates.

Meta Learning approaches

In Table 8 the methods derived from meta-learning algorithms are reported alongside the improvement achieved and the baselines used in the experiments conducted by the authors.

Model-Agnostic Meta-Learning (MAML) methods, as introduced by Finn et al. [197], aim to determine an optimal initialization model that can be fine-tuned for specific tasks. In Personalized FL, each client's model can be viewed as a separate task.

The study by Chen et al. [189], established a connection between meta-learning and Personalized FL. Drawing from the perspective that each client represents a distinct task, and introduced FEDMETA, which utilizes either MAML or Meta-SGD algorithms. The proposed method seeks to learn a shared meta-model instead of a global model.

The work in [190] further backs the correlation between FL and meta-learning algorithms and proposes adding a new stage after training with FEDAVG where fine-tuning of the global model takes place using Reptile [198], a well-known MAML algorithm. The work of Khodak et al. [191] presented Average Regret-Upper-Bound Analysis (ARUBA) which allows for adaptive learning of tasks and exhibits faster learning rates.

Fallah et al. [192] proposes PER-FEDAVG, an approach also derived from MAML algorithms. In contrast to FEDMETA and FEDAVG, PER-FEDAVG emphasizes finding the best meta-model that can be used as an initialization point enabling the clients to fine-tune it locally and obtain a personalized model tailored to their dataset.

The work on [193] is also based on the extension of meta-learning algorithms in the setting of personalized FL. Specifically, it utilizes prototypical networks [199] as the meta-learning algorithm and additionally proposes debiasing the local objectives towards the global objective.

More recently Singhal et al. [194], proposed FE-DRECON, a model-agnostic approach that divides the model into global and local parts. The purpose of the algorithm is to train the global parameters in a way that the local parameters can easily be reconstructed. The proposed method has many benefits, not only because it enables fast adaptation to the client's data but also helps in handling unseen clients since no state is required for reconstructing the local model.

The study in [195] considers the need for group-based personalization based on the assumption that client data distributions might exhibit large deviations that prevent convergence of the global model. In the proposed method, G-FML, the focus is to group clients based on their distribution and learn a model for each group.

In [196] the authors propose a Bayesian metalearning approach termed meta-variational dropout, MetaVD. The authors propose utilizing a hypernetwork to predict dropout rates for each neural network parameter that are tailored to the specific data distribution of each client. The method utilizes the estimated dropouts during aggregation to weigh each client's local update. MetaVD can be used complementary to other methods, and results validate that it benefits performance. Specifically, for the CIFAR-100 dataset improved FEDAVG by 2.44%, REPTILE by 0.79% and MAML by 0.62%. Conversely, it didn't significantly improved the PERFEDAVG algorithm for the CIFAR-100 dataset increasing accuracy only by 0.03%. The study's outcomes show that MetaVD enhances performance, though not without limitations. The use of hypernetworks for the prediction of clients dropout rates increases computational cost on the server and training times. As clients increase the added computational cost and training time restrict the systems scalability.

Knowledge distillation approaches

In Table 9 the methods derived from knowledge distillation algorithms are reported alongside the improvement achieved and the baselines used in the experiments conducted by the authors.

TABLE 8. Meta-Learning approaches

Method	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
FEDMETA (MAML) [189]	Accuracy	+4.88% (META) ^{1,2} +5.3% (FEDAVG) ¹ +4.84% (FEDAVG) ¹	Femnist Shakespeare Sent140	FEDAVG, FEDAVG(META)
FEDMETA (Meta-SGD) [189]	Accuracy	+5.68% (META) ^{1,2} +3.96% (FEDAVG) ¹ +5.71% (FEDAVG) ¹	Femnist Shakespeare Sent140	FEDAVG, FEDAVG(META)
Personalized FEDAVG [190]				
ARUBA [191]	Accuracy	+0.04 +0.00	Shakespeare	FEDAVG FEDAVG(tuned)
PER-FEDAVG [192]	Accuracy	+3.89% +12.66%	MNIST CIFAR-10	FEDAVG FEDAVG
PFL debias [193]	Model transmissions to target accuracy (Speedup) ³	×9.2 – ×10.8	CIFAR-10	PER-FEDAVG
3 classes/device⁴		×6.4 – ×18.6	CIFAR-100	
5 classes/device⁴		×6.2 – ×9.5	CIFAR-10	PER-FEDAVG
7 classes/device⁴		×4.9 – ×11.3	CIFAR-100	
		×4.5 – ×16.9	CIFAR-10	PER-FEDAVG
		×6.3 – ×16.6	CIFAR-100	
FEDRECON [194]	RMSE Accuracy	+0.032 +1.8	Movielens	FEDAVG
G-FML [195]	Accuracy	+0.63% (IFCA) −0.84% (FEDAVG+Update) +3.10% (FEDAVG+Update)	Synthetic FEMNIST Shakespeare	FEDAVG, FEDPROX FEDAVG+Update, IFCA, PER-FEDAVG
META VD [196]		+0.62% (MAML) +0.03% (PERFEDAVG)	CIFAR-100 CIFAR-100	FEDAVG, REPTILE, MAML, PERFEDAVG FEDAVG, REPTILE, MAML, PERFEDAVG

¹ Improvement over the best performing baseline. (Best baseline)

² (META) denotes the FEDAVG(META) baseline.

³ Speedup is calculated using the following formula: $Speedup = \frac{baseline}{improved}$

⁴ Number of classes per depicts the heterogeneity where fewer classes in each device indicate higher heterogeneity.

Knowledge distillation (KD) refers to the methods that aim to transfer knowledge from a large model or a set of models to a smaller one, usually also referred to as the teacher-student paradigm. KD has also been utilized to address data heterogeneity. The work on FEDMD [200] proposed knowledge distillation for FL over arbitrary neural network architectures. Even though the main goal was to address model heterogeneity by allowing the clients to define their own model architectures, it is also useful in the context of data heterogeneity and personalization. The method requires a public dataset which is used by the clients for training and for generating predictions. The predictions of each client are

consumed by a knowledge distillation method and the new global model is generated.

The work on [201] proposes the use of KD to transfer knowledge from the global model to the clients. The algorithm considers a large model on the server split into two parts, a small part for feature extraction that is trained collaboratively with the clients and a large model that resides on the server. The clients also hold a classifier model which combined with the shared feature extractor creates a full model on the device. The results of the local training alongside the logits are used to train the model on the server, which in turn is sent to the clients.

TABLE 9. Knowledge distillation and transfer learning approaches

Method	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
FEDMD [200]	Accuracy	N/A	FEMNIST CIFAR-100	N/A
FEDGKT (ResNet-8) [201]	Accuracy	-0.01%	CIFAR-10	FEDAVG(ResNet-56)
		-0.02%	CIFAR-100	
		-0.05%	CINIC-10	
	Edge computational efficiency (petaFLOPs) ¹	94.0%	CIFAR-100	ResNet-110
		88.0%		ResNet-56
	Edge computational efficiency (Params) ¹	99.9%		ResNet-110
		98.0%		ResNet-56
	Edge computational efficiency (CPU ms) ¹	96.8%		ResNet-110
		93.0%		ResNet-56
FEDDF [202]	Rounds to accuracy 80%	×4.64	CIFAR-10	FEDAVG
	$\alpha = 1$ ² (speedup) ³	×4.01		FEDPROX [137]
		×4.82		FEDAVGM
	Rounds to accuracy 75%	×3.9	CIFAR-10	FEDAVG
	$\alpha = 0.1$ ² (speedup) ³	×3.37		FEDPROX
		×4.02		FEDAVGM
FEDGEN [203]	Top-1 Accuracy $\alpha = 0.05$ ²	+1.28% (FEDDFusion) ⁴	MNIST	FEDAVG, FEDPROX
	Top-1 Accuracy $\alpha = 0.1$ ²	+1.92% (FEDDFusion) ⁴	MNIST	FedEnsemble, FEDDISTill [204]
	Top-1 Accuracy $\alpha = 1$ ²	+0.79% (FEDDISTill)	MNIST	FEDDFusion [205]
PFEDSD [206]	Accuracy	+0.14% (FEDPER)	FMNIST	FEDAVG FEDPROX
		+0.15% (FEDPER)	CIFAR-10	FEDPER
		+3.98% (FEDPER)	CIFAR-100	LG-FEDAVG PFEDME
				FedFomo
CD ² -PFEd [207]	Accuracy	+0.05% (LG-Fed) ⁴	CIFAR-10	FEDAVG LG-Fed
		+1.21% (LG-Fed) ⁴	CIFAR-100	FEDPER
FED-CO2 [208]	Accuracy	+ 4.0% (FEDBN) ⁴	Office-Caltech10	FEDAVG, FEDPROX, FEDPER,
	Accuracy	+ 3.88% (FEDBN) ⁴	DomainNet	MOON, FEDROD, FEDBN
	Accuracy	+ 6.93% (FEDBN) ⁴	CIFAR100	
FEDHKT [209]	Accuracy	+ 6.6% (FEDMD, FEDAVG) ⁴	CIFAR-100	FEDAVG, FEDPROX, FEDMD, FEDGKT, FEDDF, FEDET
CO-DISTILATION [210]	Personalized Accuracy	+1, 33% (FEDROD) ⁴	iNaturalist-2017	FEDPROX, FEDDYN, Ditto
	Global Accuracy	+1.59% (FEDROD) ⁴	iNaturalist-2017	FEDREP, FEDROD, FedBABU
DFRD [211]	Accuracy	+17.28% (FEDFTG) ⁴	MNIST SVHN CIFAR-10 CIFAR-100	FEDFTG, DENSE

¹ The improvement in petaFLOPs, Params, and CPU usage reflects the percentage by which their requirements have been reduced.

² Parameter α depicts the heterogeneity of the dataset where smaller α indicates higher heterogeneity.

³ Speedup is calculated using the following formula: $Speedup = \frac{baseline}{improved}$

⁴ Improvement over the best performing baseline. (Best baseline)

Another approach using KD, proposed in [202] replaces the aggregation on the server with model ensemble distillation. The server distills knowledge from the collected client models into the server model. Ensemble distillation requires the existence of data in the server, to overcome this issue the method proposes the use of unlabeled datasets from other domains or the generation of synthetic data.

In contrast to the previous method, the work in [203] utilizes knowledge distillation without the need for a dataset on the server. The method, termed 'Federated Distillation via Generative Learning,' trains a generator on the server, which is used to distill knowledge to the client models. The conditional generator is trained using the induced distribution of each client's data over a latent space, requiring access only to the local model parameters, thus eliminating the need for a dataset on the server.

The work on PFEDSD [206] argues that initialization of the local model in each round leads to the model forgetting historical personalized knowledge. To address this, proposes storing the previous personalized models in memory and inducing knowledge from them via a Knowledge Distillation method during local training. The proposed method alleviates the issue of forgetting in personalized FL but requires clients to maintain a state of the previous round to do so.

In [207], CD²-PFEd utilizes channel decoupling to separate the global from the personal model. Follows the same concept of separating layers into global and personalized but instead of doing so vertically the separation is done horizontally in the channels. Cyclic knowledge distillation is employed on the clients to transfer knowledge between the global and personalized channels.

The study in [212] proposes a novel approach that utilizes the Low-Rank plus Sparse technique. The global model termed Global Knowledge Representation (GKR) in the paper, consists of a low-rank global representation and is decomposed into two smaller matrices that are distributed to the clients. The client first optimizes the parameters of GKR using its local data and then proceeds with model fusion to generate the personalized model. The client fuses the low-rank representation GKR and its sparsified personal model to form the personalized model. Despite these successful results, there are areas where the study faces limitations. The mutual learning on each client device makes the method unsuitable for scenarios where devices have limited computational resources. In addition, the added computational cost might also hinder the scalability of the system by introducing stragglers.

In [209], FEDHKT, the authors present a clustering based approach where edge nodes cluster clients using an heterogeneity-aware clustering algorithm, where each cluster train a different model. Knowledge distillation in

the method is used to distil knowledge from the edge models to the central server improving its generalization. Experimental results demonstrate an improvement of at least 6.6% in the setting with 20 clients which is further increased in the setting with 50 clients indicating that the method performs better in large-scale scenarios. In [210] spectral co-distillation is utilized on the clients. In the proposed method, the global and the local model alternate between the roles of teacher and student to distill knowledge. First the global model becomes the teacher to pass knowledge to the local model and then knowledge is distilled from the trained personalized model to the global one. In addition the method employs an wait-free protocol where clients take advantage of the idle time to further improve their personalized models. Results demonstrate 1.33% improvement in personal model accuracy and 1.59% in global model accuracy against FEDROD. CO-DISTILLATION on the client side increases computational costs which might limit feasibility of the method to resource constraint devices and possibly introduce stragglers in the system. The wait-free protocol partially addresses this issue by allowing faster clients to benefit from idle time, but it is recognized that more efficient methods should be considered.

In [211], DFRD, the authors propose a data free knowledge distillation on the server method. The method employs a generator to produce a synthetic dataset, which in turn is used in conjunction with the local updates to distill knowledge to the global model. Results demonstrate that the method improves accuracy even up to 17.28% against FEDFTG in four datasets, MNIST SVHN CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100. The limitations of the method derive from the dependence of to the synthetic data generator which not be able to always produce data that capture the features and true distribution of the data and from the added computational cost which hinders the systems scalability.

The work in [208] proposes FED-CO2, a framework that utilizes knowledge transfer. In this work, each client maintains two models: the online model, which is partially personalized and is trained collaboratively with FL, and the offline local model, which is trained only on the local data in the device. The method proposes using mutual learning and knowledge distillation between the two models on both directions. Both the online and offline models are trained by integrating knowledge from each other to enhance their training. In contrast to most similar works, the method considers also the feature skew among clients. Empirical results demonstrate that the method is able to address heterogeneity from label skew as well as feature skew and improve accuracy nearly 4% on every dataset against the best performing baseline FEDBN [146] in the case of feature skew. For the label skew the method achieves an improvement of

+6.93% against FEDBN for CIFAR-100 dataset.

Clustering-based approaches

In Table 10 the methods that cluster clients are reported alongside the improvement achieved and the baselines used in the experiments conducted by the authors.

In the method proposed in [213], CBFL, clusters the clients and trains a model for each cluster. The method employs an autoencoder that is trained on each client. The collected encoder updates form the new encoder in the server. In the next phase clients use it on their data and send the average of their features that is used by the server to define clusters. In the third phase the clients train the model locally and contribute to the update of the global model of the cluster they belong to. Even though the algorithm presents a clustering based approach essential communication and computational cost is added. In addition, encoding sensitive client data can still result in information leakage. The average of encoded features might risk exposing information about individual data points especially in the presence of outliers in the dataset.

In the study presented in [214], the Clustered FL (CFL) method also groups clients based on the similarity of their data distributions and generating an optimal model for each cluster. Initially, clients are separated into those with congruent data distributions and those with incongruent data distributions. This is done to avoid unnecessary clustering of incongruent clients which could harm the generalization of their model. In contrast to the previous implementations, this method considers privacy implications that might arise as well as a dynamically changing client population.

In [215], a proximal term is employed in the clients' loss function to limit the distance between the generated local model and the nearest global model. The proposed algorithm, FESEM, consists of joint optimization that aims to discover the optimal clusters by minimizing the intra-cluster distance of the model. The clients train their models to be close to the global model of the cluster to which they belong.

A similar approach to CFL is presented in [216], FL+HC, which utilizes hierarchical clustering for the clients. In contrast to the more complex method proposed in [214] in this method a single clustering step is added simplifying the method and reducing possible computational costs. In addition, the method is able to work with various similarity measures.

As mentioned above, Iterative Federated Clustering algorithm (IFCA) that is presented in [217], also employs a clustering-based method. Though in this case, the shared representation layers are trained on all clients and only the last layers are considered in clustering.

In [218] the clustering is based on task relatedness. The algorithm considers a one-shot FL clustering approach. Before starting the FL rounds, the server collects the embeddings of the clients' data and calculates the Unified Manifold Approximation (UMAP) [222] for each client embedding. Finally, the clustering is done based on the distances between these approximations. One of the advantages of the proposed algorithm is that the clustering is achieved in one round without incurring additional communication and computation cost. Moreover, various distance metrics can be utilized for clustering and, finally, it allows the clients to be part of multiple clusters. However, the calculation of embeddings for the clients data requires an already trained encoder, which means that a public dataset to train this encoder is required beforehand.

In FedGroup [219] another measure for clustering is introduced based on the client data. The similarity measure used for the clustering is termed as the Euclidean distance of Decomposed Cosine similarity (EDC). Additionally, the proposed method is further extended by integrating FEDPROX, creating the FEDGROUPTPROX method.

The work on [195] G-FML combines clustering and meta-learning approaches to provide personalized models for the clients. A deep autoencoder is utilized to learn the low-level representation of the data in each client, the aggregation of the representations are used as representation of the clients data distribution. These representations are collected by the server to define the clusters using the k-means algorithm. Additionally, a meta-model is initialized for each cluster defined in the previous step. The rest of the algorithm optimizes the meta-model of each group through FL and the encoding and clustering procedure described above is repeated until convergence. Like similar approaches, the utilization of an encoder on the clients and the exchange of representations alongside meta-model updates, incurs additional communication and computation costs. Moreover, even though the dynamic allocation of client into clusters is considered the total number of cluster is a hyperparameter of the algorithm defined apriori.

In FLIS [220] the formulation of the cluster is achieved using inference similarity to measure similarity among clients data distributions. In contrast to previous methods the number of clusters is not required to be known beforehand, utilizes Hierarchical Clustering and considers joint as well as disjoint clusters. The inference similarity proposed, is achieved using an auxiliary dataset on the server and performing inference with the local model updates of each client. The classification layer of each local update is then used to form an adjacency matrix between clients to form the clusters. Again the use of an auxiliary dataset might not always be feasible. However, the proposed method does not incur additional

TABLE 10. Clustering-based approaches

Method	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
CBFL [213]	Rounds to 0.6895 ROC AUC	×1.25 (−25%)	eICU	Centralized, FL
CFL [214]	Perplexity	−14.2%	MNIST, CIFAR-10	FL
FESEM [215]	Micro-Acc	+5.5% (FEDAVG)	FEMNIST	FEDSGD, FEDAVG, FEDDIST, FEDPROX, FEDDIST+WS, Robust(TKM), FEDCLUSTER
	Micro-F1	+3.5% (FEDAVG)		
	Macro-Acc	+2.1% (FEDAVG)		
	Macro-F1	−0.1% (FEDCLUSTER)		
FL+HC [216]	Accuracy in 50 rounds	×1.0	MNIST, FEMNIST	FL
FL+HC [216]	Clients to reach accuracy	×1.1		
IFCA [217]	Accuracy	+5.52% +3.64%	Rotated MNIST Rotated CIFAR	FL, Local
FLT [218]	Accuracy	−0.03% (FEDSEM) +7.3% (FEDSEM)	MNIST CIFAR10	FEDAVG, Local, PCA+kM+HC, FEDSEM, CFL, IFCA
		+1.66% (FEDSEM), +12.87% (IFCA)	FEMNIST MLP	
		+2.15% (FEDSEM), +0.67% (IFCA)	FEMNIST CNN	
		+17.47% (FEDSEM)	Non-iid FEMNIST CNN	
G-FML [195]	Accuracy	+0.63% (IFCA) −0.84% (FEDAVG+Update)	Synthetic FEMNIST	FEDAVG, FEDPROX FEDAVG+Update, IFCA, PER-FEDAVG
		+3.10% (FEDAVG+Update)	Shakespeare	
FedGroup FEDGROUPROX [219]	Accuracy	+4.0% (FESEM) +0.01% (IFCA)	MNIST	FEDAVG, FEDPROX IFCA, FESEM
		+26.9% (FESEM) +1.3% (IFCA)	FEMNIST	
		−3.7% (FESEM) −7.1% (IFCA)	SYNTHETIC	
		+5.3% (FESEM) −1.5% (IFCA)	SENT140	
FLIS [220]	Accuracy	+1.49% (IFCA) +6.75% (PERFEDAVG)	FMNIST CIFAR-10	FEDAVG, FEDPROX FEDNOVA, Scaffold, LG
		+6.18% (IFCA)	CIFAR-100	
	Rounds to accuracy Speedup	×1.07 (LG)	FMNIST	PERFEDAVG, IFCA, CFL
		×1.04 (IFCA) ×1.07 (IFCA) ×1.06 (LG)	CIFAR-10 CIFAR-100 SVHN	
CAM [221]	Accuracy	+3.59% (IFCA)	FashionMNIST	IFCA

communication costs. The main issue in clustering-based approaches is that the clustering of the clients must be done while ensuring their data remains decentralized and private. Additional communication and computational cost are usually incurred to create client representations and form the clusters.

In the work in [221] aim to address clustering collapse issue observed in standard clustering approaches in FL where a cluster dominates the others as training progresses and can be integrated into existing cluster methods. In this method, clients train their local models based on the model from the cluster to which they belong and upload their updates. The server then uses the updates to refine both the cluster models and the global model. The integration of CAM into IFCA resulted in an accuracy increase from 90.13% to 93.72% on the Fashion-MNIST dataset, demonstrating a notable improvement in model performance. Even though the method enhances cluster based methods it still relies to the performance of the clustering method used.

In [223] the authors propose a label clustering approach, FEDLC. By clustering based on labels ensure that clients with similar tasks are clustered together. In addition, the method assesses the quality of the clients' datasets before training. Also an adaptive client selection mechanism is employed to avoid clients with skewed data distributions. The method successfully stabilizes the training procedure and maintains higher accuracy with non-IID clients. For FMNIST dataset the method improved accuracy by 0.5% against the method utilizing an auxiliary dataset for clustering while the difference is significantly increased in the CIFAR-10 dataset which is 14.4% indicating that the method can handle the added complexity of the task. The limitation of the proposed method lies in the clustering using labels where extremely skewed datasets may hinder performance of the clustering algorithm.

Other approaches

Another approach is presented in [224], PERFED-GAN, which employs generative adversarial network (GAN) for personalization. The GAN is used to generate samples that are sent to the central server. The role of the discriminator network in the GAN is fulfilled by the local neural network, which is trained on the true samples of the client and remains private. In each round, the server selects a subset of the generated samples for each client. The algorithm then proceeds with further training on both actual and generated data and improve both the discriminator and the generative model. To address the privacy issues that arise from exchanging generated samples, the method suggests to the utilization of privacy-preserving GAN algorithms like DP-CGAN [225].

3) System heterogeneity

FL systems also face system heterogeneity challenges. Clients participating in FL systems are likely to have differences in hardware and network resources, especially when IoT devices are employed. Hardware limitations in processing capability and memory affect the training procedure and execution time.

In addition, network connectivity is not always reliable or guaranteed, and in many cases, it may have latency and bandwidth constraints. Differences in system characteristics introduce serious issues that hinder the performance of the system. Unreliable communications lead to client dropouts, resulting in a system that either aggregates using only a small subset of the required clients or waits for long periods for slow devices to send their updates.

Waiting for slow devices, referred to as the stragglers' effect, not only results in increased execution time but also leads to underutilization of resources. Waiting for slower devices means that faster devices spend most of their time idle, waiting for further instructions. System heterogeneity has mainly been addressed in two aspects of an FL system. The first is by employing client selection methods, which are primarily based on the insight that stragglers can be identified and excluded from the training. The second is by relaxing the assumption of synchronous aggregation of updates. By utilizing an asynchronous aggregation algorithm participating devices can train on their data even for a large amount of time without blocking the aggregation and the update of the global model. Thus, this subsection is further divided into the following categories:

- **Client selection** based approaches that aim to select the most suited clients for participation.
- **Asynchronous communication** approaches that aim to eliminate the bottleneck caused by synchronization issues due to the existence of stragglers by employing asynchronous communication protocols.

Client selection based approaches

In Table 11 the methods that employ client selection are reported alongside the improvement achieved and the baselines used in the experiments conducted by the authors.

Recognizing that several clients might disrupt the process and hinder system performance, research has focused on discovering mechanisms to select the most suitable subsets of clients, avoiding stragglers and promoting fast convergence. In the work presented in [227], a semi-synchronous method is proposed, combined with a client selection mechanism that selects clients with larger

TABLE 11. Client Selection approaches for System heterogeneity

Method	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
FEDCS [226]	Time to target accuracy 75% (min)	-36.56%	CIFAR-10	FedLim
	Time to target accuracy 85% (min)	-51.9%	Fashion-MNIST	
Priority function [227]	Accuracy over epoch	$\approx +10.7\%$ (average relative difference)	FMNIST	FEDAVG
	Speedup to 75% accuracy	$\approx +33\%$	MNIST	
	Speedup to 85% accuracy	$\approx +6.6\%$ (average relative difference) $\approx +33.33\% \times 1.33$		
OCEAN [228]	Accuracy over time (rounds)	$\approx +15.33\%$ (average relative difference)	MNIST	No client selection, AMO, SMO
FEDAR [229]	Accuracy over time (rounds)	N/A	MNIST	N/A
[230]	Time to target accuracy 95% (min)	$\times 1.53$ $\times 1.69$	MNIST, Fashion-MNIST	RNS-FL SFL
OORT [231]	Speedup to 74.9% accuracy	$\times 12.1$	OpenImage-Easy	FEDPROX
	Speedup to 53.1% accuracy	$\times 5.7$ $\times 14.1$	OpenImage	FEDYOGI FEDPROX
	39 Perplexity	$\times 5.8$ $\times 8.4$	Reddit	FEDYOGI FEDPROX
	39 Perplexity	$\times 7.3$ $\times 9.1$	StackOverflow	FEDYOGI FEDPROX
	Speedup to 62.2% accuracy	$\times 7.8$ $\times 1.2$	Google Speech	FEDYOGI
		$\times 1.3$		FEDYOGI
SCOUT [232]	Accuracy to round	+36.45% -0.12% +54.76%	FEMNIST	Random DUO RUO
	Total training time	+16.89% -6.47% -0.55% -13.82%		OORT Random DUO RUO
	Final accuracy	+1.09% +2.75% +2.96% +6.73% +2.09%		OORT Random DUO RUO OORT
RAWCS [233]	Final accuracy	+0.01%		POC-0.1, POC-0.3, POC-0.5
ADAPTIVE CLIENT SAMPLING [234]	Time reduction	$-2.9\times$ (statistical)	EMNIST, Synthetic, MNIST,	statistical, weighted, uniform, full
	Time reduction	$-2.1\times$ (statistical)		
	Time reduction	$-1.5\times$ (statistical)		
INTELLIFL [122]	Accuracy	-0.01%	MNIST, CIFAR-10, FASHIONMNIST	FEDAVG HETEROFL
	Latency	-22%		FEDPROX FEDNOVA
	Communication cost	-12%		OORT, FEDMARL

TABLE 12. Client Selection approaches for System heterogeneity part 2

Method	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
DELTA [235]	Accuracy / Rounds	+0.84%/1.12× (Cluster-based IS)	FashionMNIST,	FEDAVG HETEROFL
	Accuracy / Rounds	+0.15%/1.03× (FEDPRACIS)	CIFAR-10,	FEDAVG HETEROFL
	Accuracy / Rounds	+1.33%/1.12× (FEDPRACIS)	Femnist,	FEDAVG HETEROFL
	Accuracy / Rounds	+1.55%/1.06× (FEDPRACIS)	CelebA,	FEDAVG HETEROFL

amounts of data and higher computing capabilities based on a priority function. The priority function requires three metrics from each client: the volume of data, an estimate of computational capability, and communication delay. Based on this information, the priority function assigns priorities to the clients. A higher priority gives the client a higher probability of being selected.

The FEDCS algorithm presented in [226] samples clients based on their resources. The resources of the clients are gathered in the first step of the algorithm and include information regarding the state of the communication channel, available computational resources, and the size of the local dataset. The selection algorithm aims to utilize as many clients as possible within a given time window, and so it is formulated as a maximization problem, which is solved using a greedy algorithm.

The work in [228] introduces a Wireless FL Network (WFLN) with a selection mechanism based on the condition of each client's communication channel and remaining battery. The proposed method applies constraints on the total energy consumption of each client across all rounds. The selection mechanism utilized tries to select clients and allocate bandwidth without exceeding the constraints for a set of predefined rounds.

In [229], the client selection mechanism considers the availability of resources in the client. The work is focused on IoT and using the memory, bandwidth, and battery life of the client to evaluate which clients have the resources required to execute the task. In addition, a trust mechanism is employed, which rewards clients that submit their results within the given time window, encouraging the participation of successful clients.

In [230] the work is focused on leveraging an estimate of the computing contribution and by evaluating the communication of each client. Communication is measured using the response time of each client on a request submitted by the server after aggregation. The computing contribution of each client is determined by the product of the number of local updates performed and the minimum batch size.

In the OORT presented in [231], the aim is to reduce the convergence time required to reach a specific level of performance. This is achieved by selecting clients that

provide better accuracy results and shorter execution times during training. OORT considers the problem as a tradeoff between statistical and system efficiency and calculates the utility of the client using both.

The work on [236] bases the selection mechanism proposed not only on the resources of the clients but also incorporates trust. Trust is modeled based on clients' resource consumption, with under- or over-consumption classified as suspicious. The trust scores calculated are then fed into the Deep Reinforcement Learning selection algorithm that allows the central server to determine the optimal selection strategy.

In PYRAMID-FL [118] the ranking score used for client selection is based on a utility score similar to OORT. However, in this method, the utility score is further utilized by each client to adjust aspects of the local training procedure. Specifically based on the ranking score the client can opt on more local iterations if the execution times that are achieved allow it or based on the contribution to opt on minimizing communication cost by sending only the important parameters of the local update.

Recently SCOUT [232] utilizes data and resources to model the utility. In addition, considering the correlation between clients and similarly to FEDCOR in [119] improves the diversity of the selected clients.

The work in [233] presents a Resource-Aware Client Selection algorithm (RAWCS) that takes into consideration the contribution and energy consumption incurred by the client during training. The goal is to save the resources of the clients while maintaining the accuracy of the system. Client utility is defined using limitations in processing time, communication channel quality, and battery levels, if a client satisfies these limits is a candidate for participation in the next round. The final selection consists of a random subset of the candidate clients. Randomness avoids bias towards more efficient clients.

In [234] an adaptive client selection method is proposed that takes into consideration not only statistical but also system heterogeneity and promotes selection of clients with more valuable or with better communication capabilities. The proposed scheme aims to reduce

communication time to reduce overall wall clock time of the training. The method is evaluated in three datasets and requires about 66% less time than weighted sampling and statistical sampling to achieving the same target loss. Even though the presented results demonstrate reduction in wall-clock time, it may require more training rounds compared to baselines. This trade-off could be a concern in some scenarios. In [122] the authors propose INTELLIFL, which employs MARL and enables decentralized decision-making among client devices. A key component is the intelligent client selection scheme based on reinforcement learning which selects clients that contribute the most to models accuracy considering also their resource capabilities. Additionally, the method employs a layer-wise partitioning of the model which splits the model to sub-models and which then are assigned to clients based on its capabilities. The work presents an elastic resource management framework that can also adapt to changes in the environment, making it very efficient. In addition, this elasticity enhances the systems scalability as it can effectively adapt itself as the number of clients increases or as clients with varying capabilities join or leave the system. INTELLIFL demonstrates improvements against the baselines in two out of three performance metrics: accuracy, latency and communication cost. Specifically, it demonstrates state of the art accuracy while reducing on average latency by 22% and communication cost by 12%.

In [235], propose DivErse cLienT sAmpling (DELTA), a method that promotes selection of clients with diverse gradients resulting in gradients with not only higher magnitude but also varied in direction. DELTA achieves a higher convergence rate, validated by results demonstrating 72.1% accuracy in 322 rounds on the FashionMNIST dataset, while the best-performing baseline, Cluster-based IS, achieved 71.21% in 362 rounds. Overall, while DELTA offers promising improvements, the variance-based method assumes that client data is of good quality and representative, making the method vulnerable and inefficient in the face of attacks.

Asynchronous communication approaches

In Table 13 the methods that employ asynchronous communication protocols are reported alongside the improvement achieved and the baselines used in the experiments conducted by the authors.

Most FL system implementations typically involve synchronous FL, where the central server updates the shared global model only after all client updates have been collected. Processing capabilities as well as other system-related aspects differ from device to device, making device availability and training time vary. This makes synchronization challenging in real-world FL scenarios.

Research in distributed stochastic gradient descent focused on asynchronous training [242] to address stragglers and latency, leading to the introduction of asynchronous FL. In asynchronous FL, the server updates the shared global model as soon as a new update is collected [237] [238].

Various studies have focused on refining and optimizing the asynchronous FL approach to make it more effective and practical for real-world applications. In [237] an asynchronous FL system is proposed based on two key ideas:

- 1) solve regularized local problems to guarantee convergence
- 2) and use a weighted average to update the global model, where the mixing weight is set adaptively as a function of the staleness

The proposed system facilitates non-blocking communication between the server and clients. The server consists of two main components the scheduler and the updater which run asynchronously and in parallel. The scheduler's primary role is to trigger training tasks at specific intervals while controlling the staleness of the information used by the updater. Staleness is represented by the difference between the current time (t) and the timestamp (T) of the data received by the updater thread. The updater receives models from the workers and is responsible for aggregating and updating the global model. Staleness is used to determine the mixing value that is used to weight the local update during aggregation. Large staleness incurs greater error during aggregation thus the mixing value is decreased to reduce it.

In ASO-FED [238] an ASynchronous Online FL framework is presented which focuses on an asynchronous system with convergence guarantees that maintain optimal performance. The work in ASO-FED is closely related to IoT and Industrial settings since it considers not only heterogeneous devices and data but also considers the existence of continuous data streams and addresses it by employing an online learning procedure.

Gradients resulting from training are being balanced with the help of an iterative procedure. To ensure an optimal global model the deviation of the local gradients is constrained with the use of a threshold imposed locally on the devices. The server maintains a global model and each device keeps a copy of the global model in their memory. The server aggregates each client update the moment it arrives. The aggregated model undergoes feature learning to extract a cross-client feature representation, which is used to dynamically modify learning rates for the clients.

The inspiration for feature learning comes from attention mechanisms, which have proven to be highly effective in identifying crucial features and representing

TABLE 13. Asynchronous communication approach

Method	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
FEDASYNC [237]	Accuracy / number of gradients Accuracy / perplexity	$\approx +3\%$ (average relative difference) $\approx -26\%$ (average relative difference)	CIFAR-10, WikiText-2	FEDAVG, Centralized
ASO-FED [238]	MAE, SMAPE MAE, SMAPE F1, Precision Recall, BA Accuracy	+3.52%, +2.67% +0.03%, +4.54% 0.00%, -4.34% +6.06%, +2.41% +3.26%	FitRec Air Quality ExtraSensory ExtraSensory Fashion-MNIST	FEDAVG, FEDPROX, FEDASYNC, Local, Centralized
TEA-FED [239]	Accuracy over time Time to accuracy	$\approx +0.79\%$ (average relative difference) -66.70%	Fashion-MNIST	FEDAVG, FEDASYNC
FEDBUFF [240]	Speedup to target accuracy	$\times 1.2$ $\times 2.5$ $\times 1.1$	CelebA Sent140 CIFAR-10	FEDASYNC, FEDAVGM, FEDAVG, FEDPROX
QUAFL [241]	Loss over time	$\approx -35\%$ (average relative difference)	MNIST, Fashion MNIST, CIFAR-10, CelebA	FEDBUFF, FEDAVG
ASYNCHRONOUS SGD [242]	Convergence rate	$\mathcal{O}(\sigma^2 \varepsilon^{-2} + \tau_{avg} \varepsilon^{-1})$	N/A	SGD
FEDAAM [243]	Rounds to Accuracy	$-1.12 \times$ (FEDAVG)	CIFAR-10	FEDAVG, FEDASYNC, FEDAA
GENERALIZED ASYNCSGD [244]	Accuracy	10% (ASYNCSGD)	CIFAR-10	ASYNCSGD, FEDBUFF

them in a meaningful way. When new data are collected on the device the global model is requested and is trained on them, the balance between the previous model and the new one is achieved using a decay coefficient. The dynamic learning step size, which is calculated based on feature representation, is used to address stragglers and improve performance. Stragglers are considered to have a smaller activation rate when using the global model and thus their learning step size is increased.

The work in [240] presents a system that attempts to combine the best of both worlds. It incorporates enhanced scalability through asynchronous aggregation while aligning with privacy-preserving algorithms designed for synchronous FL, such as differential privacy and secure aggregation. It is evident that previous work mainly addressed the scalability issues in the presence of stragglers but neglected privacy guarantees which is the most valuable characteristic of an FL system. The main difference from previous implementations is that it features a semi-synchronous algorithm, which, instead of aggregating the global model each time a client sends an update, stores some client updates in a buffer before aggregating them. This allows the use of privacy-enhancing algorithms. Note that the number of client updates stored in the buffer each time is not equal to the number of clients participating.

In [241] on top of the straggler issues another key challenge of FL systems is addressed, that of communication cost. Repeatedly sending the large global model to clients may overload those with limited communication bandwidth. To this end, much research has focused on compressing the model to reduce the size of the data that is exchanged [245] [21]. This work, Quantized Asynchronous FL (QUAFL), is an extension of the classical FEDAVG algorithm, which includes asynchronous aggregation and compression mechanisms.

In [246] (PAPAYA) adopts the FEDBUFF [240] asynchronous FL system and extends it to support four aspects of standard synchronous FL. Specifically, they propose mechanisms for client selection, secure aggregation, client replacement, and fast aggregation, all in the context of asynchronous FL.

It is evident that the benefits of FL become even more apparent in the domains of IoT and the Industry. FL ensures privacy by design by keeping data on the devices during training, which is also beneficial in terms of communication costs. Lastly, learning quality is enhanced by leveraging the vast resources distributed in industrial networks, resulting in better AI models.

The extension of standard synchronous FL to asynchronous has addressed the issue of device heterogeneity and the existence of stragglers, allowing non-blocking

communication and the ability to adapt to varying device availability and computation times. Recent studies [27] in AFL have offered improvements in scalability, privacy, and communication cost, but have also revealed critical challenges such as device heterogeneity, data heterogeneity, privacy, and security across diverse devices. The work in [239] proposes an asynchronous method that considers the time efficiency of the system. TEA-FED allows devices to request participation when they are idle.

In [243], the authors present an adaptive and asynchronous method called FEDAAM. The FEDAAM scheme proposes an adaptive weight allocation algorithm to intelligently manage the assignment of weights for each local update, utilizing historical update directions to assist in global model updates. The method utilizes historical global updates to guide the aggregation of the global model, combined with an adaptive weighting mechanism. The method requires fewer communication rounds to achieve the target accuracy. Specifically, it requires 1.12 times fewer rounds compared to FEDAVG, $1.7\times$ fewer compared to FEDASYNC, and $1.3\times$ fewer compared to FEDAA on the CIFAR dataset. It should be noted, however, that the results provided do not consider data heterogeneity, and the performance is likely to differ in real-world scenarios.

In [247], the authors propose an asynchronous method where each client's update is aggregated based on the client's contribution. The authors employ a systematic method to measure the contribution of each client's local update. This measurement considers two main factors, staleness and statistical heterogeneity. Staleness is the difference between the time the local update was generated and the time it was received by the server. Updates from faster clients are given more weight compared to those from slower clients, as they are more relevant to the global model. Statistical heterogeneity is based on the loss of the global model on the clients' data, promoting updates from clients with higher loss. The method achieves approximately 3.0% higher accuracy compared to FEDBUFF, though certain limitations must be acknowledged. The measurement of statistical heterogeneity can be significantly hindered in the presence of extreme heterogeneity among clients, and in many cases, higher loss may also be related to low-quality data. In [244], the authors propose Generalized ASYNC SGD, an asynchronous aggregation scheme paired with a non-uniform client selection method. This selection method is based on clients' computational capabilities and current workloads, allowing the server to prioritize faster devices or those that are ready to contribute updates sooner. By strategically selecting the clients, the method aims to reduce overall delays in receiving updates. Empirical results demonstrate that the method improves accuracy on CIFAR-10 by 10%

compared to ASYNC SGD and by 20% compared to FEDBUFF. However, it should be noted that incorrect speed estimates might result in suboptimal performance.

Other approaches

In [248] the authors present a hierarchical synchronous method with client clustering. The method is based on three key features, clients are clustered based on their computational capabilities, devices participate with other nodes in the cluster in a ring topology to update the model and finally after a specific interval the global model is aggregated from all clusters. Clustering this way improves stability of the training procedure by mitigating issues that arise from differences in performance and reducing the impact of stragglers. Test show that the method is able to convergence even on complex tasks with non-IID data and very few participating clients per round (10%), with SCAFFOLD and TFEDAVG being the only baselines that can convergence but requiring many more rounds. Specifically, in the CIFAR-100 dataset, the FEDHISYN method converges in 44 rounds, SCAFFOLD in 254 rounds, and TFEDAVG in 127 rounds, demonstrating that the proposed method is significantly more efficient than the others. Other results highlight the importance of selecting the appropriate number of clusters, which poses a limitation in the current work. The method could benefit from methods with adaptive clustering. Additional limitations include concerns regarding the scalability of the framework in extremely large-scale scenarios, where the dynamics of device participation and resource availability vary significantly and could impact the clustering algorithm. Lastly, clustering can significantly impact scalability in the presence of large volumes of clients. A notable approach that builds upon FEDPROX [137] is presented in [249], called FEDLGA. The FEDPROX method adds a proximal term to the local training of clients, which limits the impact of non-IID data. The authors argue that this adds extra computational cost to the clients and propose moving the proximal term to the server during aggregation. In addition, the authors propose an alternated Hessian estimation to approximate the optimal gradients based on the local updates. Additionally, the method allows clients to train for fewer epochs based on their capabilities. Empirical results demonstrate that the method exhibits a higher convergence rate, achieving target accuracy in fewer rounds and in less wall-clock time. Specifically, it improves accuracy by 0.4% and requires $1.1\times$ fewer rounds against the best-performing baseline, FEDDYN. In [250], DAP-FL, the authors use adaptive hyperparameter tuning and secure aggregation. The method allows clients with varying computation capabilities to participate efficiently in the training

TABLE 14. Other approaches

Method	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
FEDHISYN [248]	Rounds to Accuracy	-2.89× (TFEDAVG)	CIFAR-100	FEDAVG FEDPROX FEDAAT SCAFFOLD TAFEDAVG TFEDAVG
FEDLGA [249]	Accuracy Rounds	+0.4% (FEDDYN) 1.1× (FEDDYN)	CIFAR-10	FEDAVG, FEDPROX, FEDNOVA, SCAFFOLD, FEDDYN, FEDCM, MIMELITE, FEDSAM
DAP-FL [250]	Accuracy	2.65% (DQN)	FashionMNIST	DQN, DDPG

procedure. The authors model the training of the local model on the clients as a constrained Markov Decision Process and employ the Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) algorithm to learn the optimal hyperparameters. The method outperforms other DDPG based FL and DQN method in terms of accuracy by at least 2.65% (DQN). The method, by enabling adaptive hyperparameters in each client, allows them to participate regardless of their computational capabilities, in contrast to client selection methods that aim to exclude them. Experimental results also demonstrate that DAP-FL is more effective compared to other reinforcement learning approaches such as DQN. Specifically DAP-FL achieves 6.03% higher accuracy than DDPG-based FL and 7.85% higher than DQN. In light of these results, it is essential to consider the added algorithmic complexity and the increased computational cost on the clients from training the DDPG model, which might not be feasible for devices with highly restricted resources. Lastly, the increased computational cost also reduces the method's scalability potential. In FLUID [251], the authors leverage the effect of invariant parameters to mitigate stragglers. Invariant parameters are those that do not change significantly as training progresses. The method proposes adaptively selecting a sub-model by excluding invariant parameters, reducing the computational cost of training, and allowing devices with lower computational resources to participate efficiently. The method achieves higher accuracy compared to other parameter dropout methods but is not compared with other asynchronous methods. However, the method is fairly simple and could be used in combination with other methods. A current limitation of the approach is that it relies on predefined sub-model sizes based on the performance of stragglers, which limits the flexibility of the system.

D. Communication Efficiency

FL relies on the communication between clients and a server or among clients in the DFL setting. The

communication involves downloading the global model to the clients and uploading the local updates to the server. Communication efficiency is an crucial aspect of FL systems due to its significant impact on the overall performance of the system. Aspects that affect performance include the following:

- **Limited bandwidth.** Cross-device implementations of FL involve the participation of smartphones and IoT devices over wireless networks with bandwidth constraints. Training models and in such conditions require efficient communication.
- **Latency.** Slow and inefficient communication hinders the performance and might even render the system useless. Applications should be designed to exchange as little data as possible to alleviate possible latency issues.
- **Resource constraints.** Participating devices especially in cross-device settings are often battery-powered and have limited resources. Heavy data transmissions affect battery life and could quickly deplete available resources, preventing the device from participating in more training rounds.
- **Cost** Cloud-based solutions often base the pricing on the data transmission, and inefficient systems could significantly increase the cost of the application.

The comprehensive survey in [252] examines several critical aspects of communication in FL and presents various methods and strategies to improve communication efficiency in FL, including model compression techniques, adaptive client participation, and efficient aggregation methods. At a high level, communication efficiency can be achieved in two ways. The first is to reduce the communication rounds required to achieve the desired model performance, which decreases the overall communication cost of the system. The second is by reducing the amount of information exchanged between clients and the server or among clients in DFL. Reducing communication rounds is achieved through improved optimization algorithms. Several approaches aim not only

to achieve better results in terms of accuracy but are also designed with constraints on the communication budget. Reducing the size of the data exchanged between clients and the server can be achieved in multiple ways and can be further categorized. Client selection has been proposed to reduce overall communication bandwidth; however, while it benefits the system in terms of reducing bandwidth, it does not necessarily help participating clients save resources. Research has focused on compression methods to reduce the data exchanged. Compression is categorized into three categories: quantization, sparsification, and knowledge distillation.

1) Quantization

Quantization is a widely used method across various domains, employed to map a set of values to a smaller set. In the context of deep learning and machine learning, it is used to compress models by approximating the trainable parameters of a neural network and representing them using fewer bits. This method reduces the size of the model, thereby reducing the required bandwidth for exchanging model parameters between clients and the server. The simplest form of quantization can be considered the conversion of 32-bit floats to 16-bit floats or 8-bit integers. Methods like this are used in neural networks not only to reduce size but also to reduce the computation required, as calculations on integers require less processing than floats. In [253] the quantization scheme is defined as:

$$r = S(q - Z)$$

where r denotes a real value, q the quantized value and the constants S , scale and arbitrary positive real number and Z , zero-point and is the quantized value that corresponds to the real value 0.

The quantization methods can be categorized in uniform and non-uniform. Uniform quantization span the bins across the parameter space evenly. And between fixed and adaptive methods, where in the case of fixed the level of quantization is fixed while in adaptive it is possible to change every round.

As mentioned above, quantization in the context of FL has focused in model compression to improve communication efficiency. In [245], a number of lossy compression techniques are introduced. Among them, a probabilistic quantization technique is presented that can be used to represent a value on a predefined number of bits. The process of this quantization can be described using the following formula:

$$q = \begin{cases} r_{\min} & \text{with probability } (r_{\max} - r)/(r_{\max} - r_{\min}) \\ r_{\max} & \text{with probability } (r - r_{\min})/(r_{\max} - r_{\min}) \end{cases}$$

The above formula quantizes the values to one bit, but it can be generalized to multiple, b , bit quantization by dividing the $[r_{\min}, r_{\max}]$ into 2^b intervals. Each value

will be quantized using the above formula and the boundaries of the interval it belongs to. The rank of quantization offers a parameter to balance the tradeoff between compression and performance. The method is very simple with great benefits in communication cost, though it is a uniform quantization method that treats all the parameters the same way, which might not be optimal, and it was used only for uplink, client-to-server communication. The work presented in [270] extended the lossy compression techniques for downlink (server-to-client) communication.

The methods proposed in [254] consider quantization in the decentralized setting and argue that quantization for CFL does not directly apply to DFL. Instead of compressing the local model update, they propose to extrapolate a value from the resulted local update and the parameters of the previous node, ECD-PSGD. The method ensures diminishing errors but requires storing the model received from a neighbor.

In [271], the SecAgg method is presented with auto-tuned quantization, where the server calculates the bin size in each round. In the work presented in [257], Hyper-Sphere Quantization (HSQ), considers a global cookbook that is distributed to the clients and used to quantize local updates. The clients send only the index of the chosen code word from the cookbook.

In FEDPAQ [258], the proposed method employs client selection and combines it with the QSGD [272] quantization method to further reduce communication cost. In the work [273], quantization is employed for downlink communication using QSGD as the quantization method.

In FEDCOM [260], the proposed method improves FEDPAQ by introducing a linear combination of the global model with the average of the local updates, instead of simply averaging. Even though FEDCOM performance gains do not stand in the heterogeneous setting. FEDCOM is further extended to FEDCOMGATE, using gradient tracking techniques to reduce the variance of the local updates and improve the performance of the algorithm in the presence of heterogeneous clients.

In [259], [274] a subtractive dithered lattice quantization is proposed to address the error introduced by quantization in uplink communication. The lattice quantizer employed maps the value to their nearest lattice point. Experiments demonstrated a reduction in the average squared error compared to QSGD and uniform quantizers.

In the work presented in [262], SignSGD compressed the local updates using only 1-bit encoding the sign of the updates. The work in [263], after sparsification, further compresses the gradients by applying binary quantization. The work presented in [264] improved SignSGD in the heterogeneous setting by introducing stochasticity. The method first quantizes the values at

TABLE 15. Quantization methods

Method	Uplink/Downlink	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
PROBABILISTIC QUANTIZATION [245]	Uplink	Data size exchanged in total (MB)	5000MB (1-bit Prob. Quantization) vs 30000MB (-83%)	CIFAR	2-bit Prob. Quantization, 4-bit Prob. Quantization, 8-bit Prob. Quantization
ECD-PSGD [254]	Both	Speedup in diverse network conditions	$\approx \times 3, 3$ ECD-PSGD 8-bit (worst case), $\approx \times 9$ ECD-PSGD 8-bit (best case)	CIFAR-10	Allreduce
CE-FEDAVG, ExpQ [255]	Uplink	Number of rounds, Data size exchanged in total	$\times 6$ less rounds, $\times 3x$ less data	MNIST, CIFAR10	FEDAVG
COSSGD [256]	Both	Compression rate	$\times 1000$	CIFAR-10, BraTS2019	No compression, linear, kmeans
HSQ [257]	Uplink	Compression rate	$\times 1000$ vs SGD	CIFAR10, Fashion-mnist	SGD, SignSGD, TernGrad, QSGD
FEDPAQ [258]	Uplink	N/A	N/A	N/A	No compression, QSGD
UVEQFED [259]	Uplink	Mean squared error at fixed quantization rate	$\approx 1\%$ reduced error vs QSGD	MNIST, CIFAR-10	FEDAVG, QSGD
FEDCOM, FEDCOMGATE [260]	Uplink	Data size exchanged per round (MB)	$\approx 2MB$ vs $\approx 14, 5MB$ SCAFFOLD vs $\approx 7MB$ FEDGATE vs $\approx 2MB$ FEDCOMGATE vs $\approx 7MB$ FEDAVG on CIFAR10	MNIST, CIFAR10, Fashion MNIST, EMNIST	SCAFFOLD FEDGATE FEDCOMGATE FEDAVG
ADAQUANTFL [261]	Uplink	Data size exchanged in total (GB)	0.3GB vs 1.8GB 2-bit (-38%)		2-bit, 4-bit, 8-bit, 16-bit
SIGN-SGD [262]	Uplink	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
SPARSE BINARY COMPRESSION [263]	Both	Compression rate	$\times 24935 - \times 37208$ less bits (more than 99%) against baseline	MNIST, CIFAR-10, ImageNet	Gradient dropping, FEDAVG
STOCHASTIC-SIGN SGD [264]	Uplink	Accuracy over communication bits	$\approx 95\%$ vs $\approx 90\%$ FEDAVG (MNIST) $\approx 80\%$ vs $\approx 45\%$ FEDAVG (CIFAR-10)	MNIST, CIFAR-10	SIGNSGD, FEDAVG 5-Local Iterations
FEDHQ [265]	Uplink	Number of rounds to achieve accuracy	61 rounds vs 104 rounds FEDAVG (-41%), on 4bit & 8bit quantization for MNIST	MNIST, CIFAR-10	FEDAVG

TABLE 15. Quantization methods - continued from previous page

Method	Uplink/Downlink	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
Adaptive Quantized Federated Average [266]	Uplink	Compression rate, Data size exchanged per round per client (MB)	4x-16x, 5,6MB vs 44,67MB (-87%) (CIFAR-10)	CIFAR-10, IMDB	FEDAVG n-local iterations
T-FEDAVG [267]	Both	Data size exchanged in total (MB)	4,72MB vs 39,06MB vs 25,16MB (-87%, -80% MLP) 5243MB vs 323936MB vs 20276MB (-83%, -74% CNN) 8077MB vs 18507MB vs 11920MB (-56%, -32% ResNet)	MNIST, CIFAR-10	FEDAVG, CMFL
FEDDQ [268]	Uplink	Data size exchanged in total (MB), Number of rounds to achieve accuracy	0,72GB vs ,07GB (-65.2%), 8 rounds vs 25 rounds (-68%)	MNIST, CIFAR-10	ADAQUANTFL
LM-DFL [269]	Both	Quantization distortion	-28% (QSGD)	MNIST, CIFAR-10	ALQ, QSGD

two levels, 1, -1, with a certain probability and then transmits the signs of the resulting quantized values.

In the work in [267], FTTQ migrates Trainer Ternary Quantization (TTQ) [275] in the federated settings. In traditional ternary quantization the values are expressed using 2-bit usually $-1, 0, +1$ or $-E, 0, +E$ where E is the mean of absolute weight values, in contrast in the proposed method the values are quantized based on two trainable variables $-W_l^p, 0, +W_l^n$ for each layer l . The method demonstrated convergence while simultaneously reducing weight divergence and bias from the quantization.

The ADAQUANTFL method proposed in [261] also utilizes the QSGD for quantization though in this case allows the clients to adapt the level of compression leading to overall exchanging less bit to reach the same convergence. The method proposed in FEDHQ [265] allows for different levels of quantization in each client and assigns a dynamic weight to each local update based on their quantization level. In [266], an algorithm with different quantization levels for each client based on the bandwidth constraints of the device and overall communication threshold is presented.

More recently, the work in [268] presented FEDDQ a compression method with descending quantization. It is based on the notion that after as the model converge the smaller the gradient updates become and thus can

be represented using fewer bits. The method allows for different levels of quantization per clients associated with the training round. The method seems logical and suitable in the context of FL, where clients are not guaranteed to participate in every round. The work in [276] proposes adapting the quantization level based on the importance of the value. The method represents important values with higher precision rather than uniformly quantizing all values to the same bit length.

The work on [255] proposes an exponential quantization method that converts 32-bit floats to 8-bit integers. The method maps negatives values to the range of 0-127 and positive value to range of 128-255. The method presented in [256], presents a non-linear quantization method based on cosine function which instead of encoding the true values encodes the angle between the local update and the standard coordinate. In addition, it further improves the method by integrating probability to address the bias usually introduced in quantization methods.

Recently, the work in [277] argues that gradients after training can be efficiently modeled using the GenNorm distribution, which could be utilized by compression algorithms.

In [278], the authors propose an adaptive quantization method. This method considers the distribution of gradi-

ents to adapt the quantization level, aiming to minimize any excess variance introduced by quantization.

In [279], DADAQUANT, a time-adaptive quantization algorithm, is presented. In each round, the level of quantization is adjusted, with initial rounds having lower quantization levels to help the convergence of the model and higher levels in later rounds when the model has converged. The method utilizes loss to adjust the level in each round, balancing the need for communication cost reduction and accuracy. Results demonstrate that the method outperforms baselines in several datasets, reducing client-to-server communication by $1.1\times$ to $2.2\times$ more than the best baseline, QSGD. Similarly to DADAQUANT, the authors in [280], FEDDQ, also propose an adaptive quantization level method. However, in this case, instead of ascending the quantization level or deriving it from the loss of the model, the level is based on the range of the clients' updates. The range of the clients' updates is the difference between the maximum and the minimum, and lower ranges indicate that the model has converged. The method reduces the size of data exchanged by 65.2% and the communication rounds by 57% compared to DADAQUANT. In [281], the authors argue that biased compression mechanisms hinder the convergence of the global model and propose the Fed-EF method, which employs error feedback (EF) to correct the bias introduced by compression. In each round the client records the compression error, which is the difference between the true gradient and the compressed gradient and is used the next round to correct the bias. The method aims to correct compression bias and is intended to be used alongside a compression mechanism. However, correcting the bias in the next round introduces a delay, and in cases where clients do not participate frequently, the bias may not be corrected in time. In [269], Lloyd-Max DFL (LM-DFL), the authors propose a non-uniform quantization of model parameters that minimizes quantization distortion through adaptive adjustment of quantization levels. The Lloyd-Max algorithm employed for quantization models the distortion from quantization as the mean squared error between the original values and their quantized counterparts. The method is evaluated against ALQ and QSGD quantizers and exhibits reduced quantization distortion against them, specifically 88% against ALQ and 28% against QSGD. In [282], QHFL, the authors perform a joint analysis of quantization and transmission outages under wireless imperfect channel state information in hierarchical FL systems. The modeling considers the probability of transmission outages of quantized gradients, taking into account training and communication latency. The joint impact analysis provides useful insight and emphasizes the positive correlation between quantization accuracy and transmission outages. The findings of this work can play a crucial role in optimizing quantization

algorithms and designing communication protocols and resource allocation methods.

In Table 15 the methods that employ quantization are reported alongside the improvements achieved and the baselines used in the experiments conducted by the authors.

2) Sparsification

Sparsification is the process of creating a subset of values from a given set. The most commonly employed methods are Top-k that selects the k highest values to form the subset and rand-k, which selects randomly k values.

FIGURE 19. a) Illustration of rand-k method with $k=3$ b) Illustration of top-k method with $k=3$

One of the lossy compression methods introduced in [245] considered gradient subsampling where using a random mask the clients sent a random subsampling of the local update. The mask can be sent to the server as a seed and recovered in the server and get the corresponding indices. Randomness on the subsampling technique provides an unbiased estimator after the aggregation.

In Table 16 the methods that employ sparsification are reported alongside the improvement achieved and the baselines used in the experiments conducted by the authors.

In SPARSE BINARY COMPRESSION (SBC) [263], the gradients are compressed using a top-k sparsification method exchanging only the fraction of the updates with the highest magnitude. Similarly, the method used in the Deep Gradient Compression algorithm [283], employs a top-k selection to send only the gradients with the largest magnitude. In contrast to the previous approach the remaining gradients accumulate in each communication round until they reach the required threshold and are sent to the server.

Thus, all the gradients will be transmitted eventually. It is based on the insight that accumulating remaining gradients over time equals to increasing the batch size. However the accumulated gradients led to harming the convergence which was addressed by utilizing momentum correction and gradient clipping. The work in GENERAL GRADIENT SPARSIFICATION (GGS) [286] considers the accuracy drop incurred by the remaining accumulated gradients. The method employs gradient correction to improve the gradients exchanged. In addition, batch normalization is utilized to address the impact of delayed gradients. In FETCHSGD, as pre-

TABLE 16. Sparsification methods

Method	Uplink/Downlink	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
GRADIENT SUBSAMPLING [245]	Uplink	Data size exchanged in total (MB)	10000 (90% sparsification) MB vs 30000MB (0% sparsification) (-66%)	CIFAR	0% sparsification
SPARSE BINARY COMPRESSION [263]	Both	Compression rate	$\times 24935 - \times 37208$ less bits (more than 99%) against baseline	MNIST, CIFAR-10, ImageNet	Gradient dropping, FEDAVG
DEEP GRADIENT COMPRESSION [283]	Uplink	Compression Rate	$\times 277 - \times 608$ less gradients	CIFAR-10, ImageNet, Treebank, AN4, Librispeech	FL, TernGrad, Gradient Dropping
SPARSE TERNARY COMPRESSION [284]	Both	Data size exchanged per round (number of bits)	1302,73 MB vs 73392 MB (98% less bits), 479,27 MB vs 10382 MB (95% less bits)	CIFAR, KWS, Fashion-MNIST, MNIST	FL, signSGD, FEDAVG
FETCHSGD [285]	Both	Compression Rate	$\times 3.9$	CIFAR, FEMNIST	FL, FEDAVG, Top-k
GENERAL GRADIENT SPARSIFICATION [286]	Downlink	Compression Rate	$\times 326, \times 274, \times 307, \times 303, \times 298, \times 318, \times 186, \times 183$	MNIST, CIFAR-10, ImageNet	TernGrad
FABTOP-K [287]	Both	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
HARD-THRESHOLD SPARSIFIER [288]	Downlink	Compression rate	$\times 7.7$	CIFAR-10	ACCORDION, $top - 1\%$, $top - 0.1\%$
DC2 [289]	Both	Training speed-up	$\approx \times 2.2$ at ratio 0.1, $\approx \times 1.3$ at ratio 0.001	CIFAR-10, ImageNet, PTB	Uncompressed, Rand-k, Top-k
GTOP-K [290]	Both	N/A	N/A	N/A	Cifar-10, ImageNet, PTB
TIME CORRELATED SPARSIFICATION [291]	Both	Communication load	$\times 100$ vs top-k, $\times 2000$ vs centralized	CIFAR-10	Centralized training, top-k
DYNAMIC SPARSIFICATION [292]	Uplink	Accuracy over iteration	N/A	MNIST, CIFAR-10, Speech commands	Uncompressed, top-k
CHANNEL-AWARE SPARSIFICATION [293]	Both	Accuracy improvement over same sparsity	$\leq 7.91\%$	FASHION-MNIST	Equal Time, Equal Sparsity
Energy-Efficient and Adaptive [294]	Both	Data size exchanged per round (MB)	93.14%, 84.83%, 60% (reduction)	MNIST	FL-WS, FL-CTS, FL-TBS
PRUNEFL [295]	Time to accuracy Flops to accuracy	Seconds TFlops	-33% (SynFlow) -45% (SynFlow)	FEMNIST FEMNIST	SynFlow, SNIP

sented in [285], gradients are compressed using Count-Sketch [296] which does not rely on storing state in the clients, such as locally storing the remaining gradients, and making it suitable in the FL settings with infrequent client participation.

In [284] top-k sparsification is argued to be the most efficient in the presence of heterogeneous clients and it is extended to include downlink communication. To achieve a sparsified model in the parameter server which behaves similar to top-k methods, clients should derive their sparsification masks for uplink using the Hadamard product between their mask and the target mask for the downlink compression. Empirical study has shown that STC achieves convergence even in the presence of extremely heterogeneous distributions and manages to greatly out-perform the standard FEDAVG and sinSGD. In GTOPIK [290] a method is proposed that further sparsifies the collected client updates and results in a sparsified global model.

In FABTOP-K [287], an adaptive top-k sparsification is presented that formulates a cost function based on model accuracy, which is optimized to derive the optimal k in each round. The work presented in [288] concerns an optimal sparsifier that will ensure to retain a maximum communication budget throughout the whole training. Towards this end, error-feedback mechanism is utilized to calculate the locally accumulated error and is used to correct the gradient in each step. In addition, proposed a hard-threshold method that adapts the top-k method in each iteration to prevent error accumulation.

In [289], an adaptive compression framework is presented which is evaluated using top-k and rand-k sparsification methods. In this framework, compression is controlled based on network delays to balance between the training speed and accuracy. It consists of two main components a delay monitor and the compression control. The delay monitor is responsible for measuring the delay of the clients and compression control is responsible for adjusting the compression level according to the delay and the selected control strategy.

The work presented in [291] aims to further improve top-k sparsification methods by reducing the size required for the indices of non-zero values. The proposed method calculates a global mask on the parameters server by taking into consideration the mask of previous rounds. The clients sparsify based on the global mask which results in the two advantages of the method, the clients don't need to send the non-zero indices and due to the correlation of masks across clients a higher downlink sparsification is achieved.

The work in [297] employs a layer-wise adaptive sparsification method. Each client selects a subset of the most significant values from each layer. The number of values selected per layer depends on a communication-to-computation ratio. The proposed methods combine the

benefits of pipelining with sparsification resulting in a per-layer parallelization of sparsification and communication processes.

Recently, the work presented in [292] takes into consideration the similarity deeper layers among clients and the communication capacity of the client. The method employs two sparsification methods to address them. The Layer-wise Similarity Sparsification (LSS) sparsifies the values based on the probability of the corresponding layer to be similar to the global model which results in more values on the higher layers being selected.

The top-k sparsification method utilized on in the previous method calculates the level of k based on the available communication resources on the device. In the method presented in [293], the client sends the L_1 norm of their computed gradient to the server and the server computes the sparsity budget for the client. The calculation of the budget considers the norm as well as the transmission rate, which is used as the channel condition. Meanwhile, in [294], the method adapts the sparsification level based on the energy cost. The aim is to find a balance on the trade-off between the accuracy of the transmitted value and the energy required for transmission.

In [295], PruneFL, the author present an adaptive pruning method that reduces the model parameters. The method tracks the importance of the model parameters from the magnitude of their updates after each training. The parameters with the smallest magnitudes are considered insignificant and thus pruned. Empirical results demonstrate that the method significantly reduces time and flops to reach target accuracy. Specifically it takes 15,009 seconds and 6.8 TFLOPs to target accuracy, while the second fastest method, SynFlow requires 22,327 seconds and 12.3 TFLOPs. The method requires a high-quality initial model to effectively complete the first pruning stage and yield optimal results. The authors in [298], FedDD, present differential parameter dropout where clients drop a number of parameters based on a dropout rate assigned to them considering computational capabilities, data quality, and communication resources. Parameters are pruned based on an importance index derived from the norm of the gradient changes. Empirical results demonstrate that the method is particularly effective, especially in the case of highly non-IID data. Specifically it achieves 26.2% higher accuracy than the second best method OORT for CIFAR-10 dataset. In light of these results it is essential to consider that as the number of clients increases, the complexity of managing dropout rates and parameter selection may grow, potentially, leading to scalability issues. In [299], SAFARI, the authors pair sparsification with a compensation method for lost client updates. The compensation method tracks the similarity among clients and when a selected client does not upload an update the method

uses those of similar ones. In [300], Sparsified SAGA with Adaptive Filtration, the authors employ an adaptive sparsification method that aims to retain the most informative parameters. The method extends the SAGA algorithm by adding a filtering of the non-informative parameters after the sparsification. Results demonstrate that it maintains accuracy similar to plain SAGA, but with less communication overhead. However, the added filtering introduces additional computational overhead, and it should be considered, whether the achieved benefit in communication is cost-effective. In [301] the authors propose adaptive sparsification methods that adjust the level of sparsification based on the current state of the model and the performance requirements. In addition, the authors propose coupling the level of sparsification with the number of clients participating and allowing a higher level of sparsification as they increase.

The authors in [302], present One-Bit Analog Aggregation (SOBAA). The method employs layer-wise quantization and sparsification paired with an error-feedback mechanism that aims to correct errors from previous iterations.

In [303] a lossless sparsification method is proposed. Lossless sparsification is achieved utilizing a mapping function that transforms the gradients into an alternative space where the majority of its elements become near-zero without losing any critical information. The method was evaluated against several baselines, including FEDAVG, FedPara, FEDDQ, Top-k, and kSB and demonstrated that the combination of the mapping function with sparsification consistently improves accuracy and communication efficiency. However, the mapping function does introduce a computational overhead which should be considered in light of the computational capabilities of client devices.

3) Knowledge Distillation

In Table 17 the methods that employ knowledge-distillation methods are reported alongside the improvement achieved and the baselines used in the experiments conducted by the authors.

Knowledge distillation as mentioned above, inspired by the teacher-student paradigm trains a small model to mimic the behavior of a larger and more complex model referred to as the teacher. Knowledge from the teacher model is distilled into the student using the teacher's output as the target for the student. Knowledge distillation-based methods have been largely integrated into FL due to the benefits they can offer in terms of handling statistical and system heterogeneity.

The large and complex teacher model has a bigger capacity to address a problem and can be trained in sufficient generalization while the student model is smaller and since it resides only on the client devices it can also

also be tailored to the needs of each device addressing statistical and system heterogeneity. The benefit for the communication part of FL derives from the fact that in KD training on the student model requires the output of the teacher and full model parameters.

Federated Distillation (FD) is proposed in [304], where the clients instead of local updates upload the average of their logit vectors, and aggregation on the server is done using these logits. Distillation takes place on the clients using the global average logit vectors. The work demonstrates great improvement in communication efficiency by reducing communication costs by 26 times.

In FEDMD [200] the exchange of model parameters is substituted by the predictions of the clients on a sub-sample of the public dataset. It is unclear the exact communication benefit in contrast to the performance gain but the size of the sampled global data used is pre-defined and the communication size is limited to the size of the global dataset multiplied to the number of logits for each experiment regardless of the complexity and number of parameters on the local model on the device. In the work presented in [310]

On PFEDSD [206] which is described in the context of personalized FL uses client's predicted classes distribution for uplink data, in place of the local updates, and pseudolabels from the server for downlink data which achieves reducing the communication cost. The experiments demonstrate that they achieve better results in accuracy, while on the PFEDSD-hot variation 45% less parameters are exchanged.

In FEDGEN presented in [203], the global dataset is replaced by a generator and again only the prediction layer of the local model is exchanged. Results do not quantify the benefit of the size of the data exchanged, though demonstrate faster convergence reducing the communication rounds required to reach high accuracy compared to several baselines. Considering as target accuracy accuracy achieved by the best-performing baseline the proposed method is able to achieve it in around 60% less rounds in the best-case scenario and in the same number of rounds in the worst-case.

The work on [305], DS-FL, presents a new aggregation method for model outputs collected from clients, ERA, that aims to reduce entropy. Tests on the heterogenous setting demonstrate communication cost reduction of up to 99 percent while maintaining accuracy.

The work in CFD [308] performs an evaluation of the federated distillation algorithms in the context of communication efficiency and proposes a quantization method for compression, and delta coding, of the labels that are exchanged and further reduces the cost.

FD Meta-Algorithm [307] employs a different approach where only the uplink communication is benefited. In this method, the clients again upload the logits to the server but now the server averages the logits and distills their

TABLE 17. Knowledge Distillation approaches for compression

Method	Uplink/Downlink	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
FD [304]	Both	Data size exchanged per round (Megabits)	0.1024 vs 1228.44 (-99% bits exchanged)	MNIST	FEDAVG
FEDMD [200]	Both	N/A	N/A	MNIST/FEMNIST & CIFAR	FEDAVG
PFEDSD [206]	Both	Data size exchanged per round (number of parameters)	55% reduction	MNIST, FMNIST, CIFAR	FEDMD, DS-FL, MHAT
FEDGEN [203]	Both	Rounds to reach target accuracy	60% reduction	CELEBA, MNIST, EMNIST	FEDAVG, FEDPROX, Ensemble, FEDDISTill, FedFusion
DS-FL [305]	Both	Data size exchanged per round	up to 90% reduction	MNIST, Fashion-MNIST	FEDAVG, FD
FedAUX [306]	Downlink	Communication cost	$ \theta^{R_i} * T$ vs $ \theta * T$		FEDAVG, FEDDF, FEDBE
FD Meta-Algorithm [307]	Uplink	Communication cost	$ D_{Digit} * N_c$	CIFAR	FEDAVG, FDA, DSFL, CEFD, FEDDF
CFD [308]	Both	Data size exchanged per round (MB)	0.71 MB vs 1342.32 MB (-99%), 64 MB (-98%)	MNIST / EMNIST, CIFAR-10 / STL-10	FA, FD
FedKD [309]	Both	Data size exchanged per round (GB)	0.07 GB vs 0.12 GB (-5%) Best baseline vs 1.37 GB (-94%) Worst baseline	MIND, SMM4H	UniLM (Fed), DistilBERT, BERT-PKD, TinyBERT, UniLM, FETCHSGD, FEDDROPout
FEDFTG [151]	Both	Rounds to reach target accuracy	188.67 vs 183.67 (0,02% additional rounds to the best performing) vs 425.33 (-55% less rounds to worst performing)	CIFAR	FEDAVG, FEDPROX, FEDDYN, and SCAFFOLD

knowledge to the global model that in turn is shared with the clients as in vanilla FL. Again the improvement on the uplink communication is limited by the length of the sampled sub-set from the global model.

In FedKD [309] mutual knowledge distillation is applied improving both teacher and student models. The method involves training both teacher and student on the client devices but only the student, the smaller model, is trained collaboratively while mutual knowledge distillation between the two models allows the teacher model to also benefit from knowledge of the data of the device. In addition, to further reduce the commu-

nication cost the student model gradients exchanged are compressed using the matrix factorization technique. The experiments demonstrated a 5% communication cost reduction even against the most efficient baseline, TinyBert, and 94% reduction against the least efficient baseline, UniLM(Fed).

In the work presented in [151], FEDFTG, as already mentioned in previous sections, employs a data-free distillation method for optimizing the global model on the server after aggregation. The algorithms presented demonstrate benefits not only in addressing statistical heterogeneity, but also in achieving faster convergence

in fewer communication rounds against all the baseline methods except one.

4) Other methods

Sub models

In the work presented in [270] Federated Dropout is proposed where clients learn only a small sub-model which can be applied to the large global model, inspired by [311]. An extension to this approach can be seen in [312] and FEDDROP, though, in this work, the size of the sub-models trained on clients is not fixed and equal for all the devices. Instead, the server generates a sub-model based on the communication rate and computation speed of each client.

Low rank decomposition

One of the methods proposed in [245] is based on low rank approximation. The method considers the decomposition of the local update in two lower rank matrices $U_t^i = A_t^i B_t^i$, where $U_t^i \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, $A_t^i \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times k}$ and $B_t^i \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times n}$. In each round the A_t^i matrix is randomly generated and fixed and the B_t^i is optimized.

During uplink communication A_t^i is transmitted using the random seed used for generating it and only B_t^i matrix is required to be transmitted. The server is able to reconstruct the A_t^i matrix using the seed and the local update U_t^i using the dot product of the two matrices.

$$\begin{array}{|c|} \hline U \\ \hline (m \times n) \\ \hline \end{array} \approx \begin{array}{|c|} \hline A \\ \hline (m \times k) \\ \hline \end{array} \times \begin{array}{|c|} \hline B \\ \hline (k \times n) \\ \hline \end{array}$$

FIGURE 20. Low-rank decomposition

The method proposed in [313], FedPara, overcomes the low-rank constraint imposed in the previous method introducing low-rank Hadamard product reparameterization. Thus the local update decomposition is expressed as $U_t^i = A1_t^i B1_t^i \circ A2_t^i B2_t^i$

E. Security and Privacy

The adoption of FL by fields with particular sensitivity in data privacy and security requires robust data protection and security mechanisms. To consider a FL system safe it should protect not only against adversarial clients but should also ensure that the data will remain private even against the central server.

In the context of cybersecurity, there are several threat models associated with FL. Different threats occur in the various phases of FL by different adversaries. Following the categorization presented in [314], FL poses security risks in three different phases where each of them has

different vulnerabilities and thus faces different security and privacy threats.

- *Data and behavior auditing phase.* In this phase there are two possible threats. First, the client data might be of low quality with inaccuracies in labels and features and secondly, the client itself might be malicious or might have been compromised by adversaries.
- *Training phase.* In this phase the system utilizes the involved clients' data and computational capabilities to train collaboratively the shared model. This gives the opportunity to adversaries that have compromised clients to manipulate the data, the model gradients, and the parameters to attack the global model. Malicious actions in this phase can also come from the central server which might use the updates collected by the clients to deduce sensitive information about their training data. Lastly, due to the exchange of data between the server and the clients, this phase is prone to eavesdropping attacks.
- *Prediction phase.* In the predicting phase the trained model is shared and thus makes this phase prone to evasion and privacy inference attacks. Evasion aims to corrupt the model to produce false predictions while inference attacks aim to deduce information and reconstruct the data used for training.

FIGURE 21. The multi-phases framework of FL including data and behavior auditing, model training and model predicting from [314]

1) Threats and attacks

- **Poor data quality and malicious behavior (Auditing phase):** Involved clients/nodes are susceptible to external adversaries that aim to exploit possible vulnerabilities to gain access or corrupt the data and the client's system. In addition, not all data are equal, meaning that some of the data

collected by the clients might be of low quality or even poisoned by an adversary.

- **Poisoning attacks (Auditing phase, Training phase):** Poisoning attacks pose a critical security concern for a FL system and aim to reduce the accuracy of the model, untargeted attacks, or to inject a backdoor, targeted attacks. Adversaries aim to influence client's training and result in a shared model that produces false predictions. Poisoning is achieved either by the introduction of malicious training samples, tampering of existing samples, modifying model parameters, or by sending specific gradient updates to the central server that help achieve the adversarial goal. In addition, targeted and untargeted attacks can be further divided based on data poisoning and model poisoning. Data poisoning occurs during the data collection, examples of such attacks include adding noise or flipping the labels of the data. Model poisoning on the other hand aims to tamper with model updates and leads the server to aggregate a corrupt shared model. Since this attack requires access to model updates it is only feasible during the training phase of the algorithm.

The work in [315] is among the first that demonstrated a backdoor attack in FL by injecting patterns to the model updates and utilizing label flipping to lead the global model to misclassify certain labels. The authors in [316] extended the backdoor attack by leveraging the decentralized nature of FL and the involvement of multiple clients. In this approach the malicious clients included smaller patterns in their data which formed a bigger backdoor in the global model. Smaller patterns allowed them to be stealthier and avoid defense mechanisms making the attack more robust and more effective. To further enhance poisoning attacks and address defense mechanism the authors of [317] proposed adjusting the l_2 norm of the malicious updates. Similarly to [316], the work in [318] also aims to leverage collaboration among malicious nodes to perform an attack. The method presents a perturbation estimation scheme applied on top of backdoor training with two goals: bypassing robust aggregation mechanisms and limiting the impact of the perturbations on the effectiveness of the attack. To this end, the scheme aims to maintain the l_2 norm of the backdoored updates at a similar level to benign updates and ensure that the sum of all perturbations cancels out during aggregation. The method proposed in [319], CERP, employs several evasion techniques based on the insights from state-of-the-art defenses. The method proposed fine-tuning the backdoor trigger to reduce bias introduced by malicious updates. In addition, the distance between poisoned models

and benign models is reduced to evade Byzantine-robust aggregation methods. Finally, it employs collaboration among malicious clients and minimizes the similarity among their malicious updates to evade similarity-based defenses. Empirical results demonstrate that CERP is highly effective on several state-of-the-art defense methods in contrast to other distributed attack methods such as Sybil, DBA and LIE which fail to evade all the defenses. The method accounts for the distributed attack scenario and communication among the adversaries is required. However, the number of the adversaries used in each round does not exceed 20% of the total selected clients. Another approach for avoiding the defense methods was proposed in [320] that does not rely on malicious data or scaling of backdoored updates. In this work the authors present an attack method, F3BA, that selects the least important model parameters and injects a trigger through flipping their signs aiming to maximize the activation of the next layer when the trigger is present. Lastly training is used to bind the trigger with a label. The authors use a convolutional neural network to demonstrate the attack, but the method can be extended to any other architecture since the parameter selection step and training are model agnostic and the only part that requires adaptation is the flipping operation of the signs to maximize the next layer's activation function. The advancement of FL defenses, which now detect backdoor models from various perspectives, has led the scientific community towards adaptive attack methods. In [321] 3DFED, the authors present an adaptive attack framework that utilizes three evasion modules to improve stealthiness of backdoor attacks. The first module constrains the backdoor training to find a local minimum close to the benign minimum to evade norm clipping based defense mechanisms. The noise mask module adds noise to hide backdoor features that can easily be detected by the parameters server. Finally, the third module aims to evade dimensionality-reduction-based defense mechanisms. Another novelty of the current work lies in the continuous adaptation of the attacks mechanisms. The authors introduce the indicator mechanism which exploits redundant neural neurons that remain the same during training, to provide feedback about the success of the backdoor model in previous rounds. Insights from the indicator mechanism are used to adapt the hyper parameters of the evasion modules. Empirical results demonstrate that the method successfully evades state-of-the-art defense mechanisms and maintains a high backdoor accuracy, 73.76%, even with only 4 malicious clients. The work presented in [322],

A3FL, also identifies the need for adaptive attack mechanism to overcome defenses mechanisms. The method aims to adapt the trigger based on future dynamics of the global model. Since no information is available about the global model, participating clients and data the method optimizes the backdoor based on the assumption that the global model is trained to unlearn the backdoor. Empirical results demonstrate that the method achieves a high ASR even with only one malicious client. In contrast to traditional approaches, some recent works aim to relax the reliance of attack methodologies on a benign dataset. Recently, the work in [323] (FBA-PI) proposes using a GAN to infer representative samples for each class from the global model and use them to generate adversarial data samples that contain a backdoor trigger and are similar to benign ones. Compared to previous methods, access to actual benign data is not mandatory, while continuous improvement of the GAN enhances the effectiveness of the attack. In [324], the authors also proposed a data-free attack methodology, called DarkFed. The experiments conducted in this study demonstrate that backdoor attacks can be successfully achieved using synthetic datasets or datasets from similar tasks. Furthermore, to evade defense mechanisms, a feature mimicry approach is introduced, ensuring that the malicious updates resemble benign ones in terms of magnitude, distribution and consistency. Other notable backdoor attacks, such as in [325] LR-BA, consider passive attackers in the vertical FL setting. Specifically aims to exploit the latent representation outputs and create a malicious head that miss-classifies labels when provided with a trigger. The work regards passive attacks that occur during the inference phase and require only a small portion of training samples.

- **Privacy inference (Training and prediction phase):** Even though the main feature of FL is that it preserves privacy by not requiring sending data to the central server, studies have shown that the gradients and the shared model can be used to extract sensitive information about participating clients. Eavesdropping attacks fall under privacy inference, where the adversary steals model weights to extract meaningful information. Privacy inference attacks can be further categorized based on the goal of the adversary performing the attack, into: Membership inference attacks, in which the adversary aims to identify if specific samples were used during training of the shared model. Class representative inference attacks, in which the adversary aims to infer prototypical samples that are representative of those used during training. Data properties inference attacks, in which the adversary

aims to infer certain properties that exist in the training data of other participants. Training data inference attacks / Sample reconstruction, where the adversary aims to fully reconstruct the actual data used during training of the shared model. Privacy inference attacks make use of model parameters (or gradients) and/or the output of the model; thus, they can be applied during both the training and prediction phases.

In [326] the authors present an active membership inference attack placing the server as the attacker and exploiting its ability to manipulate the global model parameters. The attacker identifies a neuron specifically activated only by the target class and observes whether clients modify this neuron after training to infer membership of the label in the clients dataset. Results demonstrate the effectiveness of the method in exploiting correlations between features to infer information even under Local Differential Privacy, highlighting the need for improvement in privacy-preserving defenses. The authors' Source Inference Attack (SIA) method [327] employ Bayesian statistics in a non-invasive manner to calculate the probabilities of each client being the source of a sample. Although the proposed method achieves inferring the source of the target samples, its performance is limited by the number of clients participating. Increasing the pool of clients also makes it more difficult for the method to infer the correct source.

- **Evasion (Prediction phase)** Evasion is a non-invasive attack that aims to construct adversarial examples that can break through the system's robustness and lead the model to make false predictions. This type of attack requires only access to the final model and its outputs and thus exists during the prediction phase.
- **Other attacks**
An interesting approach is presented in DROPFL [328], where three client dropout attacks are discussed. The work discusses cases where adversaries control the upload communication channel of compromised clients without knowledge of the aggregation mechanism. One of the proposed attacks utilizes the Shapley value and aims to identify and eventually drop clients with valuable contributions.

2) Defenses against poisoning attacks

- **Untargeted attacks – Byzantine attacks defenses:** Robust Byzantine-resilient algorithms can converge even in a scenario where a large volume of adversarial attacks is involved. Such attempts to defend include the AUROR [329] algorithm which assumes that most honest participants will have a

similar distribution to the most important features of the model. Using this intuition, it clusters honest participants and discards updates from the outliers. Outliers are participants that exceed a predefined threshold distance. KRUM [330] measures the Euclidean distance between the collected updates and their mean; those with greater distances are discarded. In [331], Median and Trimmed Median, which utilize coordinate-wise median and coordinate-wise trimmed mean, respectively to aggregate the updates and limit the impact of malicious updates. BULYAN [332] presents a similar approach but, in this case, also computes the trimmed median of the collected updates after the outliers have been removed. Robust Aggregation for FL [333] utilizes the geometric median to aggregate the updates. Other attempts focus on different mechanisms to filter out Byzantine participants, such as in [334], which uses the filtering procedure of Steinhardt. In Zen0 [335], a score for each model update is calculated to assess performance gains, with gradients having higher scores coming from honest participants. In contrast to previous methods, Byzantine-Robust Stochastic Aggregation (RSA) [336] adds a term to the objective function to enhance the robustness of the aggregation. In [337], DnC, the authors propose a robust defense mechanism based on Singular Value Decomposition (SVD). The method centers the collected gradient updates and utilizes SVD to calculate the principal component. Client updates with strong deviations from the principal component are considered malicious. Empirical results demonstrate improved performance but also show limitations in highly skewed data distributions among clients, where DnC cannot reliably identify malicious updates due to increased variance in benign updates.

- **Targeted attacks – Backdoor attacks defenses**
Defenses for targeted attacks can be two-fold: methods for detecting a backdoor in a model or sample, and methods that improve the robustness of the method by limiting its impact or removing it. In [338], Robust Learning Rate (RLR) utilizes the sign information in clients' updates to adjust the learning rates of the collected updates during aggregation. Whenever the sum of the signs is below a predefined threshold, the method assigns the negative of the learning rate to move away from the direction of the gradients. Limitations of this work include dependence on the predefined threshold, added computational cost that increases linearly with the number of participating clients, and vulnerability to recent adaptive methods and methods that mimic benign updates. In the work [339] the

authors propose a label inference and a label replacement attack in the VFL with HE setting and demonstrate that labels can be fully recovered if the batch size is smaller than the dimension of the embedded features. To address these attacks, the authors propose Confusional AutoEncoder (CAE) and DiscreteSGD-enhanced CAE (DCAE) which integrates quantization on top of the CAE. The CAE method utilizes an autoencoder where the encoder is used to disguise true labels during training and confuse attackers, while the decoder acts as the final layer of the VFL model during inference. Empirical results demonstrate the effectiveness of the defense methods against specific attacks; however, it is a gradient-based defense and might be vulnerable to attacks that follow different strategies. In addition, training an autoencoder introduces computational overhead that could limit the scalability of the defense and its application to resource-constrained devices typical of the cross-device setting. In LOCKDOWN [340], the authors extend the pruning-based defense mechanism of centralized learning to FL. The key challenge in applying such mechanisms is that, in FL, the poisoned parameters do not exhibit significant statistical differences compared to benign ones. The authors propose an extension to pruning-based mechanisms, utilizing isolated subspace training to decouple the malicious parameters. In addition to the benefits on defense subspace training can also reduce communication overhead and model complexity, aspects that greatly improve efficiency of FL systems. Empirical results demonstrate that LOCKDOWN outperforms KRUM and RLR as it achieves high reduction of ASR, -83%, with minimal reduction in main task accuracy, -2.7%, while RLR is not able to defend and KRUM reduces main task accuracy by 43%. In FEDBAYES [341], the authors propose using Bayesian statistics to calculate the probabilities of clients' model weights and use them to identify potential malicious updates. The influence of malicious updates is reduced, and their impact is minimized, safeguarding the training procedure. Empirical results are limited, and other defense mechanisms are not used as baselines. In addition, a gradient-based method might be vulnerable to novel attacks. In FEDGAME [342], the authors propose a game-theoretic framework. The method assigns different weights to each client update based on a genuineness score. The minimax game involves the defender (server) on one side and the attacker on the other. The defender aims to reverse engineer the aggregated backdoored model and based on that to minimize the genuine score for the malicious clients and maximize it for the benign ones. Conversely, the attacker aims to maximize

the scores of the attackers and minimize those of the benign ones. The method involves reverse engineering the aggregated backdoored model to infer triggers and target classes, using them to assign genuine scores to the collected updates. The algorithm's success depends on the effectiveness of the reverse engineering method. Unlike other defenses such as FLTRUST, FEDGAME can maintain its effectiveness even without a training dataset from the current task. Instead, a training dataset from a different domain can be used, making the method more applicable to real-world scenarios. Moreover, compared to FLTRUST, the second-best performing defense mechanism, FEDGAME is more robust in cases with an increased number of malicious clients and different trigger sizes. In addition, FEDGAME is not based on similarity measures to detect malicious updates, making the method effective even against novel attack algorithms that modify parameters to mimic benign updates.

- **Detection:** These algorithms are based on the intuition that statistical differences exist between latent representations of backdoor triggers and benign samples [343]–[345].

In FL-DETECTOR [346], the authors propose a detection mechanism based on expected client updates and clustering. In each round, the server predicts the updates of the selected clients and measures the Euclidean distance to the actual update to compute a score for each client. Next, using clustering-based methods on the scores, clients are classified as malicious and excluded from training. Results demonstrate that the method successfully identifies malicious clients and reduces the success rate of the attack while maintaining accuracy. On the other hand, predicting client updates, scoring each client, and clustering in each round add computational overhead and limit the scalability of the method as the number of clients increases. In addition, the method assumes that benign clients exhibit consistency in their updates, which is not the case in online FL. Lastly, the method is prone to sophisticated attacks that utilize evasion techniques. In DEEPSIGHT [347], a sophisticated defense mechanism is presented that combines clustering and deep model inspection techniques, suitable even for large and complex models. The method is based on the observation that for malicious updates to have a high attack impact they should significantly change the direction of the gradients. The defense method is divided into two layers: the first involves identifying malicious updates, which forces the attacker to use weaker updates to evade detection, and the second uses a clipping method to mitigate the impact of any residual weaker malicious updates. The authors

utilize deep model inspection techniques to measure the data distribution of each client, assuming that malicious and benign data distributions differ. Exploiting the differences between each client's update predictions and global model predictions on random inputs, the authors devise the Division Differences (DDifs) metric and, based on the parameters of the output layer, devise the Normalized Update energy (NEUP) measurement to evaluate the similarity of dataset distributions among clients. NEUP is used to create the Threshold Exceedings metric, which the classifier is based on. While DDifs, NEUPS, and cosine similarity are used by the clustering algorithm to cluster clients with homogeneous data distributions. The results of these two methods are combined to make a final decision for each update collected. Presented results demonstrate the effectiveness of DEEPSIGHT in defending against backdoor attacks on two tasks: an NLP task for text prediction and a network intrusion detection task. In both cases the method reduces backdoor accuracy to zero in contrast to most of the baselines including, DP, Ensemble FL, FOOLSGOLD, Auror, AFA and KRUM. The only baseline method that demonstrates similar performance in terms of backdoor accuracy is FLGuard [348], but it exhibits lower precision in identifying benign updates, which affects the main task accuracy of the method on the NLP task. Notably, FOOLSGOLD [349] also demonstrates good performance in the NLP task, but it is unable to defend in the NIDS task due to the method assuming non-IID data among clients, which highlights the method's limitations in those scenarios. The proposed method efficiently utilizes deep model inspection techniques, which make it suitable for cases with large models. On the other hand, simpler models may pose a limitation to the method. Another limitation arises from the use of classification and clustering of the collected model updates, which hinders the scalability of the system in the presence of large volumes of participating clients. In FLAME [350], the authors propose utilizing dynamic clustering methods based on HDBSCAN to filter out outliers as potential malicious updates. Moreover, the method applies an adaptive clipping method to limit the influence of any update and adds Gaussian noise after aggregation to safeguard privacy while further limiting the impact of poisoned updates that might have evaded detection. Presented results demonstrate that FLAME successfully removes backdoors with minimal impact on the accuracy. The dynamic clustering method can also effectively handle sophisticated attacks utilizing multiple triggers. On the other hand, the method heavily relies on the performance of the dynamic

clustering method used. Moreover, using a clustering algorithm impairs the scalability of the method as the number of participating clients increases. In FEDRRA [351] the authors propose a two layer reputation scoring mechanism and identify as malicious clients that fail to reach a predefined score. In the first layer the DBSCAN algorithm is utilized to cluster client updates, identifying some as points and others as outliers. Outliers are regarded as malicious and are assigned a negative score. In the second layer an external dataset is used to evaluate performance of each update in and combine the performance of the latest update with past evaluations for the second score. The combination of the two layers forms the final score for each client. The method is evaluated in data poisoning as well as model poisoning attacks including, sign-flipping, additive noise and label-flipping attack. Empirical results show that the method consistently outperforms other robust aggregation methods such as KRUM, MULTI-KRUM, Median, and Trimmed Mean, and that the method is robust even in cases where 50% of the clients are malicious in both model and data poisoning attacks. Though the method comes with certain limitations, its success depends on the performance of the DBSCAN algorithm, which relies on significant differences between malicious and benign updates. Recent attack mechanisms have utilized disguising techniques to evade defenses. Moreover, the authors use an external dataset for performance evaluation, which is assumed to have the same distribution as the actual data across clients. This assumption, however, limits the applicability of the method to real-world scenarios. In FEDGRAD [352] the authors leverage the information provided by the gradients of the last layer combined with the clustering characteristics of malicious and benign clients updates to design a detection algorithm. The authors, based on the observation that malicious updates trained on the same task will be more similar and that benign updates in a non-IID setting have high variance in the first rounds of the training designed a soft filter to identify possible malicious updates. Furthermore, after the model converges, a second filter is applied, clustering the model updates into two clusters and identifying which cluster contains the poisoned updates. FEDGRAD reduces backdoor accuracy by at least 6% against KRUM and by 11.22% against RLR in all three attacks conducted using the CIFAR-10 dataset while maintaining the accuracy of the main task. The method is based in the assumption that the malicious updates are similar, which might not be the case considering recent adaptive attacks. Furthermore, the filtering and clustering

based methods could become resource-intensive as the number of clients participating increases. In RECESS [353], the scoring mechanism operates in a proactive manner and considers long-term performance of the clients. In every round the defender constructs a test gradient by scaling down and adjusting the direction of the aggregated parameters of the previous round. The test gradient is constructed in a way to magnify the variance of the malicious updates without affecting benign ones. The scoring mechanism for each client is updated whenever a client sends an update, considering the direction and magnitude of the update relative to the test gradient. Empirical results demonstrate that RECESS improves the robustness of FL systems under several poisoning attacks achieving higher accuracy than other defense mechanisms including KRUM, BULYAN, Trmean, Median, FLTRUST and DnC. There are several limitations to this work, such as the added computational cost on the server which constructs test gradients for each client, calculates score for each client in every round and maintains a gradient score for each one of them making it unfit for the cross-device setting. Moreover, it is vulnerable to adaptive attack mechanisms and in cases where the data distribution is highly skewed, as gradient magnitude and variance might also be high for benign clients.

- **Erasing:** Backdoor defense mechanisms include methods like those in [345] where backdoors are mitigated by clipping using the norm of the updates and adding noise. FOOLSGOLD [349] defends against Sybil attacks utilizing similarity methods to differentiate Sybils from benign participants. Lastly, the Certifiably Robust FL (CRFL) [354] framework has been presented to certifiably train robust FL models.

3) Defenses against privacy attacks

Defense against privacy inference attacks can be a daunting task in the context of FL due to the unique characteristics of such systems, such as data heterogeneity, network connectivity, etc. The three main categories of these defense mechanisms are the following:

- **Homo-morphic encryption (HE):** This technique allows computations to be performed on encrypted data. An additive homomorphic scheme was used by [355] to secure data through encryption against adversaries and to facilitate participation in federated training. Homomorphic encryption is widely used in distributed learning settings, as demonstrated in [356].
- **Secure Multiparty Computation (SMC):**

Secure multiparty computation, as described in [357], provides a protocol for implementing computations among participants who do not trust each other. It was applied in the FL setting and ensured security even in the presence of malicious actors [358].

The work in [359] presents LIPFED, an additive secret-sharing algorithm that preserves privacy through a decentralized aggregation mechanism, protecting both local models and the global model with encryption. In addition, the method utilizes blockchain technology for the detection of malicious clients. The results presented demonstrate that the method can defend against membership inference attacks on both the local and the global models, with performance comparable to Partially-HE across three different sizes of participating clients, 100, 1000, 10000. Specifically, Partially-HE achieves an average attack accuracy of 45.5% and 45.1% for the local and global models, respectively, and LIPFED achieves an average of 48.8% and 47.4% for the local and global models, respectively. However, the true improvement of the method comes from its computational efficiency. Compared to Partially-HE, the only other method that protects both local and global models, this method achieves a significant average reduction of 39.9 seconds (96.77%) in computational time on the clients, while adding only an average of 0.12 seconds on the server for any volume of clients. It is notable that LIPFED's computational time remains relatively stable as the number of clients increases, in contrast to other methods, demonstrating its suitability even for scenarios with large volume of clients.

- **Differential Privacy (DP):** Differential privacy is a mathematical concept that ensures no useful information can be deduced about the presence of a specific sample in the training dataset used to train the model. Several applications in the FL setting have adopted differential privacy mechanisms to ensure privacy in various forms. The three main variations are centralized differential privacy (CDP) [358], [360], local differential privacy (LDP) [361]–[363], and distributed differential privacy (DDP) [364], [365].

In DP-FEDSAM [366] the authors address the performance degradation incurred by integrating Sharpness Aware Minimization (SAM) into DPFL. The key insight is that DPFL leads to a sharper loss landscape, making the model more sensitive to noise. The SAM optimizer in each client forces the optimization algorithm to find a solution in a flat region, making it more robust to noise. Results demonstrate that the method exhibits improved robustness and accuracy, even in non-IID cases.

Specifically, DP-FEDSAM improves accuracy by 1% to 4% compared to DP-FEDAVG and 3% to 4% compared to $Fed - SMP - top_k$. As mentioned previously in the section discussing personalization, the authors of [175], FEDDPA, propose utilizing Fisher information of local model parameters to adapt noise and prevent it from overwhelming the most informative parameters. FEDDPA achieves higher accuracy than DP-FEDSAM, specifically by 2.26% on FEMNIST, 5.01% on SVHN and 0.478% on CIFAR-10 for various values of epsilon. Recent works have focused on improving DP methods, such as in [367]. In this work, the authors utilize mutual information to measure the dependence between the client's data and the model parameters. They adjust the added noise to minimize this dependence, thereby defending against gradient leakage attacks and safeguarding privacy. The method's success relies on the accuracy of estimating the mutual information between training data and model parameters. This estimation must be accurate to avoid degrading performance and lightweight to prevent introducing additional computational burdens that could harm scalability and efficiency. Although the authors propose MINE [368], a fast method for calculating mutual information based on neural networks, it still requires additional computational resources that impact scalability. Moreover, in the context of online FL, where data arrive continuously, retraining MINE whenever new data are available might be impractical. The authors of [369] propose integrating differentially private continuous data release into FL (FL-DPCR) to address the privacy-utility trade-off. The authors identify that the noise added in each round accumulates, leading to an increasing error rate in the model over the long term. To address this, they utilize a BIT-based DPCR model for the Gaussian mechanism (BCRG) to manage the added noise. The empirical results validate that DPCR improves accuracy in the DP FL setting compared to DP SGD. Moreover, the proposed BIT-based DPCR model outperforms other SoTA DPCR models in terms of accuracy, while the added computational overhead is minimal. The proposed method relies on the performance of the DPCR model used and shares any potential drawbacks, such as added computational overhead.

F. Dynamic Conditions

FL has transformed the landscape of AI and ML utilizing decentralized training across multiple devices while preserving data privacy. The application of FL in various domains leverages the collective computational capabilities of various types of devices including smartphones, IoT devices, vehicles, etc. In addition, these devices do not

operate in a specific location and often have the ability to move, changing the conditions that govern them. Thus, FL systems should not only be able to perform with various devices but also adapt to dynamic environments and conditions. Client mobility is a significant factor and could form a category of challenges on its own, but it is intrinsically linked to dynamic conditions and the need for adaptive FL systems. Therefore, it is included as a special case under this category. Dynamic conditions encompass a broad set of challenges that arise from fluctuating conditions in FL systems. These conditions include various factors such as changing data distribution, client participation, and network conditions. The scientific community has been focused on addressing these issues, and the methods proposed can be categorized based on the techniques used during adaptation.

- **Component adaptation.** This category includes methods that adjust algorithms and components to align with changing conditions. Adaptive methods focusing on component adaptation involve adaptive client participation, selecting clients that ensure system efficiency, and methods that add or remove models based on current conditions.
- **Parameter adaptation.** In the dynamic environment of FL systems, fixed parameters are not efficient. Adaptive methods that focus on changing parameters include server configurations such as weighted aggregation, ML model configurations such as model pruning, and training hyper-parameter configurations such as learning rate and local epochs.

Component adaptation

In [370], the authors propose an adaptive client selection strategy, Adaptive Client Selection Personalization (ACSP-FL), with variable number of clients per round. Each client reports to the server the accuracy of the personalized local model on its data and the clients that have lower accuracy than the average accuracy of all clients are selected for the next round. As mentioned above, the number of clients selected is not fixed and is controlled by the average client accuracy, which acts as a threshold. Furthermore the authors decay the number of selected clients as the model converges, which is applied after the mean-based selection and excludes any possible redundant clients. The method utilizing adaptive client selection and client selection decay significantly reduces communication costs while improving convergence time. Specifically, it achieves 92%, 75% and 92% accuracy in each dataset, while the best-performing baseline achieves 89%, 70% and 84% in the same datasets. Significant improvement is demonstrated in terms of communication efficiency especially in downlink communication, from server to clients, due to a significant reduction of the number of participating clients, 30% - 70% fewer clients compared to other client selection methods. However,

the proposed client selection mechanism faces several critical challenges including security and dependence on client performance. Clients with less accuracy indeed can hold knowledge not yet learned but also they may hold low-quality data, leading to degradation of the model. Also, in cases with high heterogeneity the client selection method due to not adequately selecting quality clients might result in suboptimal solutions. Lastly, considering cases of poisoned data and models exhibit reduction in accuracy which could lead to malicious clients dominating the training process. In [371] the authors consider client heterogeneity and the introduction of new clients at a later stage of the training procedure. The authors propose a retain-expand method where each client retains parts of the local model which are highly associated with the characteristics of each client, such as batch normalization layers. In each round the client expands the global model with its retained parameters and proceeds on training using this enhanced model. To address participation of clients at later rounds the authors propose collecting a number of local client updates to be used as a starting point for new clients and integrate themselves to the training procedure faster. The method ensures stability even when new clients are introduced and allows the clients to adapt to the local model and retain characteristics of their data. The FEDREM framework outperformed other FL methods such as Semi-SynFed and FEDPROX, achieving higher accuracy in various scenarios. For example, in the university scenario of the CCTSDB dataset, FEDREM improved accuracy by 3% and 13% over these baseline methods. In contrast to other works the method introduces reasonable complexity without adding any communication overhead, with the only limitation being the need for clients to retain data characteristics. In [372] the authors consider the cluster FL a valuable method used by many methods to address several challenges of FL by clustering clients with common characteristics. The authors address the issue of changing data distributions and propose a method to dynamically adjust clusters in real time, Adaptive Iterative Clustered FL - AICFL. The method includes a dynamic iterative cluster partitioning phase that allows cluster modifications based on current data distributions. Complementary, a cluster addition mechanism is utilized to add new clusters in case that new distinctive clients join the network. The clustering algorithm used utilizes mutual sensitivity which is calculated between the data of each client data and the model of each cluster. Experiments conducted in three settings, static where no dynamic conditions occur, dynamic where a portion of the cluster is periodically dropped, and distribution shift, where after round 74, the data distribution is changed. Empirical results demonstrate the effectiveness of the method since it outperforms baselines in accuracy even in the non dynamic setting. The baselines methods with

comparable performance are FLEXCF [373] and IFCA [217] which achieve similar accuracy for three of the four datasets, MNIST, FashionMNIST and FEMNIST on all settings. However, in the more difficult task of CIFAR-10 FLEXCF achieves only 62-68% on both dynamic scenarios while IFCA and AICFL achieve more than 70% accuracy. AICFL outperforms IFCA on both scenarios achieving 2 to 5% more accuracy. However, the method introduces a high level of communication overhead by broadcasting each cluster model to every client. Additionally, the complexity of the proposed method and the added communication cost limit its scalability in a cross-device setting. Recently, the authors in [374] propose a temporal-based adaptive clustered FL (TACFL) aiming to address changing data distribution via dynamic clustering. The proposed dynamic clustering method is based on the Silhouette coefficient to evaluate the quality of clusters. Clients are grouped into clusters according to the temporal patterns in their data distributions. The empirical results demonstrate the effectiveness of the method to reduce the loss against baselines and against FEDAVG. However, comparative results against FEDAVG on various numbers of clusters depict that the method reduces loss for 2 and 3 clusters but it fails to do so when using 4 clusters. This shows that the method relies on number of clusters and determining the optimal number remains a challenge. In addition, as the number of clients and clusters increases, the complexity of managing and updating them may grow, impacting scalability. The effectiveness of the method relies heavily on the quality and granularity of the available temporal data; poor quality or insufficient data may hinder the clustering process. Lastly, the continuous evaluation of cluster quality may introduce extra computational overhead, which could further impair scalability.

Parameter adaptation In [375] the authors propose AFDT, Adaptive FL for Digital Twin-enabled IIoT, a framework that utilizes deep reinforcement learning to adjust wireless parameters for Industrial IoT with digital twins. These wireless parameters include CPU frequency, bandwidth, and transmission power and are based on real-time feedback from the training process, allowing the system to optimize resource allocation and improve training efficiency. The method achieves a substantial reduction in communication cost of at least 60% against the baselines on three datasets. However, the utilization of DRL in real-world scenarios could be challenging. In addition, the method relies on accurate real-time data for optimal parameter adjustment which is not ensured in IIoT networks.

In [376] the authors propose an adaptive FL system that continuously monitors network dynamics, client participation, resource availability, and model performance. The method focuses on improving the convergence of the FL system involving MEC nodes. The au-

thors propose a multi-agent reinforcement learning system, MAACF, that allows clients to use knowledge from other participants to adjust their learning process optimizing their training procedure. Optimization of training is twofold: first, devices can dynamically adjust their training frequency considering the performance of their local model and network state; and secondly, by optimizing the timing of the aggregation based on client performance and network conditions. In addition, the method considers dynamic participation of clients, the existence of new clients, or clients with rare participation, and integrates a meta-learning approach to allow them to quickly adapt their models. In the empirical results presented, the method achieves comparable or better accuracy than the baselines (FEDAVG FEDAVG(DQN) FEDAVG(DDPG) and AFL) while achieving a significant reduction in resource consumption. Specifically in the use case with the highest heterogeneity among clients the second best performing method is FEDAVG(DQN) with 2.1639 and MAACF consumes only 1.6349, reduction of $1.323 \times$. Even though the method includes an adaptive algorithm that addresses dynamic client resources and clients introduced late in the training procedure, it is still prone to clients losing communication while scalability might pose a bottleneck due to increased complexity and client interactions.

The authors in [243] propose an adaptive asynchronous method with momentum, FEDAA, which dynamically assigns weights for global model updates to optimize aggregation on the server.” (Combine the sentences for smoother flow. The dynamic weight assignment promotes clients with better local models or with faster processing capabilities since those can have a greater impact on the model. In addition, the method integrates momentum during aggregation to leverage past information and improve training efficiency. The results demonstrate that FEDAA achieved a 25% improvement in convergence rate compared to FEDAVG, FEDASYNC, and FEDAA. However, the work focuses on clients with equal quality and quantity in datasets, and it is not evaluated in cases with data heterogeneity. Also, the method considers dynamic client participation but does not consider clients that frequently connect and disconnect.

In [377] the authors propose an adaptive strategy that aims to reduce overall communication costs by allowing the clients to postpone uploading their local updates and wait for more favorable network conditions. The quality of the communication links between the server and clients are continuously monitored and enable the clients to decide the most favorable conditions for them to upload their updates. Due to the asynchronous update of the uploaded parameters local updates have different progress for each client which is addressed by the clients through a dynamic weighting mechanism based on distance metrics and the number of local epochs performed.

The limitations of this work derive mainly from the dependence of the system to accurately assess and predict future network conditions. Failure to predict accurately could lead to suboptimal performance or model staleness due to clients not uploading their updates frequently enough.

Hybrid In [378] the authors propose a method for dynamic resource allocation utilizing a Lyapunov-based optimization framework that balances communication, computation, and learning aspects. The system continuously monitors the system and performance and adapts accordingly. Virtual queues are employed to manage resources and keep track of the learning performance and convergence rate. Based on these queues the method optimizes a function to achieve the best trade off between energy consumption, latency, and performance. The method is adaptive in three areas: client selection, adjusting transmission parameters and distributing computational resources for both clients and the server. Results presented demonstrate that the method achieves lower energy consumption while retaining convergence rate. The main limitation of this work stems from the increased complexity in managing participating clients and assigning resources, which constrains the scalability of the system.

Device Mobility

As identified in the previous section, one particular category of challenges that has significantly emerged arises from domains with mobile devices such as smartphones, smart vehicles, and mobile IoT devices. Mobility, the ability of devices to move or change location, introduces dynamic conditions to FL systems, including:

- Dynamic network topology. Mobile devices are subject to dynamic network conditions. Continuously changing levels of connectivity can lead to delays or even dropouts of participating nodes, affecting the performance of FL systems..
- Inconsistent device participation. Devices move in and out of the coverage area, altering the pool of available clients.
- Dynamic data distribution. Devices moving between areas affect the distribution of data collected, further impacting the quality and consistency of model updates.
- Resources in mobile devices are constrained, including not only computational resources but also communication and energy resources, as mobile devices often connect over unreliable networks and rely on battery power for their operation. Mobile-aware FL systems should consider the capabilities of devices without compromising convergence of the global model.

Client selection

In [379] a mobile-aware FL system is presented for edge caching in a network of vehicles.. The Mobility-aware Proactive edge Caching scheme (MPCF) method proposed considers the dynamic network topology in networks of vehicles and integrates client selection that considers the time each vehicle will be under the coverage of the edge node. The standing time within the coverage area of each vehicle is calculated based on the coverage diameter, the current distance between the vehicle and the edge node, and the speed of the vehicle. The method even though it increases the hit cache ratio, it does not address cases where the standing time of vehicles within coverage might be too short leaving the training procedure without clients. Also it completely disregards the existence of malicious clients. The authors in [380] considers/ the clients to upload unreliable updates either intentionally, poisoning attacks, or unintentionally due to energy and mobility constraints and propose a reputation-based client selection method. The method presented regards a FL system with multiple task issuers where every client can participate to. The method calculates the reputation score utilizing Subjective logic framework. Each task publisher calculates a local score consisting of belief, distrust, and uncertainty of a client based on communication link quality and the number of positive and negative interactions under quality communication links. Each publisher's local reputation score is shared over the blockchain to form the recommended reputation score and combined with the local score form the final score for each client. The proposed method even though effectively excludes malicious and unreliable clients from the training procedure has limitation in the context of scalability since management of scores of clients increases linearly to the number of clients. In addition, the selection scheme depends on reputation scores from past interactions, which adaptive attacks could exploit by introducing poisoned updates in the later rounds of training. In [381], the authors consider an area with multiple access points where clients' network connections change dynamically as they move. The proposed method takes place in 4 phases, client eligibility estimation, the head selection and reinforcement learning transformer (RL-TF) optimization, the client selection and training, and the model migration phase. For client eligibility estimation, a novel metric is presented: the regularity ratio of the data, which is derived from the number of samples divided by the number of distinct locations the client visited. Low regularity ratio depicts either low number of samples or many visited locations while high regularity ratios show that the client has an adequate dataset size and limited visited locations, which leads to improved accuracy. In the second phase the most eligible client is selected as the head and instructed to learn the optimal transformer architecture for use. Results presented demonstrate that the method achieves higher

accuracy in using less time for training and transmission compared to standard FL and ATP-FL (AutoML) [382]. In addition, carefully selecting the number of clients per round and frequency of synchronization can result in substantial reduction in computational and communication overhead by 80% and 96% respectively, with only minor accuracy drop of about 3%. On the other hand, despite the benefits, the method has some limitations that need to be acknowledged. Similar to other cases, the proposed method disregards the malicious scenario and even though the regularity ratio can provide important information about movement and available data of the device it poses a vulnerability which malicious clients can exploit to dominate the selection process and even take over the RL-TF operation. Another limitation of the regularity ratio is that promotes clients with more samples which might introduce bias in the model. In addition, the model complexity in RL-TF can be difficult for devices with limited computational power. In [383] the authors combine the overlapping protocol [384] with a client selection method to address changing conditions related with device participation, dynamic wireless transmission rates and differences in resources. The authors extend the overlapping protocol with the introduction of stalling threshold that limits local iterations to address model staleness and drift. The client selection method proposed considers statistical utility of the clients, as well as communication efficiency, though the communication efficiency considers the latency reduction from applying the overlapping protocol. The method is compared against FEDAVG, DGA [384], and DGApplus with OORT [231], a client selection algorithm. The method achieves higher speedup over FEDAVG $2.1\times$ compared to DGApplus-OORT that achieves a speedup of only $1.2\times$. Interestingly, additional results presented depict that DGA, which does not address model staleness, leads to a substantial increase in memory consumption that could jeopardize the completion of the training procedure.

Adaptive training

In [385] the authors analyze how mobility affects the performance of HFL. The work considers mainly Internet of Vehicles but it applies in any case of mobile devices and provides theoretical analysis and empirical results that demonstrate that mobility introduces a shuffling among clients that has a beneficial effect on the convergence rate and accuracy of training. In addition, they depict that the aggregation period can be adjusted based on vehicle mobility to benefit the training. In [386] the authors propose MOB-FL (FL for Intelligent Connected Vehicles), an FL framework for vehicles. The work focuses on the communication drop-offs and dynamic networks introduced by the mobility of smart vehicles which might lose connection before uploading their updates. The proposed method is able to handle dynamic networks and aims to optimize the

duration of the training round, as suggested also by [385], and the number of local training epochs to enhance resource utilization and improve convergence. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of the method, though it is based on the assumption that vehicles follow a Poisson process which might not reflect real-world traffic that is influenced by various other factors such as traffic signals or bad road conditions.

Adaptive aggregation

In Mobility-Aware Cluster FL (MACFL) [387], the authors consider the issue of clients losing connection with their access points due to changing location, resulting in the exclusion of important training data from the training procedure. MACFL considers the existence of multiple access points with different models and allows clients to upload local updates from one access point to another, ensuring continued contribution to the overall FL training. Furthermore, an attentive weighted averaging approach is proposed, which uses cosine similarity between the client's update and the global model of the AP it is uploaded to emphasize updates that are closer to the global model. Lastly, it further improves the performance of the clients' local models through personalization. MACFL is compared against Hierarchical FL (HFL) and Cluster FL (CFL) and demonstrates higher accuracy (+10%) and a higher convergence rate which is attributed to the stabilized learning procedure due to the attentive mechanism and personalization.

Joint optimization

In Federated Routing and Popularity Learning (FRPL) [388], an FL system is utilized to solve the problem of caching files to small-cell base stations (SBSs) training a content popularity model based on requests from mobile users. However, users can change location, disrupting the efficiency of the system by altering the content requested in each area and the distribution of data. The authors mitigate the issues by splitting areas based on SBS and learning a joint optimization that, in addition to content popularity, also predicts user movement across areas. The results demonstrate that the method reduces network costs and improves efficiency of the cache. In [389], the authors also propose a joint optimization method to address mobility, focusing on optimizing wireless resource allocation and training round time. Their analysis identifies the optimal training round time as being inversely proportional to the average velocity of devices. In the second step the method optimizes wireless resource allocation based on the derived time for the training round. Empirical results considering vehicle velocity reveals that, for fixed round times, accuracy improves when the velocity is below 45 km/h. However, accuracy is negatively affected when the velocity exceeds this threshold. Optimizing training round time addresses this issue and maintains high accuracy (more than 80%) even with a velocity around

150 km/h, while the baselines (fixed, ClusterFL [387], traditional mobility [390]) perform significantly worse.

G. Fairness

FL systems involve diverse clients with different devices, datasets, and demographic origins working towards training a global model. Since the quality and quantity of data, available device resources, and demographics vary, so do their contributions and, in turn, their benefits from participating in the federation. Fairness among clients has emerged as a fundamental aspect for the successful deployment of FL systems in real-world applications where equitable outcomes are essential. As highlighted in [391], achieving a balance between fairness and other aspects of FL, such as privacy, efficiency, and accuracy, is challenging. In this survey, the authors consider the privacy-fairness trade-off and present methodologies aimed at enhancing fairness. Types of fairness include:

- Individual fairness ensures that similar individuals receive similar treatment. It focuses on treating each node or user equally.
- Group fairness pertains to training a model that performs well across predefined groups. It is about balancing outcomes among different groups of nodes..

1) Individual Fairness

The work in [394] considers fairness in the context of horizontal FL. The proposed method, FEDFA, utilizes a fair weighting method in the server during aggregation that assigns weights based on clients' accuracy and their participation frequency. The method is based on the insight that clients with lower accuracy and infrequent participation contribute less information in their updates.

Fairness in the context of vertical FL is considered in [395], which defines a fairness constraint as a threshold with maximum acceptable unfairness. By using the Lagrangian function, the constraint is embedded into the objective function, becoming a min-max optimization problem that is solved using an asynchronous gradient coordinate-descent algorithm.

The work on Ditto [184] considers fairness among heterogeneous clients. The fairness of the model is evaluated based on the performance of the clients' datasets, fairer models exhibit more uniform performance across the network. The method learns personalized models as well as a general global model and uses a hyperparameter λ to balance them. Analysis of the method shows that for a specific λ value, the algorithm minimizes the error on both models.

The work in [396] proposes a client selection method for asynchronous FL that utilizes long-term fairness. The problem is formulated as a MAB problem where each client is an arm and calculates the reward considering the availability of the client. In addition, it creates a virtual queue for each client, which increases every time the client is not selected and decreases otherwise. The method selects clients considering both the reward and the debt selecting clients with high rewards and lower participation.

Another method that considers fairness in client selection is presented in [407], aiming to reduce time spent on model exchange while ensuring long-term fairness. The work proposes utilizing the C^2MAB [408] formulation for client selection. The values considered in the selection algorithm include the time taken from client selection to aggregation, fairness constraints that ensure a minimum average selection rate for each client, the availability of clients as requested before selection, and the fraction of clients that can be selected in each round.

The work proposes using Lyapunov optimization to solve the problem, including the defined constraints. The work in [409] proposes a random client selection mechanism with a fixed fraction of clients that, in combination with reduced batch sizes, alleviates the overrepresentation of clients with large volumes of data.

In [393], the authors consider the trade-off between efficiency and bias introduced by client selection and propose a fair selection mechanism. The proposed selection mechanism separates the training objective into two subproblems and utilizes alternating minimization to solve them.. The intuition for fairness in client selection is that it assigns a threshold for the minimum selection probability for each client.

The work presented in [392] discusses the difficulties of imposing fairness constraints in the setting of heterogeneous FL where the test set is not known and most likely its distribution is different from the training set distribution. Given these insights, the proposed method follows a different approach from existing work. It proposes a fairness-aware agnostic FL (AGNOSTICFAIR) solution that models a minimax game where an adversary tries to maximize the loss of the global objective. The clients are optimized with a re-weighting function to minimize loss on any possible testing dataset that the adversary generates. The adversary is optimized on the server to generate test set distributions that maximize the loss. The method is completed by incorporating the same re-weighting function in the fairness constraint, making it also agnostic to the target test set.

The work in [397], CFFL, considers reputation to ensure model fairness. Clients' reputations are calculated based on the quality of their local updates. In every round, clients receive a personalized global aggregate based on their reputation score.

TABLE 18. Fairness approach evaluation results comparison

Method	Category	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
AGNOSTICFAIR [392]	Individual fairness	Risk difference in Testing Accuracy	+0.0656 (FAIRFL) ¹ −0.03 (FEDAVG) ¹	Adult	FL, FAIRFL
		Risk difference in Testing Accuracy	+0.059 (FAIRFL) ¹ −0.07 (FEDAVG) ¹	Dutch	
E3CS [393]	Individual Fairness	Accuracy	+0.88% (Random) ¹ +0.42% (Random) ₁	EMNIST-Letter CIFAR-10	FEDCS, Random, pow-d
		Accuracy	+4.1% (q-Fair) ¹	Synthetic	FEDAVG, FEDPROX, q-Fair
FEDFA [394]	Individual fairness	Accuracy (worst 20%) ³	+7.67% (FEDPROX) ¹	Femnist	q-Fair
		Accuracy	+5.76% (FEDPROX) ¹		
		Accuracy (worst 20%) ³	+8.49% (FEDPROX) ¹ +0.32% (FEDAVG) ¹	Sent140	
FAIR VFL [395]	Individual fairness	Accuracy	+4.75%	Adult	FedBCD+CEO ⁴
		DPF	+0.01		
		DFN	−0.08		
		Accuracy	+1.63%	Compass	
		DPF	+0.07		
		DFN	+0.09		
		Accuracy	−1.52%	Crime	
		DPF	+0.06		
ASYNC-FL-F [396]	Individual fairness	Accuracy	≈ +0.3% (CS-Fairness)		CS-Fairness, CS-UCB-Q
		Rounds to 70% accuracy (Speedup)	×1.5% (CS-Fairness)		
CFFL [397]	Individual fairness	Fairness ⁵	+18.78% (DSSGD) +24.11% (DSSGD)	MNIST Adult	FEDAVG, DSSGD
		Accuracy	+5.0%	Fashion, MNIST	
DITTO [184]	Individual fairness	Variance	≈ +10.0%		TERM

¹ Improvement over the best performing baseline. (Best baseline)

² Risk difference is used to measure fairness. A fair classifier should exhibit ≤ 0.05

³ Accuracy (Worst 20%) presents the average accuracy of the 20% worst performing clients. It is a measurement used to evaluate the fairness that is achieved.

⁴ Comparison is made against the most fair variant to showcase accuracy improvement on similar fairness.

⁵ Collaborative fairness is quantified via the correlation coefficient between participant contributions and participant rewards. Values fall within $[-1, 1]$ with 1 being the most fair. The improvement in fairness is presented here.

⁶ Measures the excess risk of a client with a specific model. Lower risk indicates higher gains from the FL model.

TABLE 18. Fairness approach evaluation results comparison – continued from previous page

Method	Category	Metric	Improvement	Dataset	Baselines
FOCUS [398]	Individual fairness	FAA ⁶	+0.009 (CGSV) ¹ +0.01 (Ditto) ¹ +0.019 (q-FFL) ¹ +0.002 (Ditto, AFL) ¹	Synthetic MNIST CIFAR Yelp/IMDb	FEDAVG, q-FFL, AFL, Ditto CGSV
RSRA [399]	Individual fairness	Variance Accuracy	+0.008 −4.90%		q=1 (No fairness) q=1 (No fairness)
GIFAIR-FL [400]	Individual & Group fairness	Mean accuracy	+0.84% (Ditto) ¹	Shakespeare	FEDAVG, q-FFL AFL, Ditto
PRIVFAIRFL [401]	Group fairness	ΔEOP ²	+0.03 (FL-DP-SGD) +0.02 (FL-DP-SGD)	ADS ML-1M	FL, FL-DP-SGD
FPFL [402]	Group fairness	FNR gap ³	+0.017	Adult	FL, BMDM-FL, Fair FL, FL + Clip, BMDM-FL + Clip, Fair FLL + Clip, Private FL, BMDM-PFL
FAIRSCAT [403]	Group Fairness	Accuracy EOD ⁴	−5.80% (FEDAVG) −0.026% (Raw VAE)	DSPRITES	FEDAVG, RawVAE
FAIRFED [404]	Group Fairness	EOD ⁴ SPD ⁵ EOD ⁴ SPD ⁵	0.02 (FEDFB) −0.023 (FEDFB) 0.025 (FEDFB) 0.1 (Local)	Adult Adult COMPAS COMPAS	FEDFB, FEDAVG Local, Global RW
Fairness EHR [405]	Group Fairness	TPSD ⁶ APSD ⁷	0.014 (FAIRFED) 0.21 (FAIRFED)	MIMIC-III MIMIC-III	FAIRFED, FEDAVG

¹ Improvement over the best performing baseline. (Best baseline)

² Delta Equal Opportunity. Measures the difference of the True Positive Rates between two groups. It is used to measure fairness.

³ False negative rate (FNR) parity or equal opportunity [406]

⁴ Equal Opportunity Difference.

⁵ Statistical parity

⁶ True Positive Rate Disparity

⁷ Average Positive Score Disparity

Another approach that considers client quality is presented in [398] The work introduces fairness via agent-awareness (FAA) that aims to evaluate the quality of client distributions. FAA is measured by the maximal difference in excess risk between a client and any other client. The excess risk of a client is given by the difference between the local loss of the client and the minimum loss of any other local update.

The work in [399] considers the constraints of the IoT domain and their impact on the performance and fairness of FL systems. Specifically, client scheduling and unreliable communication channels used in the IoT

FL systems hinder performance and introduce bias. The method opts for fairer heterogeneous clients that exhibit consistency which is measured based on the variance of their updates. In addition, a resource budget and the probability of client selection are incorporated to formulate a fairness-aware FL model for a resource-constrained network. Resource constraints in the proposed method include the cost for local training on the clients and the cost for aggregation on the server, the costs are generalized and can be used to model multiple resource costs such as energy and computations required.

The work in [410] considers fairness within the IoT domain. Fairness is ensured by adding noise to the global model shared with each client, based on their contribution to the global model as measured by the deviation of the local model. In addition, it introduces the notion of utility fairness, which aims for clients to have the same learning gain and computation cost.

2) Group Fairness

In [411], the work aims to ensure group fairness without knowing the characteristics of the groups a priori. The work presented formulates and learns a minimax group fairness approach in a federated setting. Additionally, an extra hyperparameter is included that allows balancing the trade-off between utility and group fairness. The work in [401] examines the trade-off between group fairness and privacy in the cross-device setting. The method exploits statistics regarding distribution in clients in a privacy-preserving manner utilizing Secure Multiparty Computation and Differential Privacy. Fairness is guaranteed using the ROC curves of clients and deriving optimal classification thresholds with FAIRLEARN [412]. A semi-centralized approach for group fairness is presented in FAIRSCAT [403]. The work addresses bias induced by heterogeneous data distributions by employing adversarial samples to correct the bias. The bias is corrected by further training the global model using the adversarial samples on the server. The adversarial samples are generated through a Variational AutoEncoder shared among the clients that encodes a portion of the original data. The decoder on the server is responsible for restoring the samples on the server. The method has a significant drawback that requires sharing encoded original samples and might be prone to privacy leakage.

In [404], FAIRFED, the authors propose a debiasing step for the clients. Clients can follow custom debiasing techniques tailored to their data and after training evaluate their local models across various demographic groups and communicate their metrics to the server. The server calculates global fairness and, considering the clients' metrics, assigns heavier weights to the local updates that have similar fairness to the global model. The method exhibits improvement against other local debiasing mechanisms, though it is essential to consider that the performance of the method relies heavily on the performance of the local debiasing techniques applied by the clients. Additionally, sharing information about fairness of the local models with the server might risk the privacy of the clients by revealing sensitive information. The work [405] addresses bias in electronic health records across various demographic groups. The authors propose a framework based on two key components, a debiasing

mechanism and a fair aggregation method. For debiasing, the authors propose the use of adversarial networks to minimize the influence of sensitive attributes, extending their method to non-binary attributes in contrast to FAIRFED. For the aggregation mechanism the method employs fairness metrics to evaluate the performance of each model in various demographic groups and dynamically adjust the weights. The method achieves similar accuracy to FAIRFED but significantly reduces true positive rate disparity and average positive score disparity, indicating better overall fairness. A significant improvement of this work over FAIRFED is the integration of non-binary sensitive attributes, which can be very useful in real-world applications.

3) Other

In GIFAIR-FL [400], both individual and group fairness are considered. The method utilizes a weighting function that assigns heavier weights to groups with higher average group loss. The method can be applied to impose individual fairness just by considering each client as a group.

The work in [410] considers fairness in the IoT domain. Fairness is ensured by adding noise to the global model share with each client based on its contribution to the global measured by the deviation of the local model. In addition, it introduces the notion of utility fairness, which aims for clients to have the same learning gain and computation cost. Recently the work in [413] presents a modeling and analysis for egalitarian and proportional fairness and defines boundaries and conditions to satisfy them in distributed and model-sharing frameworks such as FL. The work presented in [414] proposes complete FedSV an improvement of the FedSV [415] metric which is based on Shapley [416] value to evaluate the data of a client. Complete FedSV addresses the bias introduced when clients with the same local data receive different rewards due to one not being selected during client selection.

Additional metrics associated with fairness evaluation in the context of personalized FL are presented in [417]. Specifically, four metrics regarding fairness are presented and include Average Variance, Cosine Similarity, entropy and Jain's index. All the metrics presented are calculated based on the improvement in client accuracy introduced by the personalized model compared to the global and local models.

4) Findings

The analysis of the methods reveals some key findings.

Importance of fairness: Unfair treatment towards clients could not only harm the objectives and purpose

of the system but also reduce the participation and negatively impact its overall performance.

Complexity of the trade-offs: A constant observation across the methods is that improvements in fairness often come with a cost on other aspects of FL. For example, the RSRA method increases fairness but accuracy is dropped by 4.9%. FAIRSCAT also demonstrates this behavior by improving fairness at the cost of a 5.80% drop in accuracy. This can be easily explained considering, for example, that client selection has been widely used to address several performance-related challenges such as system and data heterogeneity or challenges arising from client mobility. Fair client selection, however, contradicts the notion of selecting only the most suitable clients. Enhancing explainability and fairness in decision-making systems contradicts privacy. Introducing transparency in the training of the model risks exposing sensitive information. Incentivizing clients to participate should not compromise the efficiency of the system with added complexity to the system. Similarly, the insights from [418] underscore the trade-offs between fairness and other key aspects in FL, including performance, privacy, incentive mechanisms, and contribution evaluation mechanisms. The work in [391] also discusses the lack of studies that address both privacy and fairness, further highlighting the trade-off between these fundamental objectives of FL. In [419] the survey focuses on challenges on Vertical FL, though it also mentions that especially in highly regulated fields such as finance and healthcare, it is crucial to have explainable models to ensure compliance and accountability. Again, it is argued that explainability and fairness often contradict privacy preservation.

Context dependency: Another observation is that for many methods the effectiveness of the fairness method depends on the dataset. FAIR VFL, for instance, improves accuracy and fairness significantly in the Adult dataset but not as well in other datasets like COMPAS and Crime. This indicates that fairness might be highly context dependent and different approaches should be used for different types of data.

Tailored metrics: The variety of metrics used to measure fairness in various cases indicates that fairness is a multifaceted challenge. The context and the objectives of a system should be considered for the selection of the evaluation metrics. Diversity in FL systems renders standardized metrics inadequate to capture the important aspects and objectives of every system, so tailored approaches for evaluation should be considered. This also aligns with the findings from [418], [391] where the selection of appropriate privacy and fairness evaluation metrics is also emphasized.

H. Scalability

Following the exploration of the challenges in FL this section focuses on yet another critical aspect: scalability.

Scalability of FL systems is essential for their successful deployment across extensive and diverse networks. With the wide adoption of FL in large contexts, such as mobile devices across the globe or numerous IoT devices in smart cities, the ability of the system to scale becomes crucial for sustainability and effectiveness.

The scalability challenge in FL pertains to the system's capability to handle a growing number of participants and process large volumes of distributed data while maintaining performance in other aspects such as communication efficiency, accuracy, privacy, and fairness. The following studies highlight innovative approaches that reduce computational and communication costs and ensure that the system remains robust and efficient regardless of the number of devices in the network.

In [420] the authors consider the scalability challenges faced by wireless FL solutions. As mentioned in previous sections and in alignment with this study, increasing the number of clients presents several challenges that revolve around communication efficiency, resource allocation, data security, and privacy.

In secure federated submodel learning (SFSL) [421] the authors improve efficiency and scalability with the use of submodels and enhances security with secure aggregation. Clients are allowed to download only the submodel that best fits their data, reducing communication and computational costs.

In FedLess [422] the authors present a serverless approach for FL that supports Function-as-a-Service (FaaS) platforms. The serverless approach allows the system to automatically scale the resources based on demand eliminating the need for manual infrastructure management and enhancing scalability. In contrast to traditional FL systems where idle clients still incur costs, in this approach, these costs are saved, and resources are managed more efficiently.

In ArtFL [423], the authors employ utility-based and multi-scale training, allowing the system to integrate contributions from clients with diverse computational capabilities and data. Multi-scale training involves incorporating data from various dimensions to train the model and aims to learn scale-invariant features. This allows the model to be more robust as it can generalize better on various inputs. The method also employs latency-based dynamic data dropping which drops an amount of data based on training time.

The work in [424] considers large scale IoT system for smart cities. The method employs a multi-level architecture which allows aggregation of model parameters in different entities. Specifically, it allows aggregation on edge, fog and the cloud and achieves to significantly reduce the communication delay between clients and the server. The cloud server benefits from the reduces processing speed derived from the multi-level aggregation.

In addition, this approach allows the incorporation of a wider range of IoT devices, further improving scalability.

In [425], a large-scale traffic forecasting system is presented based on FL and clustering. The method employs clustering of the base stations based on geographical location and traffic trends improving efficiency of the training and reducing communication costs for a single global model. In addition, dynamic clustering is employed to address changing network conditions, allowing adaptation of the model and more efficient resource utilization. In addition, this approach allows the incorporation of a wider range of IoT devices further improving scalability.

In FL-MQTT [426] the authors employ the Message Queue Telemetry Transport (MQTT) protocol for communication between the server and the clients. The MQTT protocol is specifically designed for devices with limited resources, making it well-suited for large-scale IoT systems. In addition, efficiency is ensured by the client selection method used that considers the capabilities and resources of devices, including processing power, battery life, and network conditions.

VIII. Integration with other technologies

The integration of FL with newly emerged technologies aims to enhance capabilities, alleviate challenges and limitations, and further expand applicability to other domains. This section briefly discusses how the integration of FL can be achieved with technologies such as blockchain and quantum computing and the benefits they provide.

A. Blockchain

Blockchain is a decentralized storage system operating without the need for a central authority and maintaining a continuously growing list of records, called blocks. Each block is linked to the previous block via a cryptographic hash. This linkage ensures the integrity and immutability of the data, making it practically impossible to alter any record without breaking the consensus of the entire network. The fundamental architectural attributes of blockchain are: decentralization, immutability, anonymity, cryptographic encryption, and trust-based operation. The integration of blockchain technology with FL introduces several benefits, including:

- **Decentralization.** Due to the inherent decentralization of blockchain, many approaches to decentralized FL adopt blockchain. As already presented in section VI, BESIFL [81], FabricFL [82], BDFL [83] BLADE-FL [84], and Fine-grained FL [79] employ blockchain to realize a decentralized FL system.
- **Security.** The BESIFL [81] method incorporates an accuracy-based malicious client detection mechanism to remove clients that hinder accuracy in combination with a token-based incentive mechanism

that promotes honest contributors. In [427] the authors leverage smart contracts to enforce rules among clients and automatically detect and prevent malicious behavior. In BFL-SA [428], a blockchain-based decentralized FL system is presented. The method utilizes an enhanced secure aggregation method based on a publicly verifiable secret sharing protocol.

- **Incentive mechanisms.** The mechanism in BESIFL [81] rewards tokens to clients based on their contribution to the convergence of the global model. These tokens can be used by the clients to request contribution from other clients incentivizing this way the clients to provide honest updates to improve their local models. Fine-grained FL [79] utilizes a mechanism which provides greater rewards to honest participants and fewer to dishonest ones enhancing participation and security at the same time. Lastly, FLCHAIN [89] proposes an incentive mechanism to increase the participation of reliable clients, improving the efficiency of the system.

However, the integration of blockchain technology with FL also raises some concerns that should be considered in the design and implementation of applications.

- **Incentives:** Often, blockchain-based FL systems use serverless architectures where clients assume roles beyond training, such as miners, aggregators, etc. In such cases, clients may be reluctant to offer their resources when there is no immediate benefit to compensate for their cost.
- **Added latency:** Blockchain introduces additional latency due to mining, so the design of mining and verification operations should consider the scale of the current application. Focus should be given to designs that reduce complexity without jeopardizing security. In addition, techniques that minimize latency and effectively manage resource allocation.
- **Energy consumption:** Blockchain operations, such as consensus mechanisms, not only add latency to the FL system but also consume additional energy. This can be a drawback because the energy requirements can make the operational cost too expensive impairing the feasibility of the system. In addition, energy efficiency should be considered in scenarios where clients operate with batteries.

B. Quantum computing

Quantum computing is an emerging field of computer science that leverages quantum mechanics to solve problems beyond the capabilities of classical computers. Benefits of the quantum computing have given rise to Quantum FL (QFL).

First, we introduce some fundamental concepts in quantum computing commonly used in QFL:

- Quantum Machine Learning (QML) Models are algorithms that combine quantum computing with machine learning techniques, leveraging quantum mechanics to improve or accelerate the training compared to classical machine learning methods.
- Quantum communication networks (QCNs) are networks that use quantum signals to enable secure communication channels based on quantum mechanics.
 - Quantum key distribution (QKD) is a secure communication method that utilizes properties of quantum physics to exchange cryptographic keys with provable security guarantees.
 - Blind quantum computing (BQC) [429] is a protocol that allows a client to outsource quantum computations to a quantum server while keeping the data and computation private.
- Quantum data are information represented in a quantum system, characterized by quantum states such as superposition and entanglement.
 - Superposition is a quantum state where a qubit can exist in multiple states at the same time, unlike classical bits, which are limited to 0 or 1.
 - Entanglement is a quantum phenomenon where qubits are interconnected, meaning the state of one affects the state of the other.
- Quantum Security involves the development of secure communication and computation protocols utilizing quantum mechanics.
- Quantum cryptography involves the use of quantum mechanics, like QKD, to create encryption methods considered unbreakable by classical and non-quantum approaches.
- Secure multi-part quantum computing [430] is the extension of secure multi-party computation to computation with quantum inputs and circuits.
- Quantum differential privacy [431] is the extension of differential privacy in quantum computing.

Several works on QFL have already been introduced by the scientific community. The framework presented in [432] integrates quantum and classical models in a hybrid architecture that allows the federated training of classifiers. The integration is based on variational quantum circuits and classical machine learning techniques allowing the model to leverage benefits from both computing paradigms. The work mentions the limitation of Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) computers, which have limited qubit counts and are prone to errors, restricting the complexity of models that can be used. The authors of QuantumFed [433], adapt the cost function of classical neural network and instead of mean squared error and cross-entropy loss propose using

fidelity to measure differences in states. In [434] a fully quantum FL framework is presented on purely quantum data and using quantum learning employing a quantum convolution neural network (QCNN) in the clients. However, the framework considers practical implications for communication and is designed to work with existing communication channels instead of quantum communication channels. Also, again due to limitation in quantum hardware the method is based on traditional FEDAVG algorithm and not on a quantum equivalent. Another work employing QFL is presented in [435]. Again, in this work, quantum models have been used on the client side, but the complexity of the aggregation algorithms and the immaturity of current quantum hardware prevent the application of quantum aggregation algorithms. These works, along with surveys like [436] on QFL, identify several challenges:

- Limited resources. In noisy intermediate-scale quantum (NISQ) devices the number of available qubits is limited. This constrains clients to training only small local models, introducing a bottleneck for QFL.
- Quantum gate noise. Quantum gate noise is a significant challenge in quantum computing, introduced by the NISQ devices currently available. Training quantum models by the clients will generate noise that will hinder performance.
- Data heterogeneity. Quantum data are inherently high-dimensional, and when combined with the properties of superposition and entanglement, the issue of statistical heterogeneity in FL systems is exacerbated.
- Imperfect QCN operations. Noise introduced by quantum channels, gate operations, or other aspects of quantum mechanics leads to imperfections in the transmission and storage of information. These in turn can hinder performance of FL.

The integration of quantum computing and FL poses a promising direction, offering significant advantages in secure, distributed learning on quantum data. It is evident that QFL is still in its infancy, and several critical challenges remain unsolved, including limitations imposed by current quantum hardware, noise introduced during operation, and data heterogeneity. Addressing these challenges will allow the true potential of QFL to be unlocked.

IX. Future Research Directions

A. Decentralized Federated Learning

1) Management

The central parameter server in CFL allowed the realization of many techniques, such as client selection, that have improved the performance of the systems. In decentralized FL, where a central server does not exist,

standard methods used in CFL are hard to implement. Research in the field should focus on migrating existing techniques to the decentralized setting or devising new ones tailored to the unique characteristics of DFL.

B. Client selection

Analysis of the experimental results on client selection algorithms revealed instability in performance based on the dataset used. Additionally, various methods utilize client selection to address different challenges, including system heterogeneity, fairness, security, and dynamic conditions, making client selection a versatile tool that can be employed to serve multiple purposes and often involves trade-offs. There is a need for more adaptable and universal selection criteria.

C. Resource heterogeneity

1) Asynchronous data heterogeneity

Many of the presented asynchronous methods, such as FEDAAM, do not adequately address the issue of data heterogeneity. Future research should focus on the development of novel adaptive and asynchronous methods that can adequately handle statistical heterogeneity. Methods developed to specifically address these challenges should be adapted and incorporated into these methods.

D. Communication cost reduction

Research has focused mainly on the compression of gradients. Such methods as presented in the previous sections include quantization, sparsification, low-rank compression and hybrid methods. A major disadvantage of these methods is that they assume noiseless communication, which does not coincide with real-world applications. Research should focus on designing gradient compression methods that take into consideration noisy network communications.

E. Dynamic conditions

1) Robust integration of new clients

Methods such as FEDREM and MAACF address the integration of new clients or client dropouts, but challenges remain in stabilizing the training procedure. Adaptive learning rates and aggregation mechanisms that consider new and rejoining clients benefit robustness. Technologies such as meta-learning or transfer learning can help with the adaptation of the global model, while methods derived from personalized FL can help with the integration of new or rejoining clients.

2) Advanced dynamic client selection

Dynamic client selection methods still face security risks. Sophisticated client selection methods that account for

mobility, intermittent participation, and malicious activity are key areas for future work. Solutions that incorporate trust-based mechanism or anomaly detection can help in securing client selection in dynamic conditions.

F. Fairness

1) Multi-objective

The analysis of the performance of various fairness-enhancing techniques revealed that current methods optimize fairness at the expense of other aspects of FL. The methods presented demonstrated up to a 5.80% drop in accuracy, indicating the need for multi-objective optimization frameworks. The empirical evaluation of the methods revealed that fairness may be context-dependent. Techniques like Pareto optimization to balance the trade-offs of fairness could be explored in the fair FL context

2) Diverse applications

The empirical evaluation of the methods revealed that the fairness may context-dependent. The current understanding of fairness trade-offs is limited by the types of datasets commonly used in FL research. To reveal deeper insights into how these trade-offs manifest in different contexts, fair FL research should be expanded and include diverse applications and datasets.

3) Metrics

Fairness analysis revealed a variety of metrics used by different approaches to evaluate the improvement of fairness in a system. This indicates that fairness is a multifaceted challenge, and current metrics may not adequately capture its complexities. Research should focus on the refinement of existing metrics and the development of novel ones that will be able to better capture the real-world implication of fairness in FL. This will facilitate a more accurate assessment of the fairness trade-offs and the development of balanced approaches.

G. Security & Privacy

It is evident that security and privacy preservation in FL systems is not easy; it is a complex problem that involves several challenges requiring careful consideration and expertise to address effectively.

1) Adaptive attacks

Recent adaptive attacks such as 3DFED and A3FL proved to be very effective indicating the potential of further enhancing the adaptive capabilities of attacks. Future research could focus on further improving feedback mechanisms and more sophisticated ways to model the learning dynamics of the global model. RL can be used

to dynamically adapt attack strategies by employing a reward function based on the success of the backdoor. Considering that recent works employ model-agnostic FL allowing the clients to train on a model suited to their capabilities, Neural architecture Search (NAS) can be used to discover and optimize models that are susceptible to attacks or can evade detection.

2) Collaborative attacks

Methods such as DBA and CERP also demonstrated significant effectiveness in bypassing defenses by employing collaboration among the malicious clients. Further refining and advancing collaborative attacks should be explored. Technologies such as game theory, which can model the interactions between malicious clients and the server as a strategic game, federated reinforcement learning, which can train a group of malicious clients and based on feedback mechanisms learn effective strategies, and swarm intelligence, which will enable clients to adjust their attacks based on the observed effectiveness of each client's update.

3) Data-free attacks

Recent attacks such as FBA-PI and DARKFED introduce a novel approach to backdoor attacks that does not require a dataset to work. These attacks are closer to realistic scenarios where having a dataset representative of the true data distributed among clients is often not feasible. More advanced GANs to generated even more realistic and effective adversarial data could be explored.

4) Adaptive Defense Mechanisms

The evident limitations of methods with predefined hyperparameters or thresholds, such as Robust Learning Rate, the improved performance of adaptive defenses, and the recent development of adaptive attack strategies suggest the need for more adaptive defense methods.

5) Enhanced detection

An open challenge identified by the literature is the use of large models and Byzantine-robust aggregation algorithms. The large size of a model allows adversaries to add small but effective changes and remain undetected. The performance of DEEPSIGHT on successfully defending attacks against large models indicates the usefulness of deep model inspection techniques. The development of efficient algorithms for deep model inspection and gradient analysis for anomaly detection will play a significant role in defense. Additionally, the combination of different types of defense creating a multi-layered approach also demonstrated robustness against attacks.

Hybrid approaches can be utilized to cover the weakness of individual techniques.

6) Data auditing

Data and behavior auditing are usually overlooked in a FL system even though many attacks can be mitigated before compromising the training procedure. Data quality assessment methods and client trustworthiness measurements prior to the training procedure can be devised to defend against adversarial clients and servers.

7) Scalability and efficiency in defense mechanisms

Applying a defensive mechanism without incurring some type of cost to the system is very challenging. Many defense mechanisms, such as Confusional AutoEncoder (CAE) and DiscreteSGD-enhanced CAE methods, while effective, introduce computational overhead, rendering them unsuitable for large-scale and resource-constrained environments. The development of lightweight defense algorithms that maintain their effectiveness while reducing computational requirements is a significant and on-going research direction. The focus should be given in employing model optimization techniques such as knowledge distillation to compress the model or NAS to discover optimal architectures for constraint environments.

H. Blockchain-based FL

1) Incentive mechanisms

The incentive mechanisms are not fully optimized to encourage consistent and meaningful participation from all clients. Additionally, dynamic conditions affect willingness of clients to participate. There is a need for more sophisticated mechanisms that align incentives with the multifaceted goals of the FL systems and can adapt to clients conditions such as available resources and network status.

2) Lightweight and Efficient

Existing approaches do not fully address the latency introduced by the consensus mechanism. There is a need for methods tailored for FL systems that reduce the complexity of mining and verification processes without sacrificing security.

3) Energy efficiency

Energy consumption is identified as a challenge in the application of blockchain-based FL systems. However there is a gap in the development of systems that consider both security and energy-efficiency. The development of energy-efficient blockchain protocols, especially in scenarios involving battery-powered devices is an underexplored area. Techniques such as selective participation

in mining based on energy levels or the use of off-chain solutions to reduce on-chain transactions could be further explored.

I. Quantum computing

1) Quantum Gate Noise

Quantum gate noise is a critical issue and can significantly hinder the training of quantum models in QFL, where noise can accumulate in every round. There is a need for the development of noise mitigation and error-correcting methods. Recent technologies that should be evaluated in the context of QFL are surface codes, dynamical decoupling and zero noise extrapolation.

2) Quantum Data Heterogeneity

Quantum data are high-dimensional and exacerbate the problem of data heterogeneity in FL. Methods developed to address statistical heterogeneity in ordinary data might not be adequate to address the challenges presented by quantum data. Novel approaches to handle statistical heterogeneity in high-dimensional and complex quantum data in the QFL setting are needed.

3) Quantum aggregation algorithms

QFL methods have focused on employing quantum models but most of them rely on classical algorithms for the aggregation of the models in the central server due to the immaturity of quantum aggregation algorithms. The development of quantum aggregation algorithms that can efficiently aggregate quantum models, considering the unique characteristics of quantum data, is a crucial research direction.

4) Integration of quantum communication channels

Most of the presented QFL methods do not utilize quantum communication channels mainly due to their immaturity. With the advance of quantum channels and communication protocols, methods that fully integrate quantum communication channels and leverage their benefits, such as quantum key distribution for security, is essential towards unlocking the full potential of QFL.

J. Federated Analytics

Statistical heterogeneity in the Client Data remains a critical challenge in the FL systems. Many solutions have been focused on discovering clients with similar data distributions and providing a model for each cluster. Other methods utilized various distance metrics to evaluate heterogeneity in client distributions but the analysis of the clients' data distributions in a privacy-preserving manner is still an open issue. The distributed analysis of data termed as Federated Analytics is a promising

research direction since it can provide a solution to many challenges in the FL context. Such solutions are not limited on addressing only the statistical heterogeneity but can provide benefits in fairness and security.

K. Data Sampling

Data sampling has been extensively used to improve the performance of centralized learning, though standard data sampling techniques cannot be used in the context of FL where the data are distributed and private. Data evaluation methods can address many data-related problems like heterogeneity, poor quality data or the existence of polluted and noise data. Novel methods in Federated Analytics can provide the base for new data evaluation and sampling methods in the context of FL setting.

1) Benchmarks

The various contradicting aspects of FL pose difficulties in discovering the appropriate methods or the methods that truly improve performance. Evaluation of proposed methods should consider all aspects, such as communication and computation efficiency, privacy and security, fairness, accuracy, adaptability, etc. The evaluation of FL algorithms should be standardized offering cost-benefit analysis between trade-offs allowing researchers and practitioner to distinguish methods suitable for the characteristics of the problem and setting.

X. Conclusion

This survey first identifies limitations on existing surveys in the field of FL then extends the existing taxonomy introducing the architecture taxonomy for centralized and decentralized settings. The survey further elaborates on the differences between centralized and decentralized learning, showcasing strengths and limitations while also highlighting challenges that arise exclusively in decentralized settings due to the absence of a central server.

The survey also delves into the various aspects of FL systems and the inherent challenges that persist irrespective of the chosen architecture. A taxonomy for these challenges is presented, along with an attempt to categorize the solutions proposed by the scientific community whenever feasible.

Finally, the survey identifies future work opportunities in traditional challenges such as communication cost, security, and data sampling; challenges presented exclusively in decentralized settings; as well as novel paradigms that include adaptive systems to address challenges due to changes and dynamic environments, multi-modal FL that will allow the aggregation of knowledge from more clients, and online FL that will allow seamless integration of FL systems in continuous streams of data.

In essence, this survey can serve as an exploration of the current landscape of the overall research in FL

presenting the strengths, challenges and potential directions for advancing FL systems. In addition it can serve as a reference point for a quick comparison of established methods for each challenge met in FL enabling the reader to quickly familiarize with the state-of-the-art methods identified by the scientific community, the baseline methods used to evaluate the reported methods and the improvements that each method introduces. Through these two aspects, the survey ultimately aims to contribute to the evolution of collaborative and privacy-preserving machine learning algorithms like FL

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TABLE 19. Abbreviations table. Part A.

Abbreviation	Definition
FL	Federated Learning
ML	Machine Learning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IoT	Internet of Things
IoV	Internet of Vehicles
IoBT	Internet of Battle Things
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
DFL	Decentralized FL
CFL	Centralize FL
ESN	Echo State Networks
ADMM	Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers
SAM	Sharpness-Aware Minimization
QFL	Quantum FL
PVSS	Publicly Verifiable Secret Sharing
SHE	symmetric homomorphic encryption
SIMD	Single Instruction Multiple Data
PoF	Proof of Federation
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic curve
NCCB	Neural Combinatorial Contextual Bandit
RACE	Repeated Arrays of Count Estimators
DoN	Degree of non-IIDness
DFP	Dynamic Fisher Personalization
MTL	Multi-task Learning
KD	Knowledge distillation
UMAP	Unified Manifold Approximation
DDPG	Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient
EF	Error Feedback
ASR	Attack Success Rate
GAN	Generative adversarial network
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition
RL	Reinforcement Learning
FaaS	Function-as-a-Service
QCNN	Quantum Convolution Neural Network
RL	Reinforcement Learning
IDS	Intrusion detection systems
TACFL	Temporal-based adaptive clustered FL
MPCF	Mobility-aware Proactive edge Caching scheme
MACFL	Mobility-Aware Cluster FL
FNR	False negative rate
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IoBT	Internet of Battle Things
UAVs	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
ADMM	Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers
ESN	Echo State Networks
DAC	Decentralized Average Consensus
PoR	Proof of reliability
TWDM-PON	Time and Wavelength Division Multiplexing Passive Optical Networks
PVSS	Publicly Verifiable Secret Sharing

TABLE 19. Abbreviations table. Part B

Abbreviation	Definition
SHE	Symmetric homomorphic encryption
E-G	Eschenauer-Gligor
NCCB	neural combinatorial contextual bandit
KL	Kullback-Leibler
DoN	degree of non-iidness
MLSF	Multi-Leader Single-Follower
DFP	Dynamic Fisher Personalization
MAML	Model-Agnostic Meta-Learning
ARUBA	Average Regret-Upper-Bound Analysis
GKR	Global Knowledge Representation
CFL	Clustered FL
IFCA	Iterative Federated Clustering algorithm
UMAP	Unified manifold approximation
EDC	Decomposed Cosine similarity
WFLN	Wireless FL Network
QuAFL	Quantized Asynchronous FL
DDPG	Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient
HSQ	Hyper-Sphere Quantization
TTQ	Trainer Ternary Quantization
EF	Error feedback
LM	Lloyd-Max
SBC	Sparse Binary Compression
GGs	General Gradient Sparsification
LSS	Layer-wise Similarity Sparsification
FD	Federated Distillation
SIA	Source Inference Attack
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition
CAE	Confusional AutoEncoder
DDif	Division Differences
NEUP	NormalizEd UPdate energy
CRFL	Certifiably Robust FL
HE	Homo-morphic encryption
SMC	Secure Multiparty Computation
DP	Differential Privacy
CDP	Centralized differential privacy
SAM	Sharpness Aware Minimization
RL-TF	Reinforcement learning transformer
HFL	Hierarchical FL
FRPL	Federated Routing and Popularity Learning
SBS	Small-cell base station
SFSL	Secure federated submodel learning
MQTT	Message Queue Telemetry Transport
QFL	Quantum FL
QML	Quantum Machine Learning
QCNs	Quantum communication networks
QKD	Quantum key distribution
BQC	Blind quantum computing
NISQ	Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum
QCNN	Quantum convolution neural network

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